

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D1.2 System Specifications and Architecture

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Table 1: Glossary

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
5G PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMC	Autonomic Management and Control
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AN	Autonomous Networks
API	Application Programming Interface
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
CACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CB	Context Blueprint
CD	Continuous Deployment
CI	Continuous Integration
CNF	Container-based virtual Functions
CTXBs	Context Blueprints
DE	Decision-making-Element
DNS	Domain Name System
E2E	End to End
EC	European Commission
ELCM	Experiment Life-Cycle Manager

eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EXPBs	Experiment Blueprints
EXPDs	Experiment Descriptors
Exp_ID	Experiment ID
GANA	Generic Autonomic Networking Architecture
gNB	gNodeB
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSMA	Global System for Mobile Association
GST	Global Slice Template
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HCI	Hyper Converged Infrastructure
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
HW	Hardware
ID	Identification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
INT	Interoperability Testing
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
IWF	Interworking Framework
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTE	Long Term Evolution
M2M	Machine to Machine
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
mIoT	Massive IoT

ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNOs	Mobile Network Operators
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
NAB	NetApp Blueprint
NBI	North-Bound Interface
NEF	Network Exposure Function
Netapp	Network Application
NetOps	Network Operations
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVI	NFV Infrastructure
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NR	New Radio
NRF	NF Repository Function
NRS	Name Resolution Service
NS	Network Service
NSD	Network Service Descriptors
NSO	Network Services Orchestrator
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NSSI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
OAS	Open API Specification
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturers
ONAP	Open Networking Automation Platform
OSM	Open Source MANO
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PPP	Public Private Partnership
QoS	Quality Of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology

REST	Representational State Transfer
RRM	Radio Resource Management
SA	Standalone
SB	Service Blueprint
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SBI	South-Bound Interface
SCEF	Service Capability Exposure Function
SDN	Software Defined Radio
SEAL	Service Enabler Architecture Layer
SgNB	Secondary gNB
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
SotA	State-of-the-Art
SST	Slice/Service Type
SW	Software
T&L	Transport and Logistics
TaaS	Testing as a Service
TCB	Test Case Blueprint
TMV WG	Test Monitoring and Validation Work Group
UC	Use Case
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDR	Unified Data Repository
UE	User Equipment
UK	United Kingdom
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VA	Vertical Agnostic
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network

VNF	Virtual Network Function
VNFD	VNF Descriptor
VNFM	VNF Manager
VS	Vertical Specific
VSF	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
VxFS	Veritas File System
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.2 “VITAL-5G system specifications and architecture” is the second deliverable of the WP1 “Use Cases, Requirements Analysis and Architecture”. Based on the WP’s objectives and use case requirements stated in T1.1, the report includes the outcomes from T1.2 and T1.3 providing a detailed description of VITAL-5G’s platform characteristics and architecture design.

The objective of this deliverable is to define an open service validation platform using real-life resources and facilities to validate T&L related solutions and services to offer a trusted and secure service execution environment under realistic conditions. Based on the information captured from the use cases the platform validates the functionality of the system to test and verify their T&L related cutting-edge Network Applications (NetApps) with vertical specialized facilities and infrastructure through an open service validation platform.

D1.2 includes a complete and exhaustive description of the following packages:

- Detailed specifications of the requirements, components, and architecture of the VITAL-5G open platform.
- The open online repository, its mechanism (VNF/NetApp creation, onboarding, deployment, management, etc.), KPIs collection and internal tools.
- Design of the VITAL-5G facilities (5G network, cloud and edge infrastructure) and the supported interfaces, APIs and interconnections.

This detailed description of the VITAL-5G platform will be used in WP2 and WP3 to develop the end-to-end system components and define their integration design.

1. Introduction

T&L has become increasingly complex over the past years, as collection and analysis of enormous amounts of data must be completed in real time. Cameras, sensors, and other interconnected devices have to communicate across a network with an uninterrupted connectivity and large swaths of bandwidth. To overcome this complex transformation, VITAL-5G will embrace 5G technology to design a set of innovative Vertical T&L NetApps and vertical-agnostic NetApps associated with an open repository and a service orchestration platform to create an enhanced 5G experimentation facility.

To this end, D1.2 describes all the necessary components to be set up to create an open validation platform for advanced multi-modal logistics services to automate freight transport. Three 5G testbeds will be integrated in the platform to validate their T&L related solutions and services utilizing real-life resources and facilities. In addition, the platform will be designed to ensure third parties can readily engage with the platform and other available VITAL-5G resources to conduct their own experiments.

This document provides a detailed description of the requirements analysis and specifications of the online platform and the open repository and their mechanisms. This report covers the 1st version of the end to end VITAL-5G system including the architecture of all involved components.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 2: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Section(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T1.2 VITAL-5G Platform functional requirements analysis & specifications	This task is responsible for the detailed description of the characteristics that VITAL-5G platform must have based on WP's objectives and Use case requirements stated in T1.1	Section 4 Section 6	In Section 4 there is a general description of the platform requirements In Section 6 there is a detailed explanation of the platform architecture
	The purpose is to create an open service validation platform utilizing real-life resources and facilities to validate T&L related solutions and services, offering the user a trusted and secure service	Section 3	Section 3 describes VITAL-5G's platform experimentation services and involvement of third parties in each use case

	<p>execution environment under realistic conditions.</p>		
	<p>The platform will capture information from use cases in order to verify the functionality of the software: business rules, reporting requirements, authorization levels, external interfaces, historical data management, etc.</p>	<p>Section 6 Section 7</p>	<p>Section 6 describes high-level workflows and procedures, while Section 7 contains a support of VITAL-5G uses cases</p>
	<p>The description will include detailed specifications of the online platform and the open repository and their mechanism (VNF/NetApp creation, onboarding, deployment, management, etc.) as well as the supported interfaces, APIs and interconnections</p>	<p>Section 5 Section 7 Section 8</p>	<p>A detailed description of the NetApps and T&L services is stated in Section 5 Section 7 offers an account of the services and interfaces from VITAL-5G facilities and its management, orchestration and monitoring. Finally, Section 8 include the specification of the platform components (VITAL-5G portal and Open online repository) and its internal tools</p>
<p>T1.3 VITAL-5G platform and 5G-testbed Architecture design</p>	<p>This task is responsible for deriving the VITAL-5G end-to-end conceptual architecture based on the requirements and specifications established on T1.1 & T1.2, and the 5G-testbed integration approach.</p>	<p>Section 6</p>	<p>Section 6 describes VITAL-5G architecture and the VITAL-5G Platform, in particular, with details on its interaction with the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>
	<p>[...] elaborate a fine grained architecture description, containing the description of all the functional blocks and the high-level interfaces among them.</p>	<p>Section 6 Section 8</p>	<p>Section 6 introduces the functional components of the architecture and describes the workflows for their interaction, as well as the NBI and SBI or the VITAL-5G platform. Section 8 provides the details of the single architecture components.</p>

	[...] defining the architectural interfaces for: i) the NetApps and VNF Package catalogues: defining the information models, the high-level workflows and the access-based collaboration procedures	Section 5 Section 6 Section 8	Section 5 provides the information models of the NetApp package and blueprint. Section 6 (section 6.3.4.1) provides the workflows for the onboarding of new NetApps. Section 8 (section 8.2) provides the details of the Open Online Repository with NetApp, Vertical Service and Experiment catalogues.
	[...] ii) the interfaces, workflows and components for AI and ML based lifecycle management	Section 8	Section 8 (section 8.1) describes the components for service monitoring, analytics, AI/ML-based performance diagnostic and logic for service lifecycle management.
	[...] the definition of the mechanisms for VNF licensing and validation to be used within the project	Section 8	Section 8 (section 8.2.3 and 8.2.4) describes the components responsible for licensing management and NetApp blueprints validation. The components for experiment management and experimental evaluation of NetApps and services are described in section 8.1.
	From the 5G-testbed design perspective this task will develop the integration approach in terms of platform and use cases.	Section 7	Section 7 provides a generalized model for the design of VITAL-5G testbeds and facilities, explaining the specific support for VITAL-5G use cases in section 7.4.
DELIVERABLE			
D1.2 VITAL-5G system specifications and architecture			
Report on the specifications of the 1 st version of the E2E VITAL-5G system including the architecture of all involved components.			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

WP's objectives and use case requirements stated in T1.1 (D1.1)[1] have been the starting point of T1.2 and T1.3, responsible for delivering the detailed description and architecture design of the VITAL-5G platform within this document (D1.2). In order to contextualize the uptake of 5G in Europe by providing E2E facilities that validate the performance of new 5G technologies by operating trials of advanced vertical sector services, the report starts with a State of the Art analysis in Section 2.

In Section 3, experimental services from VITAL-5G are described, including involvement of third parties in each use case. Section 4 describes the open platform requirements and VITAL-5G services, while Section 5 elaborates a thorough explanation and categorization of the NetApps packages, format and composition. Following the NetApp section, Section 6 provides the architectural principles of the VITAL-5G platform, with a high-level description of the workflows, procedures and functional architecture. Section 7 reflects the study and work done regarding the design of VITAL-5G facilities and their architecture, followed by Section 8, which contains a fine-grained description of the platform components:

- VITAL-5G portal
- Open Online repository
- Platform internal tools and the web-based GUI

This section will act as input to WP2 and WP3 for the VITAL-5G platform and testbeds implementation and their end-to-end system integration.

Finally, to close the document, Section 9 provides the conclusions of D1.2.

2. State of the Art Analysis

VITAL-5G aims to utilize the existing resources and knowledge from previous 5G PPP projects (e.g., 5G EVE¹, 5GSOLUTIONS², 5G-Blueprint³) as well as other relevant projects and commercial assets to create innovation in support of a significant 5G enablement for the T&L sectoral actors. In addition, VITAL-5G will overcome critical limitations identified regarding the adoption of 5G in production services by T&L industry verticals: 1) a network-centric vision on 5G orchestration tools, 2) a substantial mismatch of backgrounds exists between Telcos and Verticals (from Phase II and Phase III), and 3) packages for 5G/NFV experimentation which are network-only services or apply to small trial experiments. Moreover, orchestration and network slicing platforms available in state-of-the-art (both in the form of design artefacts and prototypes/products) do not provide high level interfaces for allowing T&L verticals to design and deploy services in a completely automated and autonomous manner.

The VITAL-5G project will go beyond these gaps and limitations by addressing specific R&D innovations:

- Enhancements to Intent-Based APIs for NetApps: translation of high-level T&L-oriented intents in to 5G network components / VNF and NetApp deployments and configurations. Provide the functionality extensions to the intent-based APIs in order to accommodate the more complex multi-vertical environment of the VITAL-5G trials.
- Platform-agnostic vertical slice design and control for NetApps: VITAL-5G's portal logic for managing networks slices will allow for translating application requirements into specific descriptors for the virtualized 5G infrastructure and for defining the proper resources and intelligent placement within the allocated slice (adapted dynamically through automated orchestration mechanisms according to the service's lifecycle behavior).
- Advanced KPI Analytics & Diagnostics tools for NetApps: VITAL-5G will integrate KPI validation for service performance evaluation and benchmarking towards business SLA verification. Vertical services will be evaluated in a business-oriented perspective. Data from automation of operations collected will be available for further analysis and can serve as a basis for comparison in further similar NetApp implementations.
- Reusability of the 5G EVE and the 5G-Blueprint 5G facilities: VITAL-5G plans to reuse and extend the 5G EVE and 5G-Blueprint infrastructures and benefit from the technology updates in their roadmap.
- Replication in non-ICT-17 5G facilities: VITAL-5G will integrate each one of the three facilities with the VITAL-5G main platform by replicating the instantiation of the Service Portal in each of them and allowing connection to the Open Online Repository.
- Seamless integration of 5G-powered devices for freight logistics (vessels, robots, AGVs): VITAL-5G will enhanced versions of current devices that use 5G connectivity for their communications and integration with edge computing for localized latency-sensitive application workloads.
- VITAL-5G Open Online Repository & NetApps: VITAL-5G will implement a NetApp repository capable of onboarding packages, with extended role-based access controls to limit the visibility and actions on packages based on user's roles and additional policies.
- NetApps for T&L sector: Development of 13 Vertical-Specific NetApps to address specific industry challenges of the three facilities.
- Vertical-agnostic NetApps: development of 5 Vertical-Agnostic NetApps which can be utilized by multiple participating parties in a variety of vertical use cases.

¹ <https://www.5g-eve.eu>

² <https://5gsolutionsproject.eu/>

³ <https://www.5gblueprint.eu/>

2.1 Validation Platforms and Testbeds for 5G Services

VITAL-5G is part of the 5G PPP family of projects and as such, it is a natural follow-up of multiple innovative initiatives before it. In order to maximize the output produced by the project, the partners of VITAL-5G focus their effort on the innovative NetApp based solutions for the T&L sector, as much as possible, instead of trying to “reinvent the wheel” and to create an experimentation platform from scratch. This is only possible, by taking advantage of the accomplishments, know-how and expertise of the 5GPPP projects that preceded VITAL-5G, in terms of experimentation platform set-up, 5G network & vertical integrations, monitoring, result collecting and results analysis, etc., allowing VITAL-5G to build on-top of previous innovations. Figure 1 depicts the 5G PPP projects Heritage figure, indicating the links among the various projects up until March 2020.

Figure 1: 5G PPP Projects Heritage [2]

The VITAL-5G partners have strong links with multiple of the predecessor projects, especially with ICT-17 and ICT-19 projects. Significant know-how, components (HW & SW) and operational and experimentation management expertise is utilized from these projects, enabling the re-use of available elements and procedures, hence speeding up the delivery of VITAL-5G outputs, avoiding past development, deployment and experimentation mistakes and allowing for the further evolution of the provided solutions to verticals. More specifically, from ICT-17 projects a large amount of information and components is inherited with regards to experimentation platform development, deployment and utilization, trial facilities interconnection and operation and experimentation tools usage. Besides the close relationship of VITAL-5G with 5G-EVE (multiple common partners), all three ICT-17 projects are extremely relevant for VITAL-5G, as they were the pioneering

project in terms of deploying, configuring and allowing experimentation over advanced 5G testbeds in Europe, and as such multiple lessons can be learned from their experience. For this reason, the approach of 5G VINNI and 5GENESIS, are also analyzed in this section (along with 5G-EVE). From the ICT-19 projects, significant expertise and some tools are inherited to support the verticals’ application integration within the experimentation platform, the support of vertical experimenters and the execution of extensive measurement and trial campaigns. The remainder of this section highlights the VITAL-5G relationship with some of the key predecessor projects, from which a significant amount of expertise, knowledge and components are drawn.

2.1.1 5G EVE

5G EVE is an H2020 ICT-17 project (July 2018 – June 2021) that built a European 5G validation platform for extensive trials of vertical services in advanced 5G infrastructures. The project created a multi-site 5G end-to-end facility developing and interconnecting four sites in Greece, Spain, Italy and France that has been extended further with Romanian cluster to give 5G experimenters the possibility to validate their services in a variety of operational conditions. The 5G EVE facility is still used for several trials and pilots from ICT-19 projects, addressing the requirements of different business sectors like smart factory, transport, city, farming, tourism, multimedia, etc. The facility has also been extended with additional sites to reach new areas and guarantee the 5G coverage in the various target premises (e.g., factories, museums, etc.) where the pilots are executed.

5G EVE offers a complete set of experimentation services, supporting vertical service developers and providers along all the steps of validation procedure, as represented in the workflow depicted in Figure 2 [3]. The initial phases of test design and test preparation usually require the direct interaction between experimenters and 5G EVE technicians in order to identify particular service requirements, customizations and/or additional hardware and infrastructure setups that would be needed for the particular validation campaign. The test design is facilitated through blueprints that provide a common template to define services and experiments, with the possibility to reuse tools from the 5G EVE portfolio, e.g., to reproduce variable environment and network conditions, and to on-board new application components. The preparation phase allows to customize the experiment settings and schedule the testing campaign in the selected testbed, so that the site administrator can take care of the environment and infrastructure configuration, which may involve manual interventions (e.g., for the installation of additional hardware, the reservation of some resources, etc.).

Figure 2: 5G EVE Experimentation Services

The two following phases are mostly automated and they can be triggered and controlled directly by the experimenters through the 5G EVE portal or programmatically via open interfaces. At the execution time, the service is instantiated on the virtual environment and properly configured through the orchestration functionalities of the platform. Moreover, the retrieval of the monitoring data is activated and the test scripts

defined for the experiment are automatically started, collecting the related results. During the test execution, metrics, logs and KPIs are collected and made available for the experimenters to facilitate the analysis of the experiment progress. At the final validation time, the collected data are analysed through automated tools available in the 5G EVE platform for results analysis and diagnostics, providing the experimenters with reports about the obtained performance and, when degradation is detected, the identification of possible root causes. VITAL-5G inherits most of the 5G EVE concepts, workflow and methodology for the experimental validation of vertical services. VITAL-5G will extend the work of 5G EVE integrating the concept of NetApps and applying the 5G EVE experimentation procedures to services composed of NetApps, taking into account their additional characteristics, e.g., their dependencies and interactions with particular IoT and hardware devices, for the monitoring and control of the elements involved in a T&L service.

The 5G EVE architecture is depicted in Figure 3, identifying the components available in each 5G facility (represented in green) and the functional elements of the 5G EVE platform (represented in orange). In particular, the 5G EVE Interworking Framework (IWF) is the layer that unifies the access to the different 5G EVE sites and enables the orchestration of services with components deployed over multiple sites and interconnected together [3]. On top of the IWF, the web-based 5G EVE Portal provides the single access to all the experimentation tools and functionalities offered by 5G EVE. The Portal services include the onboarding of the experiment blueprints, the creation and configuration of experiment descriptors, the instantiation of new services and the launch of their experimental testing, the visualization of the collected monitoring data and the analytics and diagnostics reports.

Figure 3: 5G EVE Architecture

The VITAL-5G platform will capitalize on the 5G EVE architectural concepts, with particular reference to the unified interaction with several 5G sites as well as to the features offered by the Portal for service definition, instantiation, monitoring and validation. One of the key assets that 5G-EVE facilities is providing is the high degree of flexibility in adapting the architecture for any specific vertical. For example, French-Romanian facility cluster (shown in Figure 4) is mainly based on the 5G OAI, Mosaic-5G, Open Networking Automation Platform (ONAP), RAN OAI (LTE/NR eNodeB/gNodeB and UEs), Core OAI (4G EPC, 5GC functional entities) providing the functionalities and meeting all requirements for an end-to-end use case deployment.

Figure 4: 5G FR/RO experimentation facility cluster from 5G EVE

Moreover, considering the lessons learnt from validation activities performed by consortium partners in the context of previous and ongoing EU projects focused on 5G trials and pilots, some extensions will be introduced to enhance the features of the VITAL-5G system. Some examples include the increased flexibility and configurability of the testing procedures, the possibility to manually control the service components instantiated in the virtual environments (i.e., the possibility to access and operate on the NetApps components) and the decoupling between the service lifecycle and the testing execution logic. Even more important, considering the current trend of implementing AI/ML-based solutions for closed loop automation applied to service orchestration and re-configuration, as well as ML-driven application logic, more powerful APIs will be provided, for enhanced consumption of monitoring data, both historical and real-time, with advanced filtering capabilities and external triggers of lifecycle management actions on the instantiated services, even during the testing execution time.

2.1.2 5G VINNI

5G VINNI is an H2020 ICT-17 project (July 2018 – December 2021) developing an E2E 5G facility that can be used to first demonstrate the practical implementation of infrastructure to support the key 5G KPIs, and then to allow vertical industries to test and validate specific applications that are dependent upon those KPIs [4]. 5G VINNI is underpinned by principles that allow for highly dynamic and flexible network architectures, service deployment and testing, that will create new technical and commercial service deployment models. These will in turn drive inter-facility interconnection to enable virtualized functions from the network and service layer to be called upon from any facility, with complete location agnosticism (cloud-based network instantiation) that has no functional boundaries, implemented across multiple facility sites.

The 5G-VINNI facility sites are classified into two different types:

- Main Facility sites: E2E 5G-VINNI facility that offers services to ICT-18-19-22 projects with well-defined Service Level Agreements (Norway, UK, Spain, Greece).
- Experimentation Facility sites: 5G-VINNI sites that provide environments for advanced focused experimentation and testing possibilities on elements and combinations of elements of the E2E model (Portugal, Munich, Berlin).

In addition, there is a mobile experimentation facility site in the form of a rapid response vehicle for public protection and disaster relief (PPDR) use cases and potentially a boat.

Figure 5: 5G-VINNI facility with Main Facility sites and Experimentation Facility sites

5G-VINNI conceptual E2E facility architecture has various building blocks organized in three layers: *Resources & Functional Level* (RAN, Backhaul, Mobile Core and Cloud Computing facilities) that will provide the physical resources to host the other two layers: *Service Level* and *Network Level* (e.g., VNFs). These are interconnected to build dedicated logical networks, customized to the respective telco services, e.g., eMBB, V2X, URLLC, mMTC.

Figure 6: 5G-VINNI high level conceptual E2E facility architecture

The novelty of 5G-VINNI is the modularity which guarantees the highest degrees of freedom of both 5G-VINNI facility site configurations and facility interworking. Any Service Level or Network Level VNF from any 5G-VINNI facility, can be called upon to be included within the logical network of a use case driven from another facility creating an unlimited capability to implement and test use cases using the consolidated shared capabilities of all

facilities. This so called “*Recursiveness*” offers the potential for new business models and partner relationships (between partner operators, or between operators and large enterprise customers) whereby the service provider may both expose and consume service at different levels in the network.

The execution of internal validation campaigns, as well as the vertical customer experiments, will be run through a user-friendly Testing Portal, which will be the point where tests are configured, test campaigns are executed, and campaigns results are visualized and analyzed.

Figure 7: 5G-VINNI Test Framework

5G VINNI’s combination of this comprehensive test framework (Figure 7), the multiple interworking 5G RAN and 5G core infrastructures, and zero-touch E2E service orchestration will provide a unique platform for testing and trialling industry use cases. The platform will facilitate the rapid on-boarding of verticals by exposing network slice life-cycle management functions through an open API. By using the API’s, the verticals will be able to create, manage and de-commission network slices. This will offer a high level of agility in the management of connectivity services and will allow verticals to shorten their innovation cycles – quickly establishing network connectivity for E2E communication services and applying different test scenarios to the connectivity using the testing portal in order to evaluate the impact upon their E2E communication services.

2.1.3 5GENESIS

5GENESIS project targets to facilitate the deployment and execution of the vertical industries’ services with real users, through the proposition of a homogeneous interface that can be supported by the various platforms [5]. Therefore, a 5G experimentation blueprint has been developed in order to serve as a common architectural reference and the total 5G facility has been separated into five, diverse in terms of capabilities, yet fully interoperable, experimentation platforms (Figure 8) [5].

The main characteristics of the 5GENESIS infrastructure are:

- The facility is distributed and is comprised of various geographically dispersed platforms
- The platforms are complementary in terms of features, nevertheless aligned to the proposed common reference architecture
- The platforms are administratively independent, exposing open interfaces for inter-platform coordination and verticals experimentation
- The platforms accommodate multiple experiments from various verticals with diverse requirements
- The platforms are fully interoperable and can be interconnected in order to form a truly end-to-end Facility.

Figure 8: The 5GENESIS platforms

Each one of the platforms participating in the 5GENESIS Facility shall have the flexibility to govern its own physical topology, architecture and particular technological features. Nevertheless, towards harmonizing the different platforms and experimentation infrastructures, elements of the common reference architecture are to be replicated across the five platforms. In this way, each platform can be administratively independent, yet interoperable with the other platforms. A schematic view of the proposed 5-GENESIS Experimentation Blueprint, meant to implement all of the above-mentioned points, is depicted in Figure 9 [5].

Figure 9: 5GENESIS Experimentation Blueprint

2.1.4 5G Blueprint

The overall objective of the 5G-Blueprint project is to design and validate a technical architecture, business model and governance model for uninterrupted cross-border teleoperated transport based on 5G connectivity [6]. The project's outcome should be usable as the blueprint for subsequent operational pan-European deployment of teleoperated transport solutions in the logistics sector and beyond. The 5G infrastructure design and deployment of 5G Blueprint focus on enabling teleoperation and seamless cross border use with 5G technology. The use cases to demonstrate this capability are automated barge control, automated drive-in-loop docking, CACC based platooning, remote take-over operations. By providing Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) and massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), the architectural design of 5G network is key to the success of the project. The architecture design covers from 5G User Equipment, Radio Access Network, Edge Computing, Transport, Core Network, to network APIs. The design has a focus on addressing network slicing parameters and design for the project use cases and seamless cross bordering roaming.

Figure 10: 5G Blueprint geographic scope

The highlights of the 5G Blueprint infrastructure are:

- The 5G facility in Port of Antwerp covers diversified industrial area including: waterways, road networks, factories, infrastructure for logistic application on waterway and road networks (such as docking, parking, barging infrastructure, cranes etc), to support teleoperation uses cases.
- The 5G facility in North Sea Port covers a border-crossing area for both waterway and road network between Belgium and Netherlands to validate seamless 5G roaming.

- The 5G infrastructure is designed and built with an architecture aligned by KPN and Telenet based on different current network situation and network equipment suppliers, thus can be used as reference for further scaling in other networks.
- The platform is based on independent network infrastructure while utilizing existing commercial network footprint. Creates a good balance between exposing network interfaces towards third parties and between MNOs with operational impact on commercial networks and maximizing network availability with hybrid network design.
- The test zone has a large physical area and strong ecosystem to accommodate and validates end-to-end application and new use cases.

The overall 5G architecture of 5G Blueprint is as follows:

Figure 11: 5G Blueprint architecture overview

5G-Blueprint is very relevant to the VITAL-5G work as the two projects share the 5G infrastructure used in the port of Antwerp, which will be upgraded to Rel.16 SA for the completion of the VITAL-5G trials. The common partners shared among the two projects, namely IMEC, TEL and SF, will guarantee the knowledge transfer from 5G-Blueprint and will capitalize on lessons learned in order to more effectively set-up the VITAL-5G trials and to maximize the reuse of components.

2.2 Modelling of Vertical Applications for 5G Services

Regarding the modeling of various vertical and/or services, as well as the information models for the related VNFs, significant work has been carried out by the three ICT-17 projects, namely 5G-EVE[3], 5GENESIS [5] and 5G-VINNI [4].

In 5G-EVE a Catalogue Service has been defined as a component of the Portal Backend responsible for management of the blueprints and descriptors required for the experiment design and definition (namely Vertical Service Blueprints (VSBs), Context Blueprints (CTXBs), Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (EXPBs and

EXPDs respectively) [3]. These descriptors are used to translate the service-oriented requirements from the verticals into formal definition of vertical service and experiment settings (defined as “context”) that run in the facilities to execute the experiment. These descriptors are based on distinct templates or “Blueprints” that the experimenters can use to help them define their desired experiment. These are practically information models used to obscure the underlying complexity and retrieve information from non-expert users to assist with the definition of the experiment on a service and network level [7]. Within 5G-EVE the following blueprints have been defined: Vertical Service Blueprints, Context Blueprints, Experiment blueprints and Test Case Blueprints. As VITAL-5G inherits multiple elements from 5G-EVE including its experimentation structure and tools, a lot of these information models will also be inherited and reused, after being updated to reflect and accommodate the specific needs of the VITAL-5G experimentation architecture, updated tools and targeted vertical services.

5GENESIS[5] uses two key concepts for its experimentation process and the definition of the experiments, namely the test cases and the experiment descriptor [5]. These entities utilize information models specified in 5GENESIS Deliverable D2.3 [8] to assist with the detailed definition and configuration of the testbed and experimental setup. The 5GENESIS test cases describe the experiment and its measurable objectives and include a configuration file that specifies: i) the configuration of the environment (for all RATs and network); ii) the set of procedures; iii) the monitored metrics, and iv) formulas needed to calculate the KPIs. The experiment descriptor is a file that describes all the information needed to execute the experiment and compute the KPIs associated with the experiment. The 5GENESIS experiment descriptor, is not comprised of smaller entities as in 5G-EVE and contains information such as the type and experiment meta-data, list of test cases to be executed, slice configurations, service configuration, traffic sources and more. The Experiment Life-Cycle Manager (ELCM) will compose an experiment plan using the experiment descriptor and the information of the test cases. This is a similar approach to the one from 5G-EVE (which will also be adopted in VITAL-5G) as the designated information models, define the same parameters and offer configuration capabilities, only using a different structure (mono-block experiment descriptor instead of multiple element blocks).

5G-VINNI [4] also adopts model-based service templates for the definition of the experiments which are defined as structured document that provides a complete description of a given service, including information on service topology and expected behaviour. The service templates are offered via the 5G-VINNI service catalogue which offers the opportunity to providers and experimenters to instantiate and configure a customized experiment. The main tool/model used in 5G-VINNI for experiment definition and configuration is the Service Blueprint (SB), which is based on the GSMA Global Slice Template (GST), and consist of four main parts, namely the *service type*, the *service topology*, the *service requirements* and the *service exposure, testing and monitoring* [9]. Practically the VINNI-SB contains all the same information that 5G-EVE and 5GENESIS use for the definition of an experiment, but with a slightly different structure.

It becomes obvious that all three ICT-17 projects, which are considered very successful in experimenter engagement and 5G experimentation roll-out, use a similar approach when it comes to the definition of the VNF information models and the blueprints and descriptors used for experiment definition and configuration. VITAL-5G plans to reuse all of the successful elements of the above mentioned models and to further update them to accommodate 5G SA testbed functionality and potential new requirements from the T&L stakeholders.

Regarding the modeling of NetApps and the relevant data models used, they are only recently addressed as such, by the nine ICT-41 projects (including VITAL-5G) funded by the European Commission. As these projects are only running their first year of activities, limited information has been published on the specific approach taken by each of the projects, at the time of writing of this deliverable. However, through cross-project interaction (via 5G PPP) VITAL-5G managed to create a high-level overview of the addressed vertical services targeted and the key NetApp aspects in scope of each of the ICT-41 projects. This overview is presented in Section 5.4 of this deliverable and more specifically in Table 9. VITAL-5G plans to closely collaborate with the rest of the ICT-41 projects to produce knowledge and documentation and to provide insights and guidelines regarding the

development, deployment and validation of NetApps in various vertical industries. Discussions regarding common presence/organization of workshops and publication of white paper(s) to that effect are already ongoing.

2.3 Tools for Monitoring and Automated Testing

Significant prior work has already taken place in terms of monitoring tools, automated testing and validation methodologies for 5G networks and the services provisioned on top of them, by key stakeholder groups and previous 5G PPP projects. In order to identify the most suitable ones to be adopted for the platform and testbeds of VITAL-5G, a State-of-the-Art (SotA) study is necessary in order to understand the advantages and open issues of existing work. ETSI has performed significant work in terms of Interoperability Testing (INT) methodologies for the validation of vertical applications over 5G networks [10], which is considered as the reference point for VITAL-5G. The goal of such elaborate testing and validation methodologies is to streamline the vertical application testing and validation over 5G experimental platforms in a highly complex multi-stakeholder environment comprising Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), network and chipset vendors, vertical service providers and application developers. Through the definition of such methodologies, it is guaranteed that each stakeholders can draw useful insights regarding their product/service and find ways to further develop and increase the impact of their offering. For instance, verticals will develop assurance on the true potential of 5G related technologies for expanding their solutions or even innovating their business model, while MNOs and vendors will gain insight into the type of vertical application solutions utilizing the 5G networks, which will help them make decisions on whether and how to evolve their portfolio to support verticals with similar demands [10].

2.3.1 Relevant standards work

From a network perspective **3GPP** has performed significant work to enable precise automated testing and validation procedures, mostly focusing on network aspects, e.g., 5G NR protocols [11][12] or Radio Resource Management (RRM) [13], but also addressing application level testing [14]. Additionally, a KPI definition template has been specified in [15] to allow categorization of the KPIs and the methods, tools, and calculations that are used in order to measure and validate end-to-end KPIs and the corresponding network slices used. As expected, the 3GPP methodologies and testing procedures heavily focus on the evaluation of the various components of the networks, and even though some attempts have been made to incorporate end-to-end testing and service validation from a vertical's point of view, the detailed scenario definition (including network conditions) that would allow for their reproducibility is missing, while a detailed test-execution plan (step-by-step) is also not provided. Significant efforts are ongoing to by 3GPP to further onboard verticals into their processes and to try to work with them to update their testing and validation methodologies as evidenced by 3GPP TR22.804 [16], 3GPP TS22.261 [17] and 3GPP TS22.104 [18]

Another relevant stream of work is the work performed by **ITU** on "*APIs for interoperable testbed federations*" targeting to address the subject of testbed federation for 5G technologies, as portrayed in the currently ongoing definition of the recommendation ITU-T Q.API4TB [19]. This recommendation is expected to guide the development of testbeds that can be federated and enable the testing of complex vertical applications utilizing different network components and resources located in disjointed testbeds. The expectation is for federated testbeds to bring sustainability in fostering environments for quick innovations and testing of complex technologies and use cases, and for enabling quicker time to market for products and services [10].

ETSI has also performed considerable work to enable autonomous testing procedures for fixed and mobile networks, mostly under the umbrella of a sub-group of the ETSI TC INT Working Group, namely the Autonomic Management and Control (AMC) Intelligence for Self-Managed Fixed & Mobile Integrated Networks (AFI) WG. There are two kinds of Standards being developed in ETSI TC INT that are relevant to Vertical Applications over Autonomic/Autonomous 5G and Beyond Networks and Testing, namely:

- Standards for Testing AI Models (including AI Models of Generic Autonomic Networking Architecture (GANA) Cognitive Decision-making-Elements (DEs) for AMC in 5G and Beyond Networks[20][21][22]: These standards describe a way to test GANA cognitive indirectly by measuring network service performance KPIs, i.e., KPIs of relevance to network services like those required by Vertical Applications. The analysis and comparison of the KPIs under different operating conditions and the effect of the various network Decision Elements (DE) provide an assessment of the impact or value of DE autonomies for the network.
- Testing of Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (ANs), e.g., GANA based 5G ANs as Use Case for Standards for Testbeds Federations for 5G and Beyond (ITU-T – SG11) [23]: Through Federation, knowledge exchange and transfer, meta-data, events, triggers, synchronization and coordination messages, and many other forms of information are communicated in a collaborative fashion by testbeds/platforms to achieve E2E AMC operations such as E2E Self-Optimization of AN resources, Self-/Protection and Self-/Defense against detected security attacks, threats and risks to address security challenges that have impact on various network domains.

2.3.2 Relevant 5G PPP work

Some remarkable examples of state-of-the-art solutions can be found in the 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) initiative. 5G PPP is a joint initiative between the European Commission (EC) and the European ICT industry which aims to explore and demonstrate the key benefits of 5G technology to transform the various vertical industries and enable innovative applications which will ultimately contribute to European Union digital transformation. As discussed earlier in Section 2.1, three recent 5GPPP research infrastructure projects (under the H2020 call ICT-17-2018) stand out in terms of enabling multi-stakeholder vertical trials over state of the art 5G networks, namely, 5G-EVE [3], 5GENESIS [5] and 5G-VINNI [4]. Each of them provides an end-to-end testing platform for vertical industries to validate a wide variety of use cases in both controlled and large scale setups. These projects provide feedback to the 5G PPP Test Monitoring and Validation Work Group (5G PPP TMV WG), that has delivered a set of highly valuable recommendations on automatic testing framework for vertical KPI validation (including Testing as a Service (TaaS) approach), model driven methodology, and the mapping of E2E vertical service KPIs vs technical network KPIs. The work of the three ICT-17 projects as well as that of the 5G PPP TMV WG, is of high relevance to the VITAL-5G project and their procedures, methodologies and know-how play a major part on the definition of the equivalent processes and the architecture and tools utilized in VITAL-5G. As such, VITAL-5G is also going to comply with the terminology definition embraced by the TMV group regarding fundamental testing and monitoring aspects [10], namely:

- Monitoring: A generally passive process that is providing metrics from various components/layers of the 5G network.
- Testing: Procedure that provides a greater observability due to the active control over the type and intensity of traffic that is pushed through the network and through subsets of the network elements. This provides more degrees of freedoms in selecting what can be tested and measured (e.g., scalability or security resilience)
- 5G system: A system composed by several complex and heterogeneous components, blending IT, cloud, and telecommunication technologies, stacked on top of each other to create the full 5G network like the pyramid in Figure 12.
- Testing as a Service (TaaS): Testing process which reduces the effort that the MNOs' engineers need to put in testing the 5G infrastructure and components, by simplifying the testing operations and providing an interface to connect to the Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines of the MNOs NetOps. TaaS streamlines the execution of the different types of tests that need to be performed in each level of the 5G system pyramid (see Figure 12), while deploying and integrating the network, onboarding the VNFs, and providing the services.

As the TMV recommends supporting and using a TaaS approach in the future 5G networks, and the group is currently working on identifying several commonly shared Test Cases. VITAL-5G closely follows this recommendation and is implementing testing approaches based on commonly defined Test Case templates (see Deliverable D1.4 from VITAL-5G [26]).

Figure 12: TaaS System overview [10]

The TMV’s priority is to provide methodologies and Test Cases for the validation of the E2E services delivered to the verticals. The first step to accomplish is to define proper Test Cases in a TaaS framework for 5G service validation and identify the KPIs that should be stressed in these tests. A list of basic 5G technical KPIs has been defined by the TMV in [24], containing the type and the observing points within the 5G network for each of them. Moreover, an exhaustive analysis of 5G PPP projects’ use cases of various verticals has been performed in [25][26] mapping their service performance KPIs to corresponding 5G network KPIs. It should be noted that the definition of the VITAL-5G use case service and network level KPIs, as provided in Deliverable D1.1 [1], have been based on these works of 5G PPP and the TMV.

VITAL-5G plans to leverage the testing and validation solutions designed and implemented by the three ICT-17 projects, mentioned above, and to build on top of them, following the guidelines and recommendations of the TMV and the relevant standards. An overview table of the key characteristics of the validation solutions implemented in the three ICT-17 projects is provided in ETSI TR 103 761 V0.0.7 [10]. The most relevant attributes for the implementation of the VITAL-5G monitoring and testing tools, are showcased in Table 3.

Table 3: 5G PPP projects validation solutions attributes

Attribute	5G-EVE	5G-VINNI	5GENESIS
Validation Framework	TaaS platform supporting custom experiments, configurable virtual services, network slicing, service and network KPI collection and analysis, integrated diagnostics	TaaS platform supporting customized experiments and slicing configurations.	TaaS platform supporting standard experiments (project internal) and custom experiments (project external), slicing configurations, monitoring and analytics module, KPI collection and analysis
Experiment definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Configurable Blueprints Vertical service elements & connections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Purpose Description Initial Conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experimenter descriptor template <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test cases

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service parameters • Network requirements • Context conditions • Service & network KPIs • Evaluation criteria • Test cases • Configurable test scripts • Custom VNF/PNF onboarding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters • Procedures & expected results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Scenarios ○ Slices • 5GENESIS portal • Open APIs
Experiment workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment design • Experiment preparation • Experiment execution and monitoring • Experiment results evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment design • Experiment preparation • Experiment execution • Experiment assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment consultation phase • Experiment provisioning phase • Experiment execution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pre-run ○ Run ○ Post-run • Experiment decommissioning phase • Analysis of the results
Interfaces to verticals / experimenters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web-based Portal for the design, scheduling, deployment, execution and verification of 5G experiments • Intent Based interface • REST APIs • Results can be accessed or downloaded 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GUI for composing and scheduling tests • REST APIs • Results can be collected and stored to external databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web-based Portal for experiment execution and results collection • Open APIs
Testing Automation Capabilities	Automated execution of the experiment test cases, which includes the collection and validation of service and network KPIs and diagnostic analysis.	Tests can be scheduled in the TaaS user interface. TaaS can also be programmatically controlled through REST APIs.	Experiment Lifecycle manager which enables automating the execution of the experiments.
KPI Collection & Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service & Network KPIs collection supported • Visualization through graphs supported in the portal • Real time collection via REST APIs • KPI Downloading supported for post-processing • Threshold-based KPI validation supported • Performance Diagnosis supported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement results available via Grafana application • Measurements can be stored in external database • Threshold-based KPI validation supported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring information collected from all elements of the platform • Real-time access to KPIs supported via the analytics component • KPI database storage supported for post-processing • Advanced analytics offered via a correlation tool

3. VITAL-5G Experimentation Services

VITAL-5G provides a complete framework that facilitates the design, provisioning and experimental validation of 5G-enabled vertical services in realistic and highly configurable 5G testing environments. As a major target, VITAL-5G addresses vertical organizations operating in the T&L sectors, offering three testbeds with T&L facilities that cover scenarios spanning from river and sea-ports to warehouses. Each facility is extended with pre-commercial deployments of 5G networks, providing the mobile connectivity required for the T&L services and offering advanced features of network programmability, slicing and monitoring, combined with virtual computing resources to run the service applications. This approach provides the opportunity to replicate a variety of operational conditions in a controlled and flexible manner, so that the verticals can build and configure different experiments to verify the functionalities and the performance of their T&L services in dedicated and tunable 5G environments.

The experimentation services offered by VITAL-5G are designed to meet the requirements of T&L vertical industries, which have usually a limited know-how in networking and, in particular, in 5G infrastructures. For this reason, the modelling of services and experiments follows an application-oriented pattern, which hides the internal details of the 5G network configuration and focuses on the application components that build the vertical service logic and their high-level requirements in terms of mobile network connectivity. A key role in this vision is covered by the concept of NetApps. A NetApp is a virtual application that can be deployed in a 5G infrastructure and can make use of 5G connectivity and/or 5G services (e.g., to consume network data analytics or location information offered by the 5G Core Network) to implement its internal logic and provide its functionalities for a service consumer. The composition, instantiation and configuration of one or more NetApp, potentially designed and delivered by different software providers, gives the possibility to build complex T&L vertical services capable to exploit 5G mobile connectivity.

The VITAL-5G framework supports the verticals in all the phases of the experimental validation of T&L vertical services, starting from their design, and going through the different steps of 5G testing environment preparation and configuration, service instantiation, test execution and service performance evaluation (see Figure 13). This support is carried out with a number of experimentation services and tools which are provided by the VITAL-5G platform. The experimentation services, presented in Section 3.3, can be accessed by VITAL-5G users depending on their particular profile (e.g., differentiated for NetApp developers, experimenters, etc.) and they are made available through a web based graphical interface or programmable APIs, supporting both manual and automated interactions.

Figure 13: Experimental Validation of Vertical Services in VITAL-5G

Indeed, it is important to note that several actors are usually involved in the overall process, cooperating to the whole experimentation chain with different roles. For example, software developers and NetApp providers (often participating as third parties) contribute to the design phase bringing the building blocks of the vertical services and identifying the functionalities to be tested and the KPIs to be monitored. VITAL-5G testbed administrators, with network operators and administrators of the T&L facilities, act as mediators for the preparation of the testing environment, e.g., supporting the installation of additional hardware or the configuration of specific network settings that may be needed for particular experiments. Experimenters coordinate the experiment execution and analyze KPIs, results and reports as input for NetApps and service tuning and refinements. Section 3.2 provides an overview of the various actors and roles identified in VITAL-5G. The particular case of third party involvement is addressed in Section 3.4, especially relevant for external NetApp developers and/or service providers that would like to use the VITAL-5G offerings to experimentally validate their applications and/or build and test new vertical services, respectively. In this context, it is fundamental to highlight that the engagement of third parties as consumers of the VITAL-5G experimentation services requires the setup of operational procedures that involves aspects like training, cooperative identification of service requirements, continuous technical support and troubleshooting, thus going well beyond the implementation and the functional deployment of the VITAL-5G platform in a public production environment. These activities will be carried out in the context of tasks T6.3 (for engagement of third parties, preparation of related documentation and training activities) and T4.3 (for actual technical support, from the service/experiment design phase up to testing and validation).

3.1 VITAL-5G Architecture Terminology

This section provides a definition of some of the terms used later in this section in order to facilitate understanding of the discussion.

Table 4: Architecture Terminology

Terminology	Definition
VITAL-5G Platform	This refers to the VITAL-5G Open Platform (or VITAL-5G Platform) as shown in Figure 22. It includes the VITAL-5G Portal, the Open Online Repository, and the Management Backend systems. Vertical users and/or vertical applications access the VITAL-5G Platform to conduct experiments using the VITAL-5G toolset and NetApps. The VITAL-5G Platform interfaces with the VITAL-5G testbeds in order to enable provisioning and testing of 5G-based services.
VITAL-5G Testbed	These encompass all the network elements and infrastructure necessary to enable 5G connectivity, integrated in the VITAL-5G T&L sites. They include the 5G core network elements, edge network elements and associated cloud computing infrastructure, along with the wireless and fixed access equipment. In VITAL-5G these are the three 5G infrastructure installations being utilised in the use cases in Antwerp, Galati and Athens. The VITAL-5G testbeds include all control, management and orchestration elements necessary to configure and operate the 5G infrastructure from the core to the 5G antennas.
VITAL-5G T&L Facilities	These are also referred to as the VITAL-5G T&L Trial Facilities. They are the physical sites where the use case experiments will take place and include all the necessary hardware (sensors, actuators, gateways, vessels, AVGs, etc.) required to run the use

	case trials. In the VITAL-5G project, they are located at the sea port in Antwerp, the Danube river/port area, and the warehouse in Athens.
VITAL-5G Portal	This is a core element of the VITAL-5G Platform and is a collection of tools/functions for NetApp and service life cycle management (LCM). The portal allows the instantiation, monitoring and benchmarking of NetApps and vertical services. Users use the VITAL-5G Portal to run experiments via a dashboard or programmable API (intent-based API). All commands from vertical actors are automatically translated into 5G/NFV service descriptions and lifecycle management actions. The VITAL-5G Portal contains tools for KPI monitoring, analysis and diagnostic. This is described in more detail in Section 8.
VITAL-5G Open Online Repository	This is also called the VITAL-5G Catalogue. This is a core element of the VITAL-5G Platform that facilitates the design, onboarding, and validation of NetApps in target environments. The Open Online Repository is used to share and compose NetApps for complex services and implements a NetApp catalogue.
NetApp	A NetApp is a virtual application that can be deployed in a 5G infrastructure and can make use of 5G connectivity and/or 5G services (e.g., to consume network data analytics or location information offered by the 5G Core Network) to implement its internal logic and provide its functionalities for a service consumer.
Vertical Service	The composition, instantiation and configuration of one or more NetApps, potentially designed and delivered by different software providers, gives the possibility to build complex vertical services capable of exploiting 5G mobile connectivity.

3.2 Actors/Roles

Table 5 identifies the various actors/roles involved in the overall experimentation process and covers actors “internal” to the operation of the VITAL-5G platform, in addition to “external” actors/roles contributing NetApps and experimenting with the platform. To aid understanding, each actor/role is followed by a description and an overview of their expertise.

Table 5: Actors/Roles identified as being key contributors to the VITAL-5G experimentation process

Actor / Role	Description	Expertise
Actors contributing to provide VITAL-5G experimentation services		
Testbed Administrator /Technician	Administrators of one of the VITAL-5G testbeds, responsible for the overall testbed design, deployment and maintenance. They coordinate the scheduling of the experiments in the testbed and applies any custom configuration or installation that requires a manual intervention. Any service specific requirement with impact on the testbed functionalities should be discussed and agreed with the testbed administrators.	System integration, 5G network infrastructures and operations, cloud/edge computing, T&L infrastructures

T&L Site Infrastructure Manager	On-site at the T&L facility responsible for the infrastructure and equipment (sensors, camera, actuators, AVGs, etc.) to be used in the experiment.	Equipment for T&L facilities, including IoT sensors, actuators, other IoT devices.
VITAL-5G Open Platform Administrator	Administrator of the VITAL-5G Open Platform (i.e., VITAL-5G Portal + Open Repository), responsible for its deployment, operation and maintenance, as well as its interconnectivity to the VITAL-5G testbed.	Service platforms and system integration
VITAL-5G Open Platform Technician	Interfaces between the NetApp developers, service providers and experimenters using VITAL-5G services and the testbed technicians, to support in the design and execution of experiments and KPIs analysis.	Service platforms and system integration, some networking expertise.
Users of VITAL-5G services		
NetApp Developer (Internal or third party)	<p>Developers of vertical-specific or vertical-agnostic NetApps. They use the VITAL-5G platform to onboard their own NetApps.</p> <p>Once available on the VITAL-5G catalogue, NetApps can be used by <i>Vertical Service Providers</i> to build new (T&L) vertical services and by <i>Experimenters</i> to perform testing and validation experiments.</p> <p>NetApp developers may also focus specifically on VNFs, related to networking functions only (e.g., virtual firewall, virtual IDS, etc.). In this case they are called <i>VNF Developers</i>.</p>	<p>(T&L) service applications</p> <p>Networking functions in case of VNF developers.</p>
Vertical Service Provider (Internal or third party)	<p>Developers of vertical-specific services, which can be built composing NetApps and VNFs available in the VITAL-5G catalogue.</p> <p>They can use the VITAL-5G platform to create and onboard new vertical services and deploy them in the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p> <p>Vertical Service Providers includes the particular roles of <i>Service Developers</i>, active also in the implementation and creation of their own services, and <i>System Integrators</i>, specialized in the delivery of vertical services composed by NetApps provided by other entities.</p>	Vertical service design and implementation, service delivery and operation, system integration
Experimenter (Internal or third party)	<p>The VITAL-5G users interested in the experimental evaluation of NetApps or vertical services in a 5G environment. Experimenters can bring their own NetApps or re-use existing ones to build the services to be validated.</p> <p>Using the VITAL-5G platform, they can design their own experiments, identifying the KPIs to be monitored, the reports to be collected and the procedures for testing. They are also responsible for the management of their experiments, configuring and launching their executions, monitoring the results and analysing the produced reports.</p>	Service provisioning, tuning and testing, experimental validation and results analysis.

3.3 Experimentation Services in VITAL-5G platform

The VITAL-5G platform provides a centralized access point for all the experimentation services offered by the system to the various actors that interact with VITAL-5G. The experimentation services allow the design, provision, test and validation of vertical services, which can be composed of one or multiple NetApps and make use of 5G network connectivity and network functions.

Figure 14: Phases of VITAL-5G experimentation process

The different phases of a VITAL-5G experimentation process are represented in Figure 14. They are described below:

Vertical Service Design. This phase has the objective of designing and implementing a vertical service to be experimentally validated in one of the testbeds offered by VITAL-5G. It involves an initial step for the analysis of the testbed 5G capabilities, the devices available in the T&L facility (e.g., IoT sensors and actuators, video cameras, AGVs, etc.) and their access permissions (e.g., actuators may have private access, video cameras may have restricted access, etc.), as well as opportunities for further extensions (e.g., the possibility to install new hardware, to extend the 5G radio coverage or create additional network slices). It should be noted that this stage may require direct interactions between service and/or NetApp developers and VITAL-5G technicians, to jointly

discuss service requirements and reach an agreement on potential site enhancements or custom configurations that may be needed for the particular service. A typical vertical service in VITAL-5G is composed of one or more NetApps, which can be selected from the public ones available in the VITAL-5G Open Repository or developed as new NetApps to be onboarded in the VITAL-5G platform. The formal definition of a vertical service is specified through a Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB), which describes the composition and interconnectivity of the various NetApps, the configurable service parameters, the monitoring parameters and the high-level requirements in terms of mobile connectivity. Similarly, NetApps are defined through a NetApp Blueprint (NAB) that describes NetApps metadata like mobile connectivity requirements, software licenses, hardware dependencies, external interfaces and related protocols, usage of 5G network services, etc. (see section 5 for further information). The details of NetApps and vertical services' deployment in a virtual infrastructure are modelled through Virtual Network Function (VNF) packages and Network Service Descriptors (NSD) following the ETSI NFV standards. This approach guarantees the compatibility with the NFV orchestrators available in the three VITAL-5G testbeds, which are responsible for the instantiation of NetApps and vertical services in the target testing environments.

At the end of the Vertical Service Design phase, the related blueprints are onboarded and available in the VITAL-5G platform, in particular in the Open Online Repository. Furthermore, their NSD and VNF packages are onboarded in the target testbed.

Experiment Design. This phase has the objective of defining an experiment for the validation of NetApps or vertical services in a VITAL-5G testbed. The experiment is defined through an Experiment Blueprint (ExpB), which follows the format of 5G EVE experiment blueprints [7]. The experiment blueprint identifies the related vertical service or NetApp, the characteristics of the testing environment (e.g., network slice parameters, background traffic, etc.), the service and network KPIs to be monitored, their evaluation criteria (e.g., in terms of max/min thresholds), test scripts for testing automation, variable and configurable parameters, etc. At the end of the Experiment Design phase, the ExpB is onboarded in the VITAL-5G platform, and it is available in the Open Online Repository.

Preparation of 5G testing environment. This phase has the objective of preparing the testing environment for the execution of an experimentation campaign and, depending on the complexity of the scenario, it may require the manual intervention of the testbed administrators, in terms of 5G network settings or T&L facility configuration. The initial step of this phase involves the specific customization and configuration of the experiment and its associated NetApps and vertical service, as well as the scheduling of the experiment execution in the target testbed. The experiment customization is defined through an Experiment Descriptor (ExpD), again following the information model of 5G EVE ExpD [7], which is onboarded in the VITAL-5G platform. The scheduling of the experiments in dedicated time slots allows reservation of the required resources and guarantees the desired operational conditions, without unexpected interferences with the day-by-day activities in the testbeds' environments that may impact the experiment outcomes and limit the reproducibility of the results. Through the basic experiment configuration, the devices in the T&L facility and the network settings are properly configured, making the testbed ready for the service provisioning and the experiment execution. It should be noted that if the manual configuration of the testing environment is not required, the experimenter can immediately proceed with the following phases after the ExpD onboarding. Otherwise, an explicit notification from the testbed administrator is required to proceed.

Vertical Service Instantiation. This phase has the objective of provisioning the vertical service in the target testbed, triggering the instantiation of its NetApps in the virtual infrastructure, their activation and configuration. If the NetApps composing the vertical service are associated to restrictive software licenses (e.g., related to the number of instances that can be executed concurrently), these licenses are properly verified and validated. Depending on the dynamicity supported in the 5G testbed, the network slices dedicated to the vertical service may be instantiated on-demand during this phase, following the specification of the mobile connectivity requirements defined in the VSB. Finally, the collection of the monitoring data is properly activated and

configured, according to the network and service KPI specified for NetApps and vertical service. At the end of this phase, the vertical service instance is up and running in a dedicated virtual environment, with the NetApps activated, properly configured, interconnected to the 5G network and able to interact with the devices in the T&L facilities.

Experiment Execution. This phase has the objective of executing the experiment and collecting the monitoring data required to evaluate the performance of the service. During the experiment execution, some test scripts can be automatically configured and executed by the platform. Moreover, the user will have access to the various NetApp components, with the possibility to operate directly on their internal processes. In parallel, the mechanisms offered by the orchestrators in VITAL-5G testbeds, exposed through suitable APIs, will give the possibility to operate on the lifecycle of the vertical service, e.g., to trigger re-configuration or scaling actions even from external orchestration entities. These options are useful to evaluate how service and network KPIs vary with different deployments, configurations and dimensioning of the overall vertical services or single NetApps. The collected monitoring data can be visualized in real-time through graphs in the web based graphical interface or consumed by external entities via APIs. The combination of APIs for monitoring and service lifecycle management gives the possibility to implement closed-loop strategies, directly within the NetApps or in dedicated service orchestration logic which can be developed in third party systems.

In VITAL-5G the experiment execution and the vertical service lifecycle management will be two parallel and nearly independent procedures, i.e., an experiment can be executed over a vertical service whenever the service is in instantiated mode, but the lifecycle of the service can be managed independently without any particular relationship to the status of a particular experiment. This approach enables a higher level of flexibility in the dynamic lifecycle management of the service without the boundaries imposed by experiment executions.

Vertical Service Evaluation. This last phase has the objective of helping the experimenters in the evaluation and assessment of the vertical service performance in the 5G network. Elaborating the monitoring data and the network and service KPIs collected during the experiment execution phase, the platform analyses the results generating experiment reports. Moreover, it performs some diagnostics evaluation (also supported by AI techniques – see also section 8.1.5) to identify the potential causes of performance degradation or bottlenecks in the vertical service that may derive from networking issues at the various segments of the 5G infrastructure, poor performance of specific NetApp components or insufficient virtual resources in the computing infrastructure at the edge or core of the network.

3.4 Involvement of third Parties

The involvement of third party experimenters that are not members the VITAL-5G consortium (e.g. researchers, startups and companies) in the experimentation process and in the NetApp development and testing process, is a key aspect of the H2020 ICT-41 call and hence of the VITAL-5G project. VITAL-5G has the vision to engage with SMEs and T&L stakeholders and to involve them in the project with two distinct processes:

1. Vertical experimenters:

- a. **Target audience:** Vertical stakeholders, mostly stemming from the T&L ecosystem, that will be invited to observe, use and/or experiment over the VITAL-5G platform, using the NetApps, services and equipment developed and deployed by the VITAL-5G partners.
- b. **Goal:** 1) To disseminate the project results and create excitement in the community about the innovative solutions. 2) To offer the opportunity to experimenters to witness first-hand the benefits that 5G can bring to the T&L vertical sector. 3) To draw feedback from the T&L community as to how to further improve the solutions offered by VITAL-5G.

2. NetApp developers:

- a. Target audience: SMEs and technology development companies from the T&L and affiliated sectors (providers, consultants, IT experts), with in-house SW development capabilities. Experience in platform/service deployments and experimentation with cutting-edge technologies (5G, IoT, AI/ML) will be of added value.
- b. Goal: 1) To enable the developments, onboarding, deployment and validation of NetApps besides the ones deployed by the consortium partners, in order to assess the VITAL-5G platform's openness, flexibility and usability. 2) To expand the offered services on the VITAL-5G platform. 3) To offer the means (5G testbed, end-equipment, etc.) and tools (blueprints, descriptors, results analysis and diagnosis) to external parties to perform pre-commercial evaluation of their envisioned NetApp based product.

The detailed process to interact, invite, assist and evaluate third party experimenters, is currently being developed by Task 6.3: Capacity building programme and will be reported in deliverable D6.2 (due M18). However, in order to assist the setup of the process and the early communication with the third party experimenters an outline of the process is provided in Deliverable D1.4 [26], while the following sub-sections provide a first version of the list of components (HW & SW), tools and NetApps that will become available to the third party experimenters by the respective trial facilities of VITAL-5G. It has to be noted, that as some of the developed/used NetApps and equipment (e.g., vessels, sensors, etc.) by VITAL-5G partners can be commercially sensitive and/or require special permissions for usage, not all of the components of the trial sites will be available for the third party experimenters, meaning that access will be restricted for a sub-set of components (HW & SW).

Besides the trial-site specific components that will become available to the third party experimenters, they will also have access to the VITAL-5G central platform tools (e.g., Online repository, Results Analytics & Diagnostics tools, intent-based interfacing, monitoring tools, etc.), as presented in this deliverable, to facilitate their experimentation, results collection and analysis and the drawing of useful conclusions regarding their service and/or NetApp. The following sub-sections provide an early view of the assets that will be available to third party experimenters per site. As the project progresses and the components of the trial facilities (HW, SW, functions, etc.) mature, a more detailed list of the components and functions to become available to third party experimenters will be issued, which will be reported as part of Task 6.3.

3.4.1 Antwerp facility (BE) – Use Case 1

In the port of Antwerp trial facility, third party experimenters will be able to test and validate solutions related with automated vessel transport through the VITAL-5G platform. While the core activities of UC1 focus on demonstrating remote and autonomous vessel operation to inspire external companies similar to Seafar to adopt the ideas developed in VITAL-5G, third party experimenters will also have the opportunity to interact with the trial facility in several ways:

- On board data collection & interfacing for vessels (VS8): This vertical specific NetApp will be made publicly available to third party experimenters. Its main purpose is to collect, store and export some real-time public data coming from sensors on-boarded in the Tercofin II vessel (e.g., location, speed, vessel heading). This data could be used in new NetApps built by third party experimenters to e.g., predict trajectories or to recommend alternative paths. Additionally, this NetApp can also be reused and adapted by third party experimenters to collect sensor data from any other physical objects they may deploy and interface with (e.g., other vessels, drones, AGV, etc.)
- Remote Vessel Monitoring (VS5): This vertical specific NetApp will also be made available to third party experimenters to display the sensor data and video feeds coming from the Tercofin II vessel. This NetApp mainly consists of a monitoring dashboard used to track the vessel and supervise the network and service KPIs. The goal of this NetApp is to be reused by third party experimenters and serve as an example of a

standard monitoring dashboard for their applications. This accelerates the development of third party application that are similar to the Seafar use case as the dashboard can be reused. Examples of such use cases could be remotely monitored cars, drones, vessels, etc.

- *Real time digital twin (VA5)*: This will be a publicly accessible NetApp, meaning everyone can re-use it to build a new vertical service. The NetApp will not be open sourced, as it is IMEC's intellectual property. Its main purpose is to create a digital map of the environment in real time, based on the sensor data coming from a vessel (via the 5G network) and VS8. This NetApp's data can be used for various purposes by third party experimenters. A few examples are to use it for their own path prediction or visualization NetApp or for parties involved in the 5G Blueprint project. Furthermore, this NetApp could be reused by third party experimenters to create maps of the environments for other use cases such as autonomous driving, navigation in warehouses, etc.
- *Navigation speed optimizer (VS7)*: This NetApp is responsible for calculating the optimal speed for remote or autonomous equipment. This NetApp is initially designed to be used by remote-controlled vessels, yet its functionality can be used by third parties in experiments involving another type of equipment (e.g. sea-going vessels, drones, trucks, AGVs, etc.), making further use of the 5G-network capabilities. This NetApp allows users to link to its relevant data and create new equipment instances that require the calculation of optimal speed. Data to be linked refers to: position, planning (destination coordinates), planning at the destination and a relevant route calculator API. third party client applications can then call the Network Services Orchestrator (NSO) API to retrieve the optimal (navigation) speed and integrate it into their own dashboards. Optimal navigation speed is the speed to hold so that the equipment arrives just-in-time at the destination when a free slot is available in the planning at the destination.

3.4.2 Galati facility (RO) – Use Case 2

In Galati trial facility, experiments will aim to test and validate solutions targeting the navigation sector with focus on more efficient and safer operation of ships. Enhanced security will also be an advantage of the assisted navigation in severe weather conditions that are an important factor impacting water transport. The use case will employ NetApps, tools and equipment that Galati trial site partners developed based on data-enabled assisted navigation, systems of IoT sensors and video cameras with enhanced 5G enabled automations.

Through the VITAL-5G Platform, the users and NetApp developers will be able to onboard and validate their NetApps and perform the following actions:

- *Create and configure an instance of the vertical-agnostic data ingestion and post-processing NetApp (VA1)*: The Vertical Agnostic NetApp (see Section 3.2.1 of D2.1 [27]) enabling the data collection, storing and partial processing (e.g., from mounted sensors and video cameras). Based on this NetApp the data retrieved with low latency on the position of the ships and of the obstacles may be reused by NetApp developers in their own NetApps for setting up warnings or for reporting.
- *Create and configure NetApps based on vertical specific data from sensors* which will be made available from the local on-board server and will expose the interfaces to edge nodes and the 5G network. The aim of these experiments could be the improvement of decisions based on on-board diagnosis and monitoring functions and the reduction of the risk of human error in the decision making process which can in turn reduce the maintenance costs.
- *Request configurable 5G slices to support their experiments*: The Galati trial site will utilize a 5G SA testbed with configurable slices that can be setup manually. Third party experimenters will be able to use any of the pre-configured slices available at the Galati facility (used by the project partners for their experimentation) and also obtain new slices to be provisioned. For the requests of slices with specific configurations there will be an evaluation per case basis and an effort to accommodate as many as possible will be made.

- Collect KPIs using the 5G platform monitoring component: The output of the monitoring component of the Galati 5G-testbed will be available to the experimenters and they will be able to assess the critical network level KPIs (e.g., throughput, latency, etc.) during the validation tests of their NetApps. The results Analysis and Diagnosis tools offered by the central VITAL-5G platform, may also be used for deeper analysis of the test results and the drawing of valuable insights.
- Gather and review data from sensors and cameras by using interoperable wireless protocols over a private 5G network that will better describe the specific environment and help with the creation of local maps and with an improved collision detection mechanism based on GPS, heading, velocity, etc.
- Obtain data streams on events that can be classified in almost real time as dangerous based on various parameters and setup warnings to improve the reaction time for the crews of the various vessels. Data will be treated as confidential or public, which will lead to only some data streams being available for third parties due to commercial sensitivities.

3.4.3 Athens facility (EL) – Use Case 3

In the Athens trial facility, third party experimenters will have the opportunity to test and validate solutions targeting the automation and more efficient operation of a large logistics warehouse facility, enabled by 5G connectivity. Experimenters will be able to either make use of some of the NetApps, tools and equipment that the Athens trial site partners will have developed, in order to experience the benefits of 5G enabled automation first-hand and/or to onboard and deploy their own NetApp and validate its functionality in the real-life environment of the DIAKINISIS warehouse, using real-life available data. More specifically, in the Athens trial facility the third party experimenters will have the opportunity to:

- Create and configure an instance of the vertical-agnostic data ingestion and automation NetApp (VA1a): The Vertical Agnostic NetApp (see Section 3.2.1 of D2.1 [27]) enabling the data collection, storing and partial processing of warehouse data (e.g., from mounted sensors), may be reused by experimenters to enable the retrieval and ingestion of available data from the warehouse to their processing engines (e.g., part of their own NetApps).
- Exchange sensor data through one of the supported protocols (e.g., MQTT or HTTP): The appropriate communication protocols and interfaces will be available to experimenters to facilitate the exchange of data from sensors/equipment in the warehouse to their own NetApps.
- Interact with a simulator of the warehouse environment which includes virtual AGVs: The experimenters will be able to interact with the warehouse simulator developed for the Greek platform, which will support the operation of virtual AGVs. In this manner the experimenters will be able to set-up, configure and execute scenarios, simulating warehouse operation with AGVs, and to test/validate various optimization algorithms for warehouse processes and/or AGV utilization techniques.
- Request configurable 5G slices to support their experiments: The Athens trial site will utilize a 5G SA testbed and as such will offer a few differentiated 5G slices (e.g., eMBB, URLLC) to be used for the different tests/trials that will take place in the Athens facility. Dynamic slice provisioning and configuration will not be available in the Athens facility, and all slices will have to be configured statically. third party experimenters will be able to use any of the pre-configured slices available at the Athens facility (used by the project partners for their experimentation) and even make requests for new slices to be provisioned or for updated configuration setting on one of the existing slices. These requests will be evaluated per experimenter and per case basis, and an effort to accommodate as many as possible will be made.
- Collect KPIs using the 5G platform monitoring component: The output of the monitoring component of the Athens 5G-testbed will become available to the experimenters, so as to enable them to collect critical network-level KPIs (e.g., throughput, latency, etc.) during the validation tests of their NetApps. In

combination with the results Analysis and Diagnosis tools offered by the central VITAL-5G platform, this makes for a powerful offering enabling the deep analysis of the test results and the drawing of valuable insights.

- Utilize non-sensitive historical and test data regarding warehouse operations: Experimenters will be provided with access to non-sensitive data regarding the warehouse and AGV operations from the Athens trial site partners, which they will be able to use for the calibration and optimization of their T&L services and NetApps. As historical data stemming from real world logistics operations and test data of commercial proprietary functions can be extremely sensitive, the Athens trial site partners reserve the right to restrict access to any of these data, and only allow access on a per experimenter and per case basis.
- Access to AGV functionalities can be agreed (per case basis): Full access to the AGV and all its functions within the warehouse cannot be guaranteed for the third party experimenters, as the DIA warehouse is a live working environment, and several security and safety concerns have to be taken into account. However partial access to the AGV for limited testing can be agreed on a per-experimenter basis, in agreement with the Athens trial site partners and for a pre-defined interval.

4. VITAL-5G Open Platform Requirements

This section presents the requirements of the VITAL-5G Open Platform. Section 4.1 introduces the methodology followed to identify and categorize the requirements, while section 4.2 present the list of requirements discussing their impact on the VITAL-5G system.

4.1 Methodology

The identification of the requirements for the VITAL-5G open platform has initially followed a customer-oriented approach. Starting from the definition of the main categories of users that will interact with the platform (see section 3.2), the characteristics of their profiles have been analyzed in terms of know-how, expertise and expectations. This initial phase has identified the major experimentation services that the VITAL-5G platform should provide for each category of users, in order to facilitate the design, creation and testing of new 5G-enabled vertical services in general and, more specifically, for the T&L service.

In parallel, the practical analysis of the use cases which will be developed from the partners in the consortium, with their related vertical services and NetApps (as document in deliverable D1.1 [1]), has provided a concrete foundation to identify more technical requirements in terms of specific functionalities and capabilities to be offered by the VITAL-5G platform as a whole and by the various testbeds. Examples of these inputs are the kind of metrics and KPIs to be collected, not only at the 5G network level, but also at the virtual computing infrastructure and application level, or the variability of network slice types to be offered, as well as the characteristics and vertical-oriented understanding of NetApps and services. This technical analysis has been complemented with a survey, performed in collaboration with WP3, of the current capabilities of the three VITAL-5G testbeds, their roadmap and the possibility of introducing new functionalities or enhanced levels of programmability (e.g., for dynamic slice creation or re-configuration). This approach has allowed an early evaluation of the technical feasibility of some requirements and, where needed, their refinement in order to obtain a consistent set of indications that can concretely drive the design and implementation activities.

Another major source of information for the definition of VITAL-5G requirements, in particular associated to the support of third-party experiments, is the practical experience built through the participation in previous ICT-17 projects⁴, like 5G-EVE. These projects have offered similar experimentation facilities for 5G-enabled services, open not only for internal use cases but also for experimentations from external ICT-19 projects⁵. Beyond the experience on methodology and best practices to train, onboard and support external experimenters during their design and testing activities, the received feedbacks have been fundamental to identify the required technical improvements, e.g., in terms of flexibility in the vertical service management, direct access to the service virtual functions, open interfaces for the programmable collection of KPIs and lifecycle management of the service. Similarly, this collaboration has helped to prioritize the functionalities offered by the platform following the external perspective of very different categories of potential users, from pure verticals, mostly interested in simple and network-agnostic service deployment, to software developers and system integrators keen to make use of more advanced features for network programmability and service orchestration.

⁴ <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-phase-3-1-projects/>

⁵ <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-phase-3-3-projects/>

4.2 Open Platform Requirements

This section refines the requirements of the VITAL-5G Open Platform, initially identified in deliverable D1.1 [1], on the basis of the analysis of the experimentation services defined in Section 3.3. Where relevant, the requirements have been associated to a specific experimentation phase.

The requirements are classified as mandatory and optional, and prioritized according to their importance in the overall experimentation process. This will provide a guideline to properly schedule the VITAL-5G implementation activities in WP2. Moreover, their impact on functionalities and components of the VITAL-5G system (both VITAL-5G platform and VITAL-5G testbeds) is analyzed as input for the architecture design.

It should be noted that some requirements defined as “optional”, even if not mandatory for the core experimentation services to be offered by the VITAL-5G Platform, are actually related to added value features that would greatly improve the usability of the system and the overall user experience. For this reason, their implementation will be concretely addressed in WP2, but introduced in the later releases of the platform. This will allow to early provide a consistent set of functionalities with all the mandatory features, in support of the trials in WP4, and to progressively include enhanced features to improve the specific aspects of the design, validation or testing procedures.

Table 6: VITAL-5G open platform requirements

Requirement description	Category	Priority	Impact on VITAL-5G system
Generic Requirements (valid for all the experimentation phases)			
R_0_01: VITAL-5G Platform experimentation services The VITAL-5G Platform must provide and enable a centralized access for different actors to the VITAL-5G experimentation services during the various phases of the experimentation process: (i) Vertical Service design; (ii) Experiment design; (iii) Preparation of 5G testing environment; (iv) Vertical Service instantiation; (v) Experiment Execution; (vi) Vertical Service evaluation.	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform should provide a centralized Portal and Open Repository with open interfaces to access the various experimentation services.
R_0_02: Web based UI The VITAL-5G platform should provide a web-based graphical user interface (GUI) to access all the VITAL-5G experimentation services.	Mandatory	Medium	The VITAL-5G Platform web GUI should provide a graphical and simplified access to the Portal and Repository services. The GUI may implement wizards to guide the users across the various experimentation steps and workflows.
R_0_03: OpenAPIs to access VITAL-5G platform functionalities in a programmable manner In addition to the GUI, a subset of the functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform services should offer REST-based interfaces. Such REST APIs may be defined using the OpenAPI specification to simplify

<p>experimentation services should be made available for external software components through programmable REST APIs.</p>			<p>the development of external VITAL-5G clients.</p>
<p>R_0_04: Users profiles and groups The VITAL-5G platform should provide differentiated access permissions to multiple users, on the basis of their role (e.g., experimenter, NetApp developer, etc.) and their group (e.g., the use case where the user is involved). In particular, the users should have restricted access to private NetApps, services and experiments, as well as limited visibility and control over assets of the T&L facilities (e.g., sensors, video camera, actuators).</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should provide identity management and access control to protect digital assets and guarantee differentiated access to the functionalities offered by the platform, on the basis of the user role and group. The VITAL-5G access control should be based on RBAC (Role Based Access Control) mechanisms and differentiate the users' permissions (based on role and group) in terms of items visibility and permitted actions. The Web GUI should provide login functionalities and the access to REST API should be authorized. Mechanisms for user account registration should be supported.</p>
<p>R_0_05: Unified procedures across different VITAL-5G testbeds The VITAL-5G platform must expose common interfaces, information models and procedures to access the experimentation services, independent of the target VITAL-5G testbed where the experiments will be executed and the testbed's internal technologies or architecture.</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should implement unified interfaces, internal data models, procedures and workflows. The interaction with the various testbed should be enabled through a common abstract interface, complemented with testbed-specific drivers for adaptation and translation purposes.</p>
<p>Requirements related to Vertical Service Design</p>			
<p>R_1_01: Browsing of existing NetApps The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or to public NetApps which can be re-used and composed in vertical services. The browsing of the NetApps should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, category, etc. NetApps information should provide enough details to simplify their integration in vertical services and enable their testing and validation in the 5G network within the VITAL-5G testbed.</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should implement a NetApp catalogue in its Open Repository. Queries should allow to retrieve all the public NetApps, while access control mechanisms should be applied for the visualization of private NetApps. The NetApp package should include metadata describing the 5G related requirements and dependencies on T&L facilities hardware. These metadata will be encoded as part of the NetApp blueprint.</p>

<p>R_1_02: Onboarding of new NetApps</p> <p>The user should be able to onboard new NetApps in the VITAL-5G Platform. The onboarding should be properly authorized, taking also into account the level of access required by the NetApp to IoT devices and hardware in the T&L facility.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform NetApp catalogue should enable the creation, update and removal of new NetApp packages, managing their synchronization with the catalogues at the target VITAL-5G testbed. Access control mechanisms should be applied, in compliance with the user's roles and groups, as well as the NetApps dependencies on T&L facilities hardware.</p>
<p>R_1_03: Validation of new NetApps at onboarding stage</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform may enable the automated validation of new NetApps, in terms of NetApp package format verification and functional validation in the target testbed.</p>	Optional	Low	<p>The VITAL-5G platform may provide tools to validate the format of the NetApp package, verify the consistency of the NetApp metadata with the capabilities of the target VITAL-5G testbed and verify their correct deployment and normal behaviour in the target testbed.</p>
<p>R_1_04: Unified NetApp and service modelling</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform must expose a common format and methodology to onboard, edit, update, delete, and monitor NetApps and T&L service experiments, independent of the target 5G testbed and the format of the descriptors used in the testbed's internal catalogues.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform must support a unified format for the NetApp package, independently on the information model of the VNF packages handled in each VITAL-5G testbed. Suitable translation procedures may be required when onboarding the packages in specific VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>
<p>R_1_05: NetApps onboarding with possibility to declare metadata that helps NetApps composition, testing, and validation</p> <p>When a NetApp is onboarded, the user must be able to include metadata to facilitate composition, testing, and validation of the NetApp in an automated manner.</p>	Optional	Medium	<p>The NetApp package should include metadata describing the characteristics of the NetApp, e.g., interfaces, protocols, testing procedures, service KPIs, etc. These metadata will be encoded as part of the NetApp blueprint.</p>
<p>R_1_06: Onboarding of new Vertical Services</p> <p>The user should be able to define and onboard new Vertical Services composed by NetApps in the VITAL-5G Platform. The onboarding of vertical services including NetApps with restricted access</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include a Vertical Service blueprint catalogue in the Open Repository. The catalogue should enable the creation, update and removal of new VSBs, describing their service-level characteristics and NetApps' composition and linking to</p>

should be validated on the basis of the user groups.			NSDs defining their instantiation in a VITAL-5G testbed. The catalogue should keep the synchronization with the catalogues at the target VITAL-5G testbed. Access control mechanisms should regulate the onboarding of VSB with restricted NetApps.
<p>R_1_07: Browsing of existing Vertical Services</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Vertical Services. The browsing of the Vertical Services should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, use case, etc. Vertical Service information should provide service-level information related to their NetApps, 5G requirements and validation criteria.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G platform Vertical Service catalogue should allow queries for VSB retrieval, with suitable access control mechanisms.
<p>R_1_08: Browsing of information related to VITAL-5G testbed capabilities</p> <p>The user may be able to visualize information related to the capabilities of the VITAL-5G sites, e.g., in terms of 5G network infrastructure, available network slices, edge/cloud computing resources, IoT devices and hardware in the T&L facility (e.g., sensors, video cameras, actuators, etc., including their permitted access type, i.e., in read-only, write-only or read-write mode). The access to some information may be restricted, depending on the user profile and group.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include an inventory service with open interfaces to retrieve the details of the various VITAL-5G sites.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> in the early version of the platform, the same kind of information can be provided statically with suitable testbed documentation. Such documentation will be collected in a web page linked in the portal.</p>
<p>R_1_09: Facilitated NetApp composition in vertical services</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform can provide mechanisms to facilitate the composition of the NetApps into end-to-end services, which could be partially automated according to the metadata defined in the NetApp package and in the vertical service blueprint.</p>	Optional	Low	The VITAL-5G Platform may include a tool to automatically build the NSD associated to a vertical service blueprint, composing the NetApps' functions of its components.
<p>R_1_10: Specification of 5G requirements for NetApps and Vertical Services</p>	Mandatory	High	NetApps and Vertical Service blueprints must enable the modelling of 5G requirements, e.g., in terms of

<p>The user must be able to declare the 5G related requirements for NetApps and Vertical Services, using a simplified approach based on the declaration of pre-defined parameters.</p>			<p>characteristics of the mobile connectivity or required 5G services, using a simplified and service-oriented model. The VITAL-5G platform should internally translate these requirements into network slices, e.g., through Network Slice Templates.</p>
Requirements related to Experiment Design			
<p>R_2_01: Browsing of existing Experiment blueprints</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Experiment blueprints. The search should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, use case, etc.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include an Experiment blueprint catalogue in the Open Repository. Access control mechanisms should regulate the queries of Experiment blueprints.</p>
<p>R_2_02: Onboarding of new Experiment blueprints</p> <p>The user should be able to define and onboard new Experiment blueprint for the experimental validation of vertical services available in the VITAL-5G Platform catalogue. The onboarding of experiment blueprint referred to vertical services with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The Experiment blueprint catalogue should enable the creation, update and removal of new experiment blueprints. Access control mechanisms should regulate the onboarding of experiment blueprints associated with vertical services with restricted access.</p>
<p>R_2_03: Wizard for guided definition and onboarding of new Experiment blueprints</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform web GUI may provide a wizard to guide the user in the definition of the various parameters that constitute an experiment blueprint.</p>	Optional	Medium	<p>This requirement should be implemented through a dedicated functionality in the VITAL-5G Platform GUI.</p>
<p>R_2_04: Validation of new experiment blueprints at onboarding stage</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform may enable the automated validation of new experiment blueprints, in terms of format verification and compatibility with the existing vertical services.</p>	Optional	Low	<p>The VITAL-5G platform may provide tools to validate the format of the experiment blueprint and verify the availability of the related vertical service in the catalogue.</p>
Requirements related to preparation of 5G testing environment			
<p>R_3_01: Onboarding of new Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors for experiment customizations</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include catalogues for Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors in the Open Repository. Access control mechanisms</p>

<p>The user should be able to define and onboard new Vertical Service descriptors and Experiment descriptors in the VITAL-5G Platform catalogue, in order to declare the specific configuration and customization of services and experiments, based on their blueprints. The onboarding descriptors referred to blueprints with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.</p>			<p>should regulate the onboarding of descriptors associated to blueprints with restricted access.</p>
<p>R_3_02: Browsing of existing Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The Vertical Service and Experiment descriptor catalogues in the VITAL-5G Platform should include access control mechanisms to regulate the queries of the various descriptors.</p>
<p>R_3_03: Scheduling of service and experiment instances The user must be able to declare a preferred time slot for the provisioning of a vertical service and the execution of the experiments.</p>	Mandatory	Medium	<p>The information models and the interfaces related to service provisioning and experiment executions should allow to specify a time slot.</p>
Requirements related to Vertical Service instantiation			
<p>R_4_01: On-demand provisioning and LCM of vertical services The user must be able to provision a vertical service on-demand and request the execution of lifecycle management actions, like scaling, re-configuration and termination. The service instantiation should be enabled only for public vertical service blueprints, the ones owned by the user or associated to his/her use cases. Other LCM actions on instantiated services should be enabled only to the users associated to the given use case.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G Platform, at the Portal level, should include a component in charge of managing the lifecycle of vertical services, triggering the instantiation of the related network services in the target testbed and thus coordinating the lifecycle of the associated NetApps. The component should implement access control mechanisms.</p>
<p>R_4_02: Secure user access to instantiated NetApps The user must be able to access the Virtual Machines or containers where its own NetApps are running in a secure manner.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G testbeds must enable a secure connectivity (e.g., via VPN) to the NetApps running in their virtual environments. The VITAL-5G Platform should visualize the information required to access the NetApps (e.g., IP addresses assigned to the NetApp instances).</p>

<p>R_4_03: Hosting and execution of concurrent vertical services, guaranteeing target QoS</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform must be able to deploy, manage and monitor multiple and simultaneous instances of Vertical Services, each of them with their own NetApps.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G testbeds must support the provisioning of multiple network services, with the instantiation of their NetApps, within isolated or shared network slices, each with guaranteed QoS.
<p>R_4_04: Automated management of network slices</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform must coordinate the management of the network slices required for a given vertical service in a fully automated and transparent manner. Where required, the usage of edge resources for deployment of NetApp components should be enabled.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G platform must enable the coordinated management of the network slices required to deploy a Vertical Service and its NetApp. Such management can be based on the dynamic provisioning, configuration and termination of network slices or rely on the selection of pre-defined and pre-existing network slices at the VITAL-5G testbeds, depending on the specific testbed capabilities. These mechanisms should be triggered internally during the provisioning and lifecycle management of a vertical service, and be fully transparent for the users.
<p>R_4_05: Transparent interaction between the VITAL-5G Platform and the VITAL-5G testbeds</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform must be able to interact with the local NFV MANO and NG-RAN control systems available at the three trial facilities. The details of such interaction must be fully transparent for the VITAL-5G users.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform should adopt unified abstract interfaces for its southbound interaction with the various testbeds and adopt testbed-specific drivers to communicate with the specific orchestrator, controllers and monitoring platforms available in each testbed.
<p>R_4_06: Centralized license management for NetApps</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform should provide mechanisms to verify and manage different types of licenses associated to the NetApps.</p>	Optional	Low	The VITAL-5G Platform should include a component responsible for NetApps' license validation in coordination with service deployment and lifecycle management procedures. NetApps' licences should be modelled and declared in the NetApp package.
<p>R_4_07: Logic for optimized placement of virtual functions or automated slice management</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform may implement internal logic and procedures to optimize resource orchestration, slice</p>	Optional	Low	The VITAL-5G Platform may include an internal component, potentially implementing AI-based algorithms, responsible for optimizing the decisions on placement of NetApps virtual

<p>management and virtual function placement e.g., on the basis of the slice type and profile, resource utilisation and service demands. Such mechanisms may be implemented through AI/ML algorithms e.g., for load prediction.</p>			<p>functions and infrastructure resource orchestration.</p>
Requirements related to experiment execution			
<p>R_5_01: On-demand experiment execution The user must be able to request the execution of an experiment, starting from its experiment descriptor, over an instantiated vertical service. The user must be able to request experiments only on its own vertical services.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G Platform, at the Portal level, should include a component in charge of managing the lifecycle of the experiment execution, in cooperation with the associated vertical service management, triggering the collection of monitoring data and the analysis of the results. The component should implement access control mechanisms.</p>
<p>R_5_02: Automated execution and configuration of test scripts The user can declare test scripts that will be automatically configured and executed during the running of an experiment.</p>	Optional	Medium	<p>The VITAL-5G platform component responsible for experiment management should be able to trigger the execution of test scripts, e.g., in specific NetApps. The modelling of the experiment should support the declaration of test scripts with configurable variables.</p>
<p>R_5_03: Support for secure, manual execution and configuration of test scripts on NetApps during experiment execution. During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to access the NetApps in a secure manner, in order to manually trigger the execution of commands or test scripts.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G testbeds must enable a secure connectivity (e.g., via VPN) to the NetApps running in their virtual environments during the experiment execution phase.</p>
<p>R_5_04: Decoupled service lifecycle management during experiment execution. During the execution of an experiment, the user (or an external entity) must be able to trigger lifecycle management actions on the associated vertical service (e.g., to scale up and down, terminate or re-configure some NetApps).</p>	Optional	Low	<p>The logic of the VITAL-5G Platform components responsible for vertical service and experiment execution lifecycle management should be decoupled and independent.</p>

<p>R_5_06: Monitoring, collection and visualization of 5G network metrics and KPIs.</p> <p>During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize monitoring data related to 5G network KPIs, as declared in the experiment blueprint.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform, at the Portal level, should include a monitoring platform for the collection, storage and visualization of monitoring data, coming from different data sources. VITAL-5G testbeds should be able to measure 5G KPIs and publish the data into the VITAL-5G monitoring platform.
<p>R_5_07: Monitoring, collection and visualization of service-level metrics and KPIs.</p> <p>During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize service-level KPIs, as declared in the experiment blueprint, assuming that the NetApps implement the mechanisms required to collect and publish such data.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G monitoring platform should give the possibility to receive monitoring data in a standard format, facilitating the publishing of monitoring data from the NetApps deployed in VITAL-5G testbeds.
<p>R_5_08: Monitoring, collection and visualization of metrics and KPIs related to the virtual computing infrastructure.</p> <p>During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize monitoring data related to the virtual computing infrastructure (e.g., CPU or memory utilization), associated to the consumption of resources for the service NetApps.</p>	Optional	Medium	VITAL-5G testbeds should be able to collect KPIs from their virtual computing infrastructure and publish the data into the VITAL-5G monitoring platform.
<p>R_5_09: Secure access to real-time and historical monitoring data via open interfaces.</p> <p>The user (or an external entity) must be able to access the various monitoring data collected during the execution of an experiment in a secure and authorized manner through open interfaces. These interfaces should support the efficient consumption of the data both in real-time or through queries for historical data.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G monitoring platform should provide a secure and open interface for external entities to retrieve the monitoring data stored and/or collected. Access control mechanisms should regulate the access to the different categories of monitoring data.
Requirements related to Vertical Service evaluation			
<p>R_6_01: Visualization of information related to executed experiments, with reports on the service and network KPIs collected during their execution.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G monitoring platform should store the service and network KPIs and enable their visualization on a per experiment basis. The VITAL-5G

<p>The user must be able to visualize the list of executed experiments and, for each of them, visualize its details, graphs related to its service and network KPIs, as well as results related to the experiment execution.</p>			<p>platform component responsible for experiment management should be able to store the results of executed experiments and expose them to the GUI. The VITAL-5G platform should include a component responsible for the analysis of the monitoring data, in order to produce experiment results (e.g., based on KPIs' thresholds declared for the experiment).</p>
<p>R_6_02: Automated diagnostic for identifying service bottlenecks and root cause of performance degradation.</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform should be able to process the KPIs collected during an experiment and identify in an automated manner the potential causes of performance degradation, related to issues at the 5G network or computing infrastructure level.</p>	Optional	Medium	<p>The VITAL-5G platform may include a diagnostic component, potentially adopting AI techniques, that examines the collected monitoring data and outputs an analysis of the possible reasons of the service underperformance.</p>

5. NetApps in VITAL-5G

This section describes the concepts of NetApps in VITAL-5G, how they are modelled and how they can be composed in Vertical Services. In particular, Section 5.1 introduces the concept of NetApp and the service-oriented approach defined in VITAL-5G to represent them. The categories of NetApps are presented in Section 5.1.1, while Section 5.1.2 explains how various NetApps can be combined together to build a more complex vertical service. The concept of NetApp package, used to distribute the NetApps and make them available through the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, is described in Section 5.2, defining the format of the package (Section 5.2.1) and its information model (Section 5.2.2), including the elements of the NetApp blueprint. The related data model will be specified in WP2 and documented in deliverable D2.1 [27], where the NetApp blueprints of VITAL-5G NetApps will be also reported. The modelling of a vertical service is defined in Section 5.3, where the concepts related to Vertical Service Blueprints, Vertical Service Descriptors and their translation into NFV Network Service Descriptors and Network Service instances are explained. Finally, Section 5.4 provides a survey of NetApps modelling and management in the context of other 5G PPP projects, highlighting commonalities and differences with the VITAL-5G approach.

5.1 Concepts and modelling

One of the key objectives of VITAL-5G is the realization of the Networked Application (NetApp) concept, which aims to simplify the vertical service design, lifecycle management and testing on top of 5G infrastructures. In this sense, in VITAL-5G we envision vertical services, and more in particular T&L services, as the composition of NetApps into service-chains with multiple virtual application components that make use of 5G connectivity. Here, each NetApp provides its own complete functionality, even when deployed as a stand-alone entity, but it can cooperate and interact with other NetApps to deliver more complex T&L services aligned with the overall business target of a Service Provider. The focus is therefore set on establishing mechanisms that on the one hand enable simple composition of NetApps and, on the other hand, abstract the low-level orchestration details required to deploy the service on top of 5G infrastructures.

In practical terms, the NetApp concept extends the typical orchestration-oriented descriptors proposed in ETSI NFV (e.g., VNFDs, NSDs) with enhanced declarations of the service level information that simplify the re-usage and integration of NetApps into vertical services. For example, the definition of NetApps interfaces allows to compose together different NetApps and share their adoption across multiple T&L services. From the 5G slicing and orchestration capabilities perspective, the NetApps also extend the orchestration descriptors with the specification of the main characteristics of the required 5G slice profile, and with establishment of the 5G Core services which the NetApp leverages for optimized orchestration decisions.

The VITAL-5G NetApp concept also covers the integration and validation phases of the NetApp development lifecycle. For this the VITAL-5G NetApp definition also includes the definition of the test scripts and the targeted metrics and KPIs which allow the assessment of the NetApp on a certain scenario from both a functional integration and overall performance perspective.

Figure 15: Example of NetApp

Figure 15 represents an example NetApp, in particular an IoT Management Platform NetApp that handles IoT data from/to local IoT supervisors installed in the field at the UE side, e.g., in various vessels. These IoT supervisors act as IoT gateways towards a number of multi-protocol and multi-vendor IoT devices, both sensors and actuators, and use the 5G connectivity to interact with the IoT Management Platform NetApp, which can be deployed dynamically in the virtual computing infrastructure (edge or cloud) offered by one of the VITAL-5G testbeds.

The picture highlights some of the concepts related to the modelling of a NetApp. Following an approach similar to the structure of a Virtual Network Function (VNF), a NetApp can be considered as a set of internal *Atomic Components* (the red boxes in the Figure 15), which correspond to virtualized deployment units (e.g., a container or a Virtual Machine) and implement the different parts of the NetApp logic. These components interact with each other through a number of internal *Connectivity Services* (the dotted line in the NetApp box), i.e., the equivalent of virtual networks. Each component has one or more endpoints that enable this interaction. The endpoints can be internal ones (light-grey circles in the Figure 15), used only for the interaction among the components of the same NetApp, or external ones, used to interact with elements external to the NetApp. For example, external endpoints are used to model the connection points associated to the NetApp interfaces that provide access to the NetApp’s functionalities for final users or other service elements that interact with the NetApp itself.

A particular case of external endpoint is the one through which the NetApp is interconnected to the 5G network, i.e., on the N6 interface of the 5G system. In the NetApp modelling, this endpoint is characterized by one or more 5G service profiles, which describe the characteristics of the network slices required for the given NetApp’s functionalities. The 5G service profile includes information like the slice service type (i.e., eMBB, URLLC, mMTC), relevant QoS parameters (e.g., uplink and downlink data rate, latency, jitter) and additional attributes related to the 5G mobile connectivity, like coverage area, radio access technology, etc. Moreover, the possibility to deploy a NetApp in the context of a 5G infrastructure gives also the opportunity to consume some of the services offered

by the 5G network, for example the network data analytics service and the localization service, used to retrieve information about the performance of the 5G network and the position of the UEs, respectively.

In the particular T&L sector, several NetApps interact with hardware devices that are deployed in the T&L facility, e.g., with IoT gateways, AGVs, etc. In the NetApp modelling, this is expressed as hardware dependency (the grey box on the left of the picture) since the NetApp functionalities are strictly related to its interaction with these components and its validation requires their presence in the testing environment.

All these characteristics contribute to define a service-oriented description of the NetApps, which can be used by the vertical actors to easily select and manipulate NetApps for building their own vertical services. Following this modelling, the vertical does not need to go into the details of the internal structure of the NetApp, to have the know-how related to its deployment over a virtualized infrastructure or to understand the complex configuration of a 5G network slice. The NetApp package, as a consequence, needs to include two levels of modelling:

- the abstract and service-oriented model, captured in the NetApp blueprint, which defines the metadata used by the vertical to search, operate, combine and test NetApps through the functionalities exposed by the VITAL-5G platform;
- the orchestration-oriented and network-oriented model, captured by the VNF descriptor/package and any related 5G network slice template, which defines how the NetApp components need to be instantiated, dimensioned and interconnected over the virtual computing infrastructure and how the network slices must be configured to properly serve the expected traffic flows. This model is not directly exposed to the vertical, but it is used internally in the VITAL-5G platform and in each of the VITAL-5G testbeds to drive the deployment of the NetApps in their target environments.

5.1.1 Categorization of NetApps

NetApps can be classified following two different types of categorizations: (i) vertical-specific versus vertical-agnostic NetApps and (ii) service-based versus component-based NetApps.

A **vertical-specific NetApp (VS-NetApp)** implements functionalities designed specifically for a given vertical scenario and vertical service. Its usage is related to a specific use case and it is not designed to be easily customized or configured to adapt to different environments or services. Examples of vertical-specific NetApps are software-based IoT gateways specialized for a single type of IoT device, data processing engines with specialized and service-driven logic, dashboards for a predefined type of data, etc. A **vertical-agnostic NetApp (VA-NetApp)**, instead, is a generalized NetApp that can be easily adopted in different services since it supports multiple customizations, data models, processing types, etc. Example of vertical-agnostic NetApps are databases, message brokers, generalized monitoring probes or generalized AI/ML engines.

The other categorization type differentiates between component-based and service-based NetApps. **Component-based NetApps** are atomic and elementary software components that operate in a generalized manner and can be composed together and configured in a flexible manner, so that they can be customized to serve different purposes. A component-based NetApp can be delivered as a packaged set of software images with predefined configurations and interfaces, which can be then updated and customized to build more specialized NetApps delivering their own service. These are typically defined as **service-based NetApps**, i.e., NetApps providing independent services that can be accessed in a standardized manner to support specific business requirements. In this sense, a service-based NetApp can be deployed in stand-alone mode, without any dependency on additional NetApps, and it is able to provide its own complete set of functionalities. A service-based NetApp can include multiple software components, providing added-value services through their interaction. An example of service-based NetApp could be a data collection function that includes authorization

mechanisms and translation of raw data into a common format. In general, multiple component-based NetApps, properly configured and customized, can be combined together to form a service-based NetApp, as shown in Figure 16. Here, for example, the component-based “Data Storage” NetApp, which can be used in general to store different types of data, is configured with specific data models and then used as part of a wider service-based NetApp which implements a monitoring system.

Figure 16: Composition of customized component-based NetApps in a service-based NetApp

5.1.2 NetApps and (T&L) Vertical Services

As described in the previous section, a NetApp can provide its own complete set of functionalities even when deployed as a stand-alone entity. However, it can also cooperate and interact with other NetApps to deliver more complex vertical services. While in VITAL-5G the focus is mostly on T&L services, the concept of 5G-enabled vertical services composed of multiple NetApps is applicable to very different sectors and the VITAL-5G architecture, service modelling and procedures can be considered as general ones, not only limited to the T&L services.

Vertical (T&L) services are loosely coupled chains of cloud-native and 5G ready NetApps, which can leverage the 5G infrastructure and services for their instantiation in virtual environments and their interaction with mobile users and/or IoT and T&L devices deployed in the field in the T&L facilities. NetApps can be reused and composed across multiple vertical services, speeding up and facilitating the design and delivery of new services.

The key difference between a service-based NetApp, composed of multiple software functions, and a Vertical Service composed of multiple NetApp is the fact that a service-based NetApp is distributed with a single package (potentially integrating multiple software images) and delivered by a NetApp developer, following the same principle of VNFs. On the opposite, a Vertical Service is composed of multiple NetApps that can be provided by different vendors and it does not include the internal package distributions, but only their references, following the approach of NFV Network Services.

Figure 17: Example of Vertical Service composed by two NetApps

Figure 17 represents an example of a Vertical Service resulting from the composition of two NetApps, a Data Collection NetApp and a Digital Twin NetApp. The Data Collection is a service-based NetApp that internally is composed of multiple component-based NetApps and offers functions to retrieve data from the field, authorize the data access, translate the data into a common format, store and visualize them. The Data Collection NetApp provides a set of functionalities, accessible from external entities, to (i) configure the NetApp, (ii) retrieve the data from the internal storage and (iii) visualize the data through a dashboard. These functionalities are modelled as “provided interfaces” and they describe the details required by a service provider to compose the NetApps with other ones in order to create a vertical service with additional features. In this example, the Data Collection NetApp provided interfaces are “consumed” by the Digital Twin NetApp, which uses the data retrieved from the storage to build the digital twins of particular objects of interest. As represented in the picture, the Digital Twin NetApp is characterized by a “consumed interface”, that models the need to interact with a NetApp offering those kinds of functionalities. Moreover, the internal details of the Data Collection NetApp can be fully omitted when building a vertical service: as shown in Figure 18, all the NetApps appear as black boxes in the Vertical Service model, keeping only the details of the respective interfaces.

Figure 18: Example of Vertical Service composed by service-based and component-based NetApps

The criteria to compose the vertical services depend on the specific requirements of the service, while the NetApp and vertical service modelling provides the highest level of flexibility in a service-independent manner. In the example reported in Figure 18, the vertical service is composed of NetApps of different types (both service- and component-based) and provided by different vendors. In this particular example, the service provider may be interested in developing its own algorithms and logic for data aggregation and processing, without focusing too much on the techniques to retrieve the data from the various protocol busses in the field or the development of dashboards for graphical interfaces. As a consequence, in order to quickly build a complete end-to-end solution to propose to its customers, he/she complements the “Sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing” NetApp, which constitutes the core of its offering, with a data collection and a visualization NetApp provided by third parties and available in the VITAL-5G catalogue.

Obviously, the decision on the composition logic lies with the service provider, who should take into account both functional and non-functional requirements. The functional requirements can be verified through the analysis of the NetApps’ interfaces, while the non-functional ones need to take into account the performance that can be measured during the experimental validation on the VITAL-5G platform. In this particular example, the composition with the third party Data Collection NetApp on one hand simplifies the data ingestion from heterogeneous sensors exposing a single interface to consume data in a unified format, but on the other hand introduces an additional delay in the whole data collection chain. This may make the overall service suitable for a data processing applied to reporting and medium/long term data analysis, but less applicable for real-time

reactions. The experimental validation functionalities offered by the VITAL-5G platform, with the features to collect and analyze network-level and service-level metrics, will help to identify potential issues in this sense.

It should be also noted that different versions of the same type of NetApp, potentially provided by different vendors, can be adopted to build a vertical service. This approach gives the opportunity to exploit and evaluate the particular customization, internal logic and proprietary algorithms offered by different NetApps and to select the most suitable ones for potentially different operational environments. In the example shown in Figure 19, two vertical services for the visualization of sensors data are adopting two different versions of a Data Collection NetApp, developed by different software providers. This can be useful e.g., in case of NetApps specialized to retrieve data from different field buses or implementing data collection techniques that guarantee different latency. The compatibility of multiple NetApps within a given vertical service depends on their external interfaces, which must be open and specified in the NetApp metadata to allow the service providers to easily compose the NetApps in their end-to-end vertical services. The NetApp internal logic, instead, can be kept proprietary and fully hidden to service providers and experimenters, who would be interested only in the NetApp performance within the overall vertical service.

Figure 19: Example of vertical services using two implementations of the same NetApp

The possibility to use different NetApp versions to replace a logical component of the vertical service is expected to increase the market opportunities for NetApp developers, often SMEs, which can propose custom solutions with added value designed for specialized targets. Similarly, the possibility to build services with extreme flexibility, choosing their components from a wide catalogue and validating their performance in variable contexts is fundamental for the service providers. In fact, on the basis of the experiment results obtained through the VITAL-5G platform, they can deploy a variety of service customizations with different NetApps' version and optimized service tuning, to better match the expectation of particular customers' segments or the 5G network characteristics expected in their target operational environments.

5.2 NetApp Packages

5.2.1 NetApp Package format

Traditional VNF packages provide the software images of the Virtual Deployment Units (VDUs) composing the VNF itself (or Containerized Deployment Units in case of Container-based Network Functions - CNFs) and a VNF descriptor defining how the VNF should be deployed in a target virtual environment (e.g., number and size of VDUs for different deployment flavours of the same network function, internal and external network connectivity, performance metrics to be collected, etc.). Moreover, a typical VNF package also includes a set of additional files and metadata related to the VNF configuration files and software licenses.

NetApps packages extend the concept of VNF packages to provide additional information that facilitates the distribution, deployment and re-use of NetApps in several environments and across multiple application services, focusing particularly on aspects related to:

- NetApps integration into end-to-end service chains combining multiple NetApps (in the VITAL 5G case specific for the T&L sector);
- Automation of NetApps testing and validation, from a functional and non-functional perspective, in a variety of 5G environments.

The definition of this additional information is modelled through NetApps metadata embedded in the NetApp packages and encoded in a NetApp blueprint. Such metadata has a twofold purpose in the context of the VITAL 5G Platform. On one hand they can be shown on the 5G Online Repository to facilitate and enhance the searching and the browsing of NetApps in the VITAL 5G NetApp catalogue. On the other hand, they specify the NetApp-specific logic which is used to drive the automation of NetApp testing and validation in the VITAL 5G target testbed. Moreover, a number of optional files can be embedded in specific folders of the NetApp package to provide additional documentation and test cases to facilitate the usage and validation of NetApps for software developers.

Figure 20: High-level representation of a NetApp package

Figure 20 represents the composition of a NetApp package. In general, the NetApp package is a zipped file that includes a textual file with the NetApp blueprint, used to describe the NetApp metadata, and a variable number of folders including various files, like VNF packages, software licenses, specification documents related to the software design and test cases.

The NetApp packages are used to onboard new NetApps and to download them from the VITAL-5G online repository. In order to make it more manageable, a NetApp package may not include directly the entire VNF package with the related software images (the size of VM image is in the order of GB), but only their references. In this case, the package includes a textual file with URLs to retrieve the VNF package from the NFV Orchestrator catalogues in the VITAL-5G testbed where it is available or from an external software repository used by the NetApp developer to distribute the software.

5.2.2 Information model

Table 7 provides the list of information elements which compose the information model of a NetApp, identifying how they are mapped into the various items that compose a NetApp package. The format of the VNF package

and VNF descriptor follows the specification defined in the ETSI GS NFV-SOL 004 [29] and NFV-SOL 006 [30]. More in detail, the VNF packages used in VITAL-5G are compliant with the format adopted by the OpenSource MANO (OSM) [31] NFV Orchestrator (NFVO), which is available in all the three VITAL-5G testbeds. The format of the NetApp blueprint is a proprietary one, encoded in JSON format, and it follows a similar paradigm to the Vertical Service blueprint originally defined in the context of the 5G EVE project and extended in VITAL-5G to represent the blueprint of a T&L Vertical Service. On the basis of the NetApp package information model, WP2 has defined the related data model, which is documented in deliverable D2.1 [27].

Table 7: Information elements of a NetApp package

NetApp package element	Source	Description
Software images	VNF package	Images of the software to be deployed in the virtual environment to instantiate the components of the NetApp. Software images can be Virtual Machine (VM) images or container images, depending on the adopted virtualization.
Virtual Function (VF) Descriptor	VNF descriptor in VNF package	Descriptor providing the details about the deployment of the NetApp software components in the virtual environments and their lifecycle management. Includes information about the interconnectivity among the components, the external connection points, the virtual resources required to instantiate (or to scale to) different flavors of the function, the configuration, the monitoring metrics, etc.
Software license	License files in NetApp package License element in NetApp blueprint	Provides the licensing term for the NetApp as a whole and, if needed, for its components. License metadata in the NetApp blueprint enables the VITAL-5G platform to perform the e-licenses validation during the instantiation and lifecycle management of NetApps.
NetApp features	NetApp blueprint	Describes the high-level characteristics of the NetApps, like NetApp type, category, target VITAL-5G testbed, access level (public/restricted), related use case, detailed description for users and developers, etc. This information would be used in the VITAL 5G Online Repository to classify NetApps and to visualize their details.
NetApp high-level structure	NetApp blueprint	Provides the high-level and service-oriented description of the NetApp structure, defining its atomic components, how they are interconnected, and the internal and external endpoints used to interact with the NetApp.
5G mobile connectivity requirements	NetApp blueprint	Identifies the NetApp requirements in terms of 5G mobile connectivity, e.g., slice type, target KPI values for minimum throughput in uplink or downlink, maximum latency, etc. These requirements are associated to the external endpoints interconnecting to the 5G network.

5G services requirements (optional)	NetApp blueprint	Identifies the list of 5G services exposed by the 5G core network which may be required by the NetApps. Currently, the network data analytics and the localization services are defined. Their support depends on the capabilities of the 5G network deployed in the VITAL-5G testbed.
Monitoring information	NetApp blueprint	Provides a list of the application and infrastructure metrics that must be monitored to evaluate the performance of the NetApp. Application metrics are generated by the NetApp itself, while infrastructure metrics must be measured at the infrastructure level in the testbed where the NetApp is running. Infrastructure metrics include both 5G network KPIs and metrics related to the usage of computing resources (e.g., used CPU, memory, disk).
Software-related documentation	NetApp blueprint Additional files in NetApp package (optional)	Provides software documentation with the aim of facilitating third party software developers to integrate the NetApp in T&L services. For example, it provides information about the NetApp interfaces, e.g., protocols, message formats, etc. Optionally, the NetApp package can include additional files with protocol-specific interface specification (e.g., OpenAPI spec. for REST API, SQL schemas, etc.).
Test and validation specification (optional)	Additional files in NetApp package (optional)	As an option, NetApps can also specify a list of test cases (with test environment, test scripts, variables to automate the testing execution, etc.) with the related validation criteria to assess the NetApp performance in the target 5G infrastructure. Such testcases can be embedded as files in the NetApp package and they may follow the VITAL-5G Test Case format specified in D1.4 [26].
Hardware requirements (optional)	VNF descriptor	Defines hardware requirements related to the physical servers where the virtualized component of the NetApp will run.
Hardware compatibility (optional)	NetApp blueprint	Provides the list of hardware devices (e.g., IoT sensors/actuators, IoT gateways, AGVs, vessels control system, etc.) which must be installed in the T&L facility and reachable from the NetApp in order to enable its functionalities.

5.3 (T&L) Vertical Services Blueprints

As discussed in section 5.1.2, multiple NetApps potentially provided by different vendors can be stitched together in a service chain that composes a vertical service. The representation of vertical services in VITAL-5G follows the approach originally defined by the 5G-TRANSFORMER project [28] and then further extended in the 5G EVE project [7]. The Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) is used to provide a service-oriented, high-level description of the service characteristics and it constitutes a template that the vertical users can use to customize their services.

The VSB includes the list of the service components, which in VITAL-5G are NetApps, with details about their endpoints and interconnectivity. As for NetApps, the service external endpoints interconnecting to the 5G network are characterized by a service profile that identifies the requirements of the 5G mobile connectivity and drives the selection or provisioning of the 5G network slices. The VSB provides additional information related to the service logic, for example application or infrastructure-level monitoring metrics, a number of variable service parameters that the user can customize to request different versions or deployment flavours of the same service, as well as variable configuration parameters that can be specified at the instantiation time.

The VSB is associated to a Network Service Descriptor (NSD) that describes how the service must be instantiated and orchestrated in an NFV Infrastructure (NFVI) deploying an NFV Network Service (NFV-NS). The NSD is composed of VNFs that, in VITAL-5G, correspond to the VNF packages associated to the NetApps composing the service. The instantiation of the service can follow different flavours, e.g., including or excluding some NetApps and deploying a variable number of instances of the same NetApp. This approach allows, for example, to remove some functionalities or to scale the service dimension based on the target operational environment, e.g., presence of some types of sensors, number of expected mobile users, number of vessels to be controlled, etc.

The various service flavours are modelled internally in the NSD and they can be selected automatically by the VITAL-5G platform on the basis of the vertical service customization requested by the user. This customization can be defined assigning specific values to the variable service parameters declared in the VSB. Such values are encoded in the Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD), that provides the specification of a vertical service requested by the user (e.g., a vertical service provider) filling the template of the VSB. Using some translation rules defined as part of the service design process, the VITAL-5G platform selects the flavour more suitable to meet the requirements specified by the user and instantiates the NFV-NS accordingly in the target VITAL-5G testbed (see Figure 21). In order to simplify the overall service definition, the translation rules are optional in VITAL-5G and, if missing, the service is automatically instantiated with the NFV-NS default flavour.

It is worth to mention that the NFV MANO systems, available in the VITAL-5G testbeds and interfaced by the VITAL-5G platform, are compliant with the NFV MANO functionalities specified by ETSI NFV standards. In this sense, they provide interfaces at the NFV Orchestrator level to instantiate and operate on the lifecycle of NFV network services, while the management of single VNFs is not permitted. In fact, VNFs are usually handled internally through dedicated VNF Managers (VNFM) that are not exposed via external interfaces. This means that the instantiation and testing of single NetApps need to be associated in any case to a corresponding network service, where this network service would include just a single VNF, i.e., the target NetApp itself.

Figure 21: Vertical Service design, customization and instantiation

Table 8 provides a list of the information elements of a (T&L) Vertical Service, specifying where they are defined, i.e., at the VSB, VSD or NSD level. The definition of related data model is in the scope of WP2, and it is documented in D2.1 [27]. The format of the NSD follows the ETSI GS NFV-SOL 006 [30] specification, as adopted by the OSM orchestrator.

Table 8: Information elements of a Vertical Service Blueprint

Information element	Defined in	Description
Vertical Service high-level structure	VSB	Provides the high-level and service-oriented description of the vertical service structure, with a list of its NetApps (referred through their NetApp blueprint), their min/max multiplicity, interconnectivity, endpoints and functions chain. Vertical service endpoints must be mapped to a subset of the NetApps external endpoints.
NFV Network Service Descriptor	NSD	Descriptor providing the details about how the vertical service can be instantiated over a NFVI, identifying the virtual functions to be deployed, how many and the related size, how they must be interconnected internally and to external infrastructure networks, etc. The NSD must refer the VNFDs of the NetApps included in the vertical service.
Vertical Service features	VSB	Provides the high-level description and characteristics of the vertical service, for classification and filtering purposes, e.g., VITAL-5G testbed, access level (public/restricted), related use case, visibility level, human readable description, etc.
Vertical Service customizable parameters	VSB	Provides the list of service-level parameters, configurable from the user, that influence the deployment of the service.
Translation criteria (optional)	Translation rules	Rules that map ranges of values for a subset of the service-level parameters into the corresponding flavour of the NSD. They are used to translate the high-level definition of the service provided by the vertical into the technical description of the NFV-NS to be instantiated. If not defined, the NFV-NS is deployed with its default flavour.
Vertical Service configuration parameters	VSB	Provide the list of parameters that the user can set and configure when requesting the service. Such values are configured on the single NetApps after the instantiation procedure.
5G mobile connectivity requirements	VSB	Identifies the overall service requirements in terms of 5G mobile connectivity. These requirements are associated to the external endpoints of the service interconnecting to the 5G network and, when present, they override the corresponding parameters declared in the NetApp blueprint.
Monitoring information	VSB	Provides a list of the application and infrastructure metrics that must be monitored to evaluate the performance of the service as a whole. The application metrics must be a subset of the ones declared in the NetApps included in the service. Infrastructure

		metrics may include additional items than the ones defined in the NetApps.
Test and validation specification (optional)	Additional files in NetApp package (optional)	As option, NetApps can also specify a list of test cases (with test environment, test scripts, variables to automate the testing execution, etc.) with the related validation criteria to assess the NetApp performance in the target 5G infrastructure. Such testcases can be embedded as files in the NetApp package and they may follow the VITAL-5G Test Case format specified in D1.4 [26]
Hardware compatibility (optional)	VSB	Provides the list of hardware devices which must be installed in the T&L facility to run the service. The list can be a subset of the corresponding items declared in the NetApp blueprints.

5.4 NetApps in the context of 5G PPP activities

A total of nine projects (including VITAL-5G) have been funded by the European Commission in the context of the “H2020-ICT-41-2020: 5G innovations for verticals with third party services” call, targeting the development, validation and promotion of NetApps in various vertical sectors and the engagement with third party experimenters of the respective sectors. Each project is working on precisely defining the concept and capabilities of the NetApps and their related components, as integrated in the overall system architecture as envisioned by each project. The Technical managers of the projects and their experts are currently discussing relevant approaches and insights in the 5G PPP Technology Board (TB) sessions and the respective 5G PPP Working Groups, such as the Architecture WG and the Software Networks WG. Based on the work carried out individually from the projects and through active collaboration, it is the vision of the ICT-41 projects to progress some guidelines regarding the definition, deployment and best practices on the use of NetApps in various vertical sectors. Such a common approach will be defined through the common organization of workshops and webinars, as well as through 5G PPP WG discussions. For the time being each project has defined some key elements that are related to the deployment and use of NetApps, as presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Key elements for NetApps use & deployment

Project Name	Testbeds	Vertical	Considered NetApp aspects
5GASP	Aveiro (PT) Bucharest (RO) Patras (EL) Bristol (UK) Ljubljana (SK) Murcia (ES)	Automotive PPDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated and open DevOps based CI/CD process for developers, to translate their applications / services into NetApps, based on vertical-specific requirements. NetApp store providing access to NetApps, Network Functions and Network Services NetApp marketplace incl. NetApp catalogue
5G-EPICENTRE	Malaga (ES) Aveiro (PT) Barcelona (ES) Berlin (DE)	PPDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open source repository for PPDR 5G NetApps Cloud native transformation Decoupling of network functions from virtual machines (VMs) toward Containerized Network Functions (CNFs) Accommodate a microservices-based model, e.g., deconstructing VNFs into microservices, that can be deployed on a shared cloud infrastructure

5G-ERA	-	Robotics automation for PPDR Automotive Healthcare Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A middleware which enables cloud native resource provision over autonomous robots • Extending 5G open environment and standard APIs of testbeds into robotic vertical sectors
5G-IANA	Ulm (DE) Ljubljana (SK)	Automotive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp Orchestration and Development framework (NOD) • 5G-IANA NetApp toolkit linked with a new Automotive VNFs repository • Data model with a simplified high-level representation of different service components, to hide network complexity
5G-INDUCE	Spain Greece Italy	Industry 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full stack NetApp Management platform • NetApp composition API • Break NetApp into cloud native components • Build/Generate the interconnection of NetApp components • Showcase the full NetApp deployment chain
5G-MEDIAHUB	Norway Spain	Media & Entertainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApps: Application enablement services, offering PaaS extensions (e.g., CDN) • Hiding NFVI and 5G complexities, while supporting cloud-native vertical applications • Offering domain specific (i.e., media) and domain agnostic (e.g., security) NetApps • Unified Northbound APIs for vertical applications • NetApps can span across multiple testbed facilities within Network Slice Instances (NSIs)
EVOLVED-5G	Athens (EL) Malaga (ES)	Industry 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middleware layer that will simplify the implementation and deployment of vertical systems at large scale • 5G-Enabled vertical apps with the aid of NetApps that consume 5G core Northbound APIs • NetApp marketplace and open repository • New North-bound APIs and/or vertical enablers that could fulfil more vertical requirements, such as app-level analytics
SMART 5GRID	Italy Greece Bulgaria	Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated, open, cooperative, and fully featured 5G network platform, customised for smart energy distribution grids • In conjunction with the 5G network facility, the Open Service Repository will have access to network resources and it will be used to develop and accommodate NetApps
VITAL-5G	Antwerp (BE) Athens (EL) Galati (RO)	Transport & Logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online NetApp repository • Cloud-native design and deployment over 5G infrastructures (edge/cloud) • Service-based NetApps: Each NetApp can include multiple virtual components and provides “added-value” services composing different software modules • Component-based NetApps: Atomic software components working in a generalized manner, which can be composed together and configured in custom manners to serve different purposes

6. VITAL-5G Architecture

The high-level architecture of the VITAL-5G system, as originally defined at the proposal stage and still valid in its main concepts and principles, is represented in Figure 22.

Figure 22: High-level architecture of the VITAL-5G system

The overall system is structured in two layers. At the upper layer, the VITAL-5G Platform provides the various actors with a unified access to all the VITAL-5G experimentation services. The VITAL-5G Platform operates over the lower layer of the architecture, composed of a set of testbeds deploying a 5G network infrastructure with virtual computing capabilities and SDN/NFV technologies in three different types of T&L facilities, i.e., a sea and a river port and a warehouse.

The VITAL-5G Platform is composed of two macro blocks, both of them exposing their services through programmable interfaces and web-based graphical interfaces to enable the access for external software entities (e.g., service orchestrators, other vertical applications, etc.) and human actors (e.g., NetApp developers, experimenters, etc.). The Open Online Repository offers the catalogue of NetApps, vertical services and experiments onboarded in the system and allows to upload new services or NetApps and preliminary validate their compatibility with the target testbed. The VITAL-5G Portal offers the mechanisms to provision and manage the vertical services, execute the experiments, retrieve the monitored data and visualize experiment results and reports.

The Open Online Repository and the VITAL-5G Portal interact with the three different testbeds, and in particular with their 5G management system, NFV orchestrator and monitoring system. Some common actions performed over the testbeds include onboarding of new packages and descriptors, instantiation and lifecycle management of services and NetApps in the virtual environments, configuration or selection of 5G network slices in support of the provisioned services, collection of 5G network KPIs and interaction with running NetApps components for configuration and monitoring purposes. Each testbed deploys internally its own 5G infrastructure, SDN/NFV technologies and monitoring platform, with T&L trial facilities deploying specific types of T&L and IoT devices. Despite this technological fragmentation, all the testbeds expose a unified set of basic functionalities towards the VITAL-5G platform. Additional functionalities can be offered as options for more advanced and dynamic procedures. A generalized model for VITAL-5G testbeds, their main services and interfaces, and a common architecture of the facilities are presented in Section 7, as input for the VITAL-5G testbeds deployment in WP3.

This section focuses on the architecture of the VITAL-5G Platform, describing the list of experimentation services provided by the platform (Section 6.10) and discussing how they are consumed by the various actors that interact with the system (Section 6.2). The high-level functional architecture of the VITAL-5G Platform is documented in Section 6.3.

6.1 VITAL-5G Platform Services

The VITAL-5G platform offers a set of services and tools that facilitate the entire experimentation process, during the different experimentation phases introduced in Section 3.3. Table 10 provides an overview of these services and tools, mapping them to the particular experimentation phase and identifying the associated VITAL-5G macro-components (i.e., VITAL-5G testbeds or VITAL-5G Platform, with VITAL-5G Portal and Open Online Repository).

Table 10: Experimentation services and tools offered by VITAL-5G

Experimentation phase	VITAL-5G service or tool	Involved VITAL-5G component
Vertical Service design	Inventory of VITAL-5G testbeds, providing information on 5G network capabilities and available devices in each testbed.	VITAL-5G testbeds VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Schemas for NetApp blueprints and Vertical Service blueprints, to facilitate the design and modelling of new NetApps and services.	VITAL-5G Platform: Open Online Repository
	Catalogue of public NetApps that can be re-used as components to build new vertical service.	VITAL-5G Platform: Open Online Repository
	Onboarding of new NetApps, with validation of NetApp blueprint format, verification of the compatibility with the selected site, onboarding of VNF packages in the NFV orchestrator of the target testbed and functional verification of a successful instantiation in the virtual environment.	VITAL-5G Platform: Open Online Repository VITAL-5G testbeds

	Onboarding of new vertical service blueprints with automated onboarding of NSDs in the NFV orchestrator of the target testbed.	VITAL-5G Platform: Open Online Repository VITAL-5G testbeds
Experiment design	Schemas for Experiment blueprints, to facilitate the design and modelling of new experiments.	VITAL-5G Platform: Open Online Repository
	Onboarding of new experiment blueprints, with validation of blueprint format and verification of compatibility with the declared vertical services.	VITAL-5G Platform: Open Online Repository
	Guided definition of experiment blueprints with a wizard to select vertical service, network and service KPIs, evaluation criteria, test cases, and configuration parameters	VITAL-5G Platform: Open Online Repository
Preparation of 5G testing environment	Wizard or intent-based tools to customize, configure and schedule an experiment, to be selected from experiment blueprints available in the Open Online Repository.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal and Open Online Repository
Vertical Service instantiation	Automated provisioning of vertical service with instantiation and configuration of its NetApps.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Automated configuration or selection of 5G network slices to support the vertical service.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Activation and configuration of service and network KPIs monitoring.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Validation of software licenses for NetApps to be instantiated or scaled up.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal and Open Online Repository
	Manual or automated lifecycle management of instantiated services and NetApps (e.g., for scaling or re-configuration purposes).	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds

	Secure interaction between NetApps and well-defined sets of devices in T&L facilities.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Direct and secure access to instantiated NetApps for manual re-configuration and troubleshooting.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
Experiment execution	Customization, configuration and launch of experiments.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Automated configuration and execution of test scripts.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Collection and elaboration of monitoring data: retrieval of network KPIs from the testbed infrastructure and collection of service KPIs from NetApps components.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Visualization of monitoring data collected in near-real-time through graphs and dashboards.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Direct and secure access to instantiated NetApps for execution of test scripts and troubleshooting.	VITAL-5G testbeds
	APIs to trigger lifecycle management actions on the instantiated service and NetApps in a programmable manner.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	APIs to retrieve monitoring data for service and network KPIs in a programmable manner.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
Vertical Service evaluation	Analysis of experiment results.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Validation of network and service KPIs.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	AI-based diagnostics for identification of bottlenecks and origin of performance degradation	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Experiment reporting	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal

6.2 Mapping between VITAL-5G services and roles/actors

The users of the services provided by the VITAL-5G platform can be aggregated in three main categories, i.e., NetApp developers, Service Providers and Experimenters. These three categories, derived from the roles and actors defined in section 3.2, identify three different profiles of users that can access the VITAL-5G platform where, for each profile, a number of actions are enabled on the system. The three user categories can be described as follows:

- **NetApp developers**, in charge of NetApps' design and implementation. They use the VITAL-5G platform for onboarding their NetApps in the VITAL-5G system, through the Open Online Repository, so that they can become available as building blocks for vertical services. The category of NetApp developers includes also developers of VNFs, i.e., functions related only to networking that can be composed together with NetApps into end-to-end services. NetApps developers may be not specifically focused in the experimental testing of their applications, but just interested in sharing them on the VITAL-5G catalogue to promote their adoption in a wide community.
- **Service providers**, in charge of building vertical services through the composition of one or more NetApps and, optionally, network functions. Service providers can visualize and reuse public NetApps, define and onboard new vertical services, as well as request their instantiation in one of the VITAL-5G testbed. The category of service providers includes also roles like vertical service developers and system integrators. Service providers may be not specifically focused in the experimental testing of their vertical services, but just interested to orchestrate their deployment and execution in the production environment of a VITAL-5G testbed. This may be the case of a post-testing phase, where the service is actually delivered and operated in its target environment.
- **Experimenters**, a broader category of users of the VITAL-5G platform. Experimenters are interested in validating new NetApps or services that can be provided entirely by themselves, built using third party NetApps or simply available in the VITAL-5G repository. Consequently, experimenters have the possibility to onboard new NetApps or services, visualize the already existing ones, instantiate and manage new services, design, onboard and launch new experiments and visualize the related monitoring data, reports and diagnostic results. Experimenters are thus focused on the testing of NetApps and services, usually performed before their final launch on the "public" catalogue for massive adoption from external users and their operational delivery in the target environment.

In VITAL-5G all users are associated to one or more of these three categories, which regulates the kind of actions that they can perform over the VITAL-5G platform. Moreover, users are associated to user groups, corresponding to VITAL-5G use cases. The user group regulates the visibility and accessibility to items that are not public, but specifically associated to a use case and, consequently, that can be visualized, used or manipulated only by the members participating in that use case. For example, sensors deployed in the T&L facility for a specific use case will be visible only to that use case participants; similarly, private NetApps designed for a single use case will be available only to compose vertical services and run experiments related to that use case.

Table 11 summarizes the actions permitted for the three user categories in each of the experimentation phases, assuming that the user belongs to the related use case. All the functionalities offered by the VITAL-5G platform for the related actions are implicitly supported, as described in the previous section. For example, the onboarding of a new NetApp includes the access to the NetApp blueprint schemas, the verification of the NetApp compatibility with selected testbed, the validation of the NetApp package format, the onboarding of the VNF package in the target testbed, etc.

Table 11: Actions enabled for VITAL-5G user categories

Action on VITAL-5G platform enabled for...	NetApp Developer	Service Provider	Experimenter
Vertical Service design			
Visualization of information on VITAL-5G testbed capabilities	Y	Y	Y
Visualization of available NetApp packages	Y	Y	Y
Onboarding of new NetApp packages	Y	N	Y
Modification or removal of existing NetApp packages	Y (only owned NetApps not in use)	N	Y (only owned NetApps not in use)
Visualization of available Vertical Service Blueprints	N	Y	Y
Onboarding of new Vertical Service Blueprints	N	Y	Y
Modification or removal of existing Vertical Service Blueprints	N	Y (only owned services not in use)	Y (only owned services not in use)
Experiment design			
Visualization of available experiment blueprints	N	N	Y
Onboarding of new experiment blueprints, via REST API, upload via web GUI or web GUI wizard.	N	N	Y
Modification or removal of existing experiment blueprints	N	N	Y (only owned experiments not in use)
Preparation of 5G testing environment			
Visualization of available Vertical Service Descriptors	N	Y	Y
Onboarding of new Vertical Service Descriptors, via REST API, upload via web GUI or web GUI wizard.	N	Y	Y
Modification or removal of existing Vertical Service Descriptors	N	Y (only owned services not in use)	Y (only owned services not in use)
Visualization of available Experiment Descriptors	N	N	Y
Onboarding of new Experiment Descriptors, via REST API, upload via web GUI or web GUI wizard.	N	N	Y
Modification or removal of existing Experiment Descriptors	N	N	Y

			(only owned services not in use)
Vertical Service instantiation			
Request to instantiate new vertical services	N	Y	Y
Visualization of details about instantiated vertical services and related NetApps	N	Y	Y
Request to scale up/down a vertical service (via GUI or REST API)	N	Y	Y
Request to terminate a vertical service (via GUI or REST API)	N	Y	Y
Visualization and access to monitoring data related to a vertical service	N	Y	Y
Access to vertical service's NetApps	N	Y	Y
Experiment execution			
Request to launch new experiments	N	N	Y
Visualization of details about running experiments	N	N	Y
Launch of test scripts and access to NetApps during experiment execution	N	N	Y
Visualization of monitoring data related to the experiment execution on the VITAL-5G Portal web GUI	N	N	Y
Retrieval of monitoring data related to the experiment execution via REST API	N	N	Y
Request to scale up/down a vertical service involved in the experiment execution (via GUI or REST API)	N	N	Y
Request to terminate a vertical service involved in the experiment execution (via GUI or REST API)	N	N	Y
Vertical Service evaluation			
Visualization of experiment results	N	N	Y
Visualization of diagnostics results	N	N	Y
Visualization and download of experiment reports	N	N	Y

6.3 VITAL-5G Platform

This section describes the functional architecture of the VITAL-5G platform. Starting from the main architectural principles that have driven its design (Section 6.3.1) also on the basis of the requirements discussed in Section 4.2, the main system components of VITAL-5G Portal and Open Online Repository (also called VITAL-5G Catalogue) are identified in Section 6.3.2. Potential deployment models for the VITAL-5G architecture are discussed in Section 6.3.3, focusing on the model selected for the reference implementation of the architecture,

which will be developed in WP2 and installed and operated in WP3 and WP4 for the execution of the trials. The high-level workflows, northbound and southbound interfaces are finally described in Section 6.3.4, 6.3.5, and 6.3.6, following an abstract and protocol-independent approach. The specification of protocol messages and Open API will be addressed in the context of WP2, as part of the implementation of the reference architecture. The internal functional elements of the VITAL-5G Platform will be described in Section 8.

6.3.1 Architectural Principles

The VITAL-5G Platform has been designed according to the following guidelines and architectural principles:

1. The VITAL-5G Platform should be designed to enable experimentation services for internal and external users, with different profiles and access rights, providing functionalities and features customized for the various levels of expertise of the planned user categories. In particular, the access to the VITAL-5G experimentation services should be facilitated and simplified following a vertical-driven perspective but providing additional options for enhanced configurability, programmability and flexibility in 5G network configuration and service management.
2. The access to the VITAL-5G Platform services should be enabled both via graphical user interfaces for human interactions and via programmable, open interfaces for third-party systems interactions.
3. The VITAL-5G Platform should support multi-tenancy and concurrent experimentations for multiple users over the same infrastructure.
4. The VITAL-5G Platform should provide secure and isolated access to private or restricted resources, based on user profiles and user groups, while guaranteeing full visibility and access to public resources⁶.
5. The VITAL-5G Platform should be compatible with the architectures, functional elements and interfaces of 5G systems, as defined in the 3GPP specifications, assuming that VITAL-5G testbeds will deploy 5G network infrastructures compliant with the standards and will make use of the latest NFV and SDN technologies for deployment of virtualized network and service functions and, where needed, configuration of the transport network.
6. The VITAL-5G Platform should be compliant with 3GPP and ETSI standards for its interaction with the VITAL-5G testbeds, adopting where relevant de-facto standards. This will guarantee the exploitability of the VITAL-5G Platform software (even beyond the project termination) facilitating its interoperability with common deployments of 5G networks and infrastructures.
7. The VITAL-5G Platform should be designed following a modular approach with unified abstract interfaces that enables a simple integration with (additional) testbeds supporting enhanced functionalities or proprietary interfaces, to be supported developing testbed-specific adaptors.
8. The design of the VITAL-5G Platform should maximize the re-usage of existing architectural components from previous 5G PPP projects (in particular 5G EVE) which have developed open platforms for experimental validation of 5G-enabled services for internal and external users. In particular, the introduction of new components should be limited to the support of additional functionalities or features, while solutions based on extensions, adaptations and customizations of existing modules should be preferred. When new functional elements are required, their interfaces should be designed to facilitate their integration with the existing platform components and workflows, without a major impact on the overall system.
9. The design of the VITAL-5G Platform should be inspired by Service Based Architecture (SBA) principles, with each functional element providing an interface to enable the consumption of its services from the other elements of the system or the final users. Depending on the type of expected interactions,

⁶ Here a resource represents a generic item managed by the VITAL-5G platform, e.g., a NetApp blueprint or a NetApp instance, an IoT device in a VITAL-5G testbed, a deployed service, a 5G network slice, an experiment, etc.

query/reply patterns for synchronous communication as well as subscribe/notify patterns for asynchronous communication should be supported.

10. The design of the VITAL-5G Platform should enable the deployment of its components in a virtualized computing environment, with mechanisms for modular, dynamic, configurable and automatic orchestration.
11. At the functional architecture level, the design of the VITAL-5G Platform should be protocol and language agnostic, enabling different implementations of the same functionalities and components. The specific decisions on protocols, formats and language of the messages, etc. will be taken during the implementation activities in WP2.
12. All the north-bound interfaces of the VITAL-5G Platform should be open to facilitate its integration with third party systems.
13. The VITAL-5G Platform should follow a modular design easy to extend and configure for supporting additional capabilities, technologies and functionalities that may be introduced in next releases of the platform itself or in the VITAL-5G testbeds.

6.3.2 VITAL-5G Platform Functional Architecture

The functional architecture of the VITAL-5G system is represented in Figure 23, highlighting the centralized VITAL-5G Platform that operates over the three VITAL-5G testbeds. The VITAL-5G platform is structured in two main components, i.e., the VITAL-5G Portal backend and the Open Online Repository (called also VITAL-5G Catalogue), each of them including a number of functional elements and supported by a set of management backend services. Both Portal backend and Open Online Repository provides north-bound interfaces (NBI) that allow the VITAL-5G users to securely access the authorized VITAL-5G services (see Section 6.1) in a programmable manner, mostly via REST APIs. On top of these interfaces, a unified web-based GUI offers an additional graphical Portal with dedicated tools, designed to simplify the users' manual interaction with the VITAL-5G platform, for both VITAL-5G Portal and Catalogue.

On its south-bound interface (SBI), the VITAL-5G Platform interacts with the platforms, services and tools deployed in the VITAL-5G testbeds. This interface is designed with a modular and plugin-based approach that deals with the diversity of capabilities and APIs related to the three testbeds while exposing a uniform layer towards the functional elements of the VITAL-5G platform. As further analysed in Section 7, each VITAL-5G testbed provides a number of common functionalities towards the platform. In particular, NFV MANO for the orchestration of NFV network services (including NFVO catalogue and service lifecycle management functions), infrastructure monitoring for both 5G network and virtual computing resources in cloud and/or edge environments, management and inventory of 5G network slices, as well as an inventory of the hardware available at the trial facility, e.g., for IoT and T&L devices.

Figure 23: VITAL-5G Functional Architecture

Table 12 provides the list of the VITAL-5G Platform functional elements, describing their functionalities and identifying their NBI and/or SBI⁷ where relevant. A more comprehensive description of each component will be provided in Section 8.

Table 12: Functional elements of VITAL-5G platform

VITAL-5G Platform Functional Element	Description	NBI	SBI
VITAL-5G Open Online Repository			
NetApp Catalogue	Provides the catalogue of the NetApp packages available in the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, managing the synchronization with the related VNF packages onboarded in each VITAL-5G testbed.	Onboarding, query and removal of NetApp packages	Onboarding, query and removal of VNF packages (associated to NetApps) on NFVO catalogue.
Service Catalogue	Provides the catalogue of the VSBs and VSDs available in the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, managing the synchronization with the related NSDs onboarded in each VITAL-5G testbed.	Onboarding, query and removal of VSBs (with related NSDs) and VSDs.	Onboarding, query and removal of NSDs (associated to VSBs) on

⁷ Only NBI/SBI functions related to external interactions are reported, i.e., with VITAL-5G platform users on the NBI and with VITAL-5G testbeds on the SBI.

			NFVO catalogue.
Experiment Catalogue	Provides the catalogue of the experiment blueprints (ExpB) and descriptors (ExpD), including potential test scripts, available in the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository.	Onboarding, query and removal of ExpBs and ExpDs.	N/A (ExpB/ExpD kept locally in VITAL-5G Platform)
NetApp Validator	Provides the functionalities to validate the format of a NetApp package, verify its compatibility with the target testbed and, as option, test its instantiation in the target virtual environment.	Validate NetApp package. Test NetApp deployment.	Instantiation of VNF package (where supported).
NetApp License Storage & Manager	Provides a storage for the licenses associated to the NetApps and the functionalities to validate them during the lifecycle of the vertical services.	Onboarding of license information	N.A. (Internal component)
VITAL-5G Portal Backend			
Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager (LCM)	Implements the procedures to instantiate and manage vertical services, performing the translation to the NFV-NS, coordinating its lifecycle management interacting with the NFVO at the VITAL-5G testbeds, activating the monitoring and selecting or creating the required 5G network slices.	Instantiate, scale, configure, terminate vertical services.	Instantiate, scale, configure, terminate NFV-NSs. Select, create, configure 5G network slices.
Service & Network Monitoring	Provides a centralized monitoring platform for the collection, storage, retrieval and visualization of monitoring data, for both network and service KPIs. Monitoring data are pushed into this monitoring platform in a unified format by the monitoring systems available in each VITAL-5G testbed and by NetApps with service monitoring capabilities.	Query and visualization of monitoring data.	Collection of service and network KPIs.
Service Testing & Experiment Manager	Implements the procedures to execute an experiment over a running vertical service, coordinating the execution of test scripts and triggering the analysis of the experiment results.	Launch and terminate experiments. Retrieve experiment results.	N.A.
Intent-Based Requests Manager	Translates intent-based requests into vertical service or experiment requests, following the format of VSDs and ExpDs.	Intent-based service or	N.A.

		experiment request.	
Result Analytics	Elaborates the monitoring data collected through the Service & Network Monitoring to compute the experiment results.	Query experiment results	N.A.
AI-based Diagnostics	Elaborates the monitoring data and the experiment results through AI-based techniques for advanced experiment diagnostics.	Query experiment diagnostics	N.A.
AI-based Placement & Life-Cycle Management Logic	Optional internal service that may be invoked by the Vertical Service LCM to request the optimal placement of NetApp components or to automate the execution of service scaling actions.	N.A.	N.A.
VITAL-5G Management Backend			
Multi-site Inventory	Provides a manually configured inventory of systems, platforms, tools and IoT/T&L devices available in each site.	Query IoT/T&L devices.	N.A.
Access Control	Provides the mechanisms for authorizing the access to the various services of the VITAL-5G platform.	Management of user accounts.	N.A.
Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory	Provides a centralized inventory for the 5G network slices configured in the various VITAL-5G testbed. In case of testbeds with programmable APIs for slice management, it mediates the creation, retrieval and termination of network slices.	Query of 5G network slices and slice management capabilities. Creation and termination of network slices.	Query, creation and termination of 5G network slices, if supported on the testbed.

6.3.3 Deployment Models for VITAL-5G Architecture

The deployment model selected for the reference implementation of the VITAL-5G platform, which will be used during the execution of the project, is based on a centralized pattern. This model, shown in Figure 24, is characterized by a central cross-testbed platform deployed in a single instance (placed on the Romanian testbed), which provides a unified access to all the VITAL-5G users, independently on the target testbed where they will execute their experiments. The VITAL-5G platform is managed in centralized mode, in the context of the VITAL-5G project execution and activities, and it handles internally multi-site inventories, catalogues, repositories for all the users, NetApps, services, network slices, IoT devices, etc. At its southbound, it is interconnected to all the three testbeds via secure VPNs and implements testbed-specific drivers to mediate the interaction with the heterogeneous orchestrators, monitoring systems, 5G network infrastructures, etc. deployed in each testbed.

Figure 24: Centralized deployment model for VITAL-5G architecture

The choice of this solution is particularly suitable during the project runtime since it simplifies the development, integration, testing, configuration, troubleshooting and maintenance activities, which are applied to the single platform. In other terms, we can consider a single and centralized administration of the VITAL-5G platform, operating within the project consortium, that is responsible for the overall platform operation and interacts with the various testbeds administration, responsible instead for the single T&L facilities and 5G infrastructures, with related users, services, devices, etc. The users that want to access the VITAL-5G services require an agreement in place with the VITAL-5G consortium and can interact with the overall system using the unified and centralized access of the VITAL-5G platform.

However, in order to guarantee a proper exploitability of VITAL-5G results and testbeds after the termination of the project, the testbed owners can deploy per-testbed instances of the VITAL-5G platform in order to continue to offer 5G experimentation services over their own 5G infrastructure and T&L facility. The resulting deployment model, applied to the Antwerp testbed as an example but applicable to all the three testbeds, is represented in Figure 25. In this case, the VITAL-5G Platform is deployed in Antwerp and it is managed by the Antwerp testbed administrator, together with the testbed itself. At the southbound, only the Antwerp testbed driver is adopted, simplifying the maintenance and troubleshooting when the single testbed is updated with new releases of 5G networks, orchestrator, monitoring systems, etc. Similarly, the internal databases of the VITAL-5G platform will store only the information related to the Antwerp site users, NetApps, services, devices, etc., simplifying the overall operational and management procedures. Finally, in this post-project scenario, the users will have business agreements directly with the operators of the target testbed, or third-party entities managing the business of experiment validation services over the given testbed. In this scenario, additional business agreements may be in place between the testbed operators and the developers of the VITAL-5G platform software, e.g., for licenses of closed source software components, for software support and maintenance of open-source software components, for system integration and/or new software developments to support updates in the testbeds' systems.

Figure 25: Distributed, per-testbed deployment model of VITAL-5G architecture

6.3.4 High-level Workflows and Procedures

Keep open to support both options for network slice selection and dynamic creation

This section describes the high-level workflows for the main procedures implemented by the VITAL-5G platform, as follows:

- Onboarding of a new NetApp package
- Instantiation of a Vertical Service
- Creation, execution and monitoring of an experiment

The workflows are presented as message sequence diagrams showing the interactions among the various functional elements of the VITAL-5G platform and, where needed, the VITAL-5G testbeds. In these workflows the usage of the VITAL-5G Platform Web GUI is assumed as the single entry-point for the system. Alternatively, the users may access the platform directly through the REST APIs of its components.

The access control mechanisms are omitted in this representation of the workflows, for readability reasons. However, they are implicitly applied to evaluate the feasibility of each action requested by the user on the basis of user category and user group, as well as the use case associated to the requests, following the criteria explained in Section 6.2. The access control requires initially the authentication of the user via username and password. The authentication procedure can be mediated through the user login at the GUI or performed directly via REST API interacting with the Access Control component and returns a token that is used to authorize all the following requests: (i) NetApp Package Onboarding, (ii) Vertical Service Instantiation and (iii) Experiment creation, execution and monitoring.

6.3.4.1 NetApp Package Onboarding

The workflow to onboard a new NetApp package in the VITAL-5G platform, making it available on the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, is shown in Figure 26.

The first step is the onboarding of the VNF package, which includes the software image and the VNFD of the NetApp software. From the GUI, the VNF package is onboarded directly on the target VITAL-5G testbed, in its NFVO catalogue. The information about URL and credentials to reach the NFVO can be obtained with a query (omitted in the picture) to the Multi-site Inventory. The NFVO returns the unique ID assigned locally to the VNF package.

Figure 26: Workflow for NetApp Package onboarding

The second step is the onboarding of the NetApp Package, which includes the reference to the VNF package ID returned previously by the NFVO, the NetApp blueprint and all the other elements presented in section 5.2. The NetApp package is onboarded through the GUI, which preliminarily validate its format with the NetApp Validator and then forwards it to the NetApp Catalogue. Here the package is unzipped and the NetApp blueprint is processed to verify its compatibility with the target site. In particular, the NetApp requirements in terms of IoT or T&L devices and 5G connectivity are compared with the testbed information retrieved from the Multi-site Inventory. The objective is to verify the presence of the required hardware and, in case of testbeds with pre-

configured network slices, the availability of slices matching the service profiles declared in the NetApp blueprint. The NetApp package is then stored in the NetApp catalogue and the assigned unique ID is returned. As optional step, the NetApp catalogue may initiate an additional interaction with the NetApp Validator in order to validate, from a functional point of view, the correct instantiation of the NetApp in the target testbed. In this case, the NetApp Validator interacts with the NFVO to request a testing instantiation of the VNF associated to the NetApp and verify its status.

The final step of the workflow is required only for proprietary NetApps with licenses managed through the VITAL-5G Platform. In this case, the NetApp developer can onboard the licenses granted for the usage of the NetApp to specific tenants. The licenses are stored into the NetApp License Storage & Manager component (License Manager in the picture) where they will be verified during the NetApp provisioning phase.

The onboarding of VSB and ExpB follows a similar procedure, also mediated through the GUI, but involving the Service Catalogue and Experiment Catalogue respectively. The VSB includes also the related Network Service Descriptor, which is onboarded in the NFVO at the target testbed. Once onboarded, all the NetApp packages, VSB and ExpB can be visualized through the GUI or retrieved with queries to the REST APIs of the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository.

6.3.4.2 Vertical Service Instantiation

The instantiation of a Vertical Service allows the service to be deployed in its target testbed, with the creation of all its NetApps and the interconnection to the 5G network through the usage of network slices compatible with the 5G slice profile characteristics defined in the blueprints. Once instantiated, the user can visualize the information of the service on the VITAL-5G Portal GUI and obtain details about its NetApps, assigned network slice, IP addresses, etc., which can be used to properly interact with the various service components.

The initial step that the user needs to perform is the specification of the desired service characteristics, configuring the variable service parameters which are declared in the service blueprint. This step is facilitated by the GUI, which can show the configurable fields for the selected service. The result is a Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD) which is onboarded in the Service Catalogue of the Open Online Repository, as shown in Figure 27. Here a unique VSD identifier is generated and the VSD is stored in the internal database, returning the VSD ID which can be visualized by the user on the GUI.

Figure 27: Workflow for definition of a Vertical Service via VSD specification

Once created, the VSD can be used as reference for the instantiation of vertical services matching those characteristics. The procedure is depicted in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Workflow for instantiation of a vertical service

Using the GUI, the user selects the target testbed and the desired VSD, and specifies some information for the given service instance, e.g., the UEs to be connected, configuration parameters for the applications, license keys for proprietary NetApps if required. The GUI triggers the instantiation request to the Vertical Service LCM

component, which updates its internal records and coordinates the entire instantiation procedure operating in asynchronous mode and returning immediately the unique identifier of the Vertical Service instance (VS_ID in the picture). This ID can be used anytime to query the Vertical Service LCM about service status and information, in order to follow the progress of the instantiation steps. The various steps can be summarized as follows:

- The Vertical Service LCM retrieves from the Service Catalogue of the Open Online Repository the VSD and the related VSB, which is used to identify the required NetApps. The NetApps blueprints (NAB) are also retrieved from the NetApp Catalogue. Processing the blueprints and VSD information, the Vertical Service LCM determines the NSD of the network service to be instantiated in the VITAL-5G testbed and the profiles of the required 5G network slices. Moreover, it determines if there are NetApps that require the validation of their software licenses before proceeding with their deployment.
- In case of NetApp software licenses to be validated, the Vertical Service LCM issues requests to the License Manager of the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository to get the approval for the NetApp deployment, providing information on the license key of the user and the expected size of the NetApp (for usage-based licenses, see section 8.2.3 for further details).
- The Vertical Service LCM queries the Multi-site Inventory to get details about slicing capabilities and NFVO deployed at the VITAL-5G testbed where the service will be instantiated. This information is used to properly interact with the target testbed.
- The Vertical Service LCM interacts with the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory to request the configuration of the network slices, providing slice profiles and UEs (i.e., through their IMSI). The actual configuration of the slice depends on the testbed capabilities. If network slices can be managed dynamically and in a programmable manner, they are created and configured on-demand through the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory. If the testbed requires a static and manual management of the network slices, they must be created from the testbed administrator in advance and stored in the inventory. In this case, at this stage the network slices are already existing, and they are just selected by the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory on the basis of the requested service profiles and configured with the UEs.
- Once the 5G network slices are in place and properly configured, the Vertical Service LCM interacts with the NFVO at the testbed to request the provisioning and configuration of the NFV network service that includes the NetApps. Depending on the testbed information collected from the Multi-site Inventory, the Vertical Service LCM may indicate particular networks configured on the testbed to interconnect the service to the most suitable data networks available in the target infrastructure (e.g., to guarantee the external access, or the connection to local data networks placed at the edge, etc.). After the successful instantiation of the NFV network service, the Vertical Service LCM gathers all the details of the service and its NetApps (e.g., assigned IDs and IP addresses) and updates its internal record.
- Depending on the type of NetApp software licenses, the Vertical Service LCM may need to notify the License Manager about the successful instantiation, so that it can update its internal counters (e.g., number of running NetApp instances for a given user).
- Finally, the Vertical Service LCM interacts with the Service and Network Monitoring component to activate the collection of the metrics and KPIs associated to the vertical service, as declared in the service and NetApps' blueprints, specifying the topics where the monitoring data will be published.

At the end of the procedure, the Vertical Service and all its NetApps are properly instantiated, configured and running. Moreover, the collection of the monitoring data is in place. The user can visualize the details of the service using the GUI, as shown in Figure 29. Such information can then be used to connect to the various NetApps, request LCM actions on the running service (e.g., scaling) or retrieve monitoring data with specific filters using the interface of the Service and Network Monitoring.

Figure 29: Workflow for retrieval of Vertical Service information

6.3.4.3 Experiment creation, execution and monitoring

The workflow for the creation, execution and monitoring of experiments is represented in Figure 30. As for the vertical services, there is an initial phase where the user can specify the parameters of the experiment, through the creation of an Experiment Descriptor (ExpD), which will provide the values for the variable parameters defined in the Experiment Blueprint (ExpB). The ExpD is onboarded in the Experiment Catalogue of the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, where it is stored in the internal database.

Then, the user can proceed with the request for the creation of the experiment, specifying its ExpD ID, the ID of the Vertical Service (previously instantiated) which is associated to the experiment and a number of configuration parameters for tuning the conditions of the testing environment and the test execution. The request is forwarded from the GUI to the Service Testing & Experiment Manager component, which is in charge of coordinating all the procedures related to the experiment lifecycle. It initially retrieves ExpB and ExpD from the catalogue and locks the vertical service on the Vertical Service LCM. It should be noted that only a single experiment is permitted over a vertical service instance, in order to avoid overlapping test executions; as a consequence, if the vertical service is already locked the experiment is rejected.

If the experiment can be accepted, the Service Testing & Experiment Manager creates a new entry in its record and returns the unique experiment ID (Exp_ID in the picture). This ID can be used to query the status and the progress of the experiment during its entire lifecycle, as well as request actions related to its testing procedure. In particular, in order to start the experiment, the user needs to launch an experiment execution. As option, the user may provide configuration parameters that would override the ones set during the experiment creation. This would allow the running of different experiment versions with changed configuration settings, enabling results to be compared.

Figure 30: Workflow for experiment creation, execution and monitoring

The launch of the experiment execution triggers a number of actions under the coordination of the Service Testing & Experiment Manager. If one of these actions fails, a roll-back procedure is performed. In particular, the following actions are performed:

- Configuration of KPIs on the Service and Network Monitoring component, activating the collection of the KPIs that will be computed during the execution of the experiments and published on a given set of topics.

- Configuration of the NetApps with the testing parameters.
- Configuration of the Results Analytics notifying the launch of the experiment execution and triggering the computation of the KPIs.

Once the configuration is completed, the VITAL-5G platform is ready to process the monitoring data and elaborate the KPIs. At this stage, the user can connect to the NetApp, execute scripts, operate on the user equipment, etc., as required by the experiment execution. In the meantime, the monitoring data from all the configured sources at the VITAL-5G testbed (i.e., for 5G network, infrastructure, and service metrics) will be published in the Service & Network Monitoring component and consumed by the Result Analytics, which will elaborate the KPIs following the criteria defined in the experiment blueprint. Such KPIs will be in turn published in the Service & Network Monitoring. The collected metrics and KPIs will be made available through the GUI, with graphs. Alternatively, the user may retrieve them using the programmable interface of the Service & Network Monitoring. As an option, the Service Testing & Experiment Manager may trigger the execution of testing scripts in the various NetApps of the service, to automate some of the testing actions.

When the experiment execution is terminated, the user sends a request to stop it. Then, the Service Testing & Experiment Manager interacts with the Results Analytic component to notify the end of the experiment execution and to trigger the validation of the experiment results, on the basis of the target KPIs values defined in the ExpD. An experiment result report is generated and made available for the user. In this phase, if the diagnostic feature is enabled, the Results Analytic can further interact with the AI-based Diagnostic component to trigger the performance diagnosis algorithms (this optional step is not represented in the picture since the details for this part of the workflow are reported in deliverable D2.1 [27]). When the validation phase is concluded, the Service Testing & Experiment Manager cleans up all the testing configuration previously applied to the NetApps and updates the internal experiment record.

It should be noted that after the conclusion of an experiment execution, the user can launch another one over the same experiment. This can be repeated until the experiment as a whole is terminated by the user, triggering the release of the lock on the associated vertical service.

6.3.5 North-bound Interface

The design of the VITAL-5G Platform architecture follows the principles of a Service Based Architecture, with all its functional elements exposing open interfaces to provide access to their services and functionalities. All the consumers of these services can simply implement the client-side of such interfaces. In VITAL-5G, some VITAL-5G Platform functional elements provide interfaces which can be consumed by the platform users; the whole set of these interfaces constitutes the VITAL-5G Platform North-bound interface (NBI).

The adoption of REST APIs for the implementation of the VITAL-5G Platform NBI will be adopted in WP2; however further implementations based on different protocols are also possible (e.g., based on protocol buffers). All the requests received on the NBI must be authenticated and authorized, on the basis of the user's profile and associated groups. The access to the NBI can be performed in a programmable manner or through the mediation of the VITAL-5G Platform GUI. In the former case, the user will need to compose the message and trigger the request. For example, assuming the adoption of REST APIs, the requests can be issued via REST clients embedded in users' applications or via stand-alone REST clients (e.g., Postman⁸, Curl⁹ ...). In the latter case, the user will interact with the GUI, which will act as REST client and it will be responsible for the composition of the messages, the issue of the request and the reception and processing of the response.

⁸ <https://www.postman.com/>

⁹ <https://curl.se/>

Table 13 summarizes the NBI exposed by the relevant VITAL-5G Platform components. It should be noted that some elements provide only internal interfaces not belonging to the NBI (i.e., interfaces consumed only by other elements of the platform) and, consequently, they are not mentioned in the table.

Table 13: North-bound Interface of VITAL-5G Platform

Functional component	Interface	Main functionalities
NetApp Catalogue	N_Cat: management of NetApp packages and NetApp blueprints.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboard/Remove/Download NetApp package Download NetApp package artifacts Download VNF Package associated to a NetApp package Get NetApp blueprint Get VNFD associated to a NetApp package Get (filtered) lists of NetApp blueprints
Service Catalogue	S_Cat: management of Vertical Service Blueprints (VSB) and Vertical Service Descriptors (VSD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboard/Remove/Update/Get VSB Onboard/Remove/Update/Get NSD associated to a VSB Onboard/Remove/Update/Get translation rules to map VSBs and NSDs Onboard/Remove/Update/Get VSD Get (filtered) list of VSBs and VSDs
Experiment Catalogue	E_Cat: management of Experiment Blueprints (ExpB) and Experiment Descriptors (ExpD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboard/Remove/Update/Get ExpB Onboard/Remove/Update/Get ExpD Get (filtered) list of ExpBs and ExpDs
NetApp Validator	N_Val: inventory of blueprint schemas, validation of blueprints and NetApp packages, testing of NetApp deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get NetApp/Vertical Service/Experiment blueprint schema Get Vertical Service/Experiment descriptor schema Get VNFD/NSD schema Validate NetApp/VS/Experiment blueprint Validate NetApp package Test NetApp deployment
NetApp License Storage & Manager	NL_Mgt: management of licenses assigned to VITAL-5G users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboard/Remove/Modify/Get software license
Multi-site Inventory	Dev_Mgt: management of devices in VITAL-5G testbeds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboard/Remove/Update device in VITAL-5G testbed (admin action)

		Get device information Get (filtered) list of devices available in VITAL-5G testbeds
Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory	Slice_Mgt: management of network slices in VITAL-5G testbeds	Onboard/Remove/Update network slice in VITAL-5G testbed (admin action) Get network slice information Get (filtered) list of network slices available in VITAL-5G testbeds
Access Control	User_Mgt: management of VITAL-5G users	Create/Remove/Update/Get user account (admin action) Create/Remove/Update/Get user profiles and user groups (admin action)
	Token_Mgt: management of tokens for authentication and authorization	Login / Logout Create / Refresh token
Vertical Service LCM	VS_Mgt: management of vertical service lifecycle	Instantiate/ScaleIn/ScaleOut/Configure/Terminate Vertical Service Instance Get (filtered) list of Vertical Service instances Get Vertical Service instance information Get NetApp instance information
Service Testing & Experiment Manager	Exp_Mgt: management of experiments	Create/Remove experiment Launch/Stop experiment execution Get experiment information and results Get (filtered) list of experiment
Service & Network Monitoring	Mon: retrieval of monitoring data	Read collected metrics and KPIs, on a per service and per experiment basis
Result Analytics	Res_Mgt: retrieval of experiment results	Get experiment results Get experiment execution results

6.3.6 Unified South-bound Interface towards VITAL-5G Testbeds

The South-bound Interface (SBI) of the VITAL-5G Platform enables its interaction with the VITAL-5G Testbeds, to support the following types of functionalities:

- The selection and/or management and configuration of network slices over the shared 5G infrastructure available in the VITAL-5G testbeds;

- The onboarding, provisioning and management of NetApps and Vertical Services to be deployed as VNFs and NFV Network Services in the virtual computing infrastructures offered by the VITAL-5G Testbeds;
- The collection of monitoring metrics from the 5G infrastructure, addressing both the 5G network performance or load and the usage of computing/storage resources of the virtual computing nodes where the NetApps are running.

Moreover, an additional interface may be provided as optional, to collect information related to the hardware devices (e.g., IoT sensors, AGVs, video cameras) installed in the T&L facilities at the VITAL-5G testbeds, with all the details required to properly interact with them. This interface can be considered as optional since, by default, the testbed administrator will configure the devices manually in the Multi-site Inventory using its NBI. However, in case of testbeds supporting open interfaces to access the inventory of the devices available there, automatic device discovery procedures can be implemented at the Multi-site Inventory to reduce the number of manual configurations required by the administrators.

Each VITAL-5G testbed implements its own NFV MANO orchestrators, slice management systems and monitoring platforms, each of them with their own interfaces. At the VITAL-5G Platform level, a unified SBI presents an abstract and common interface towards all the platform components that need to interact with the VITAL-5G testbed. Then, specific plugins and adaptors to be developed (where needed) in the context of WP3, will perform the translation towards the testbed-specific protocols and messages, as shown in Figure 31. From the perspective of the VITAL-5G Platform components, the VITAL-5G testbeds will thus appear as black boxes exposing a unified interface through their specialized plugins, independently of the variety of tools, platforms and systems implementing the actual functionalities.

Figure 31: VITAL-5G Platform South-bound Interface

Figure 31 represents the interfaces defined on the unified SBI, indicating their consumers on the VITAL-5G Platform side. The testbed-specific systems represented in the picture (i.e., Monitoring System, Slice Management System, NFV MANO System and their internal components) are provided just as examples; the decisions on the internal structure are delegated to each testbed, which can select their own solutions.

Table 14: VITAL-5G Platform South-bound Interface

Testbed system	Interface	VITAL-5G Platform Component	Main functionalities
NFV MANO System	Nfvo_cat: management of VNF packages and Network Service Descriptors.	NetApp Catalogue Service Catalogue	Onboard/Remove/Download VNF packages Get VNF package info Get VNFD Onboard/Remove/Get NSD Get (filtered) list of VNF package info Get (filtered) list of NSD
	Nfvo_lcm: Management of the lifecycle of NFV Network Services and configuration of their virtual functions	Vertical Service LCM Service Testing & Experiment Manager	Instantiate/ScaleIn/ScaleOut/Configure/Terminate NFV Network Service Instance Configure VNF instance Get (filtered) list of NFV Network Service instances Get Network Service instance information Get VNF instance information
5G Slice Management System	Slice_conf	Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory	Get (filtered) list of network slice instance Get network slice instance information Configure UEs for a network slice instance Create/Remove/Update network slice instance (optional, valid for testbed where on-demand network slice provisioning is supported)
Monitoring System	Mon_conf	Service & Network Monitoring (acting as consumer)	Create/Remove/Configure data source for computing infrastructure monitoring metric Create/Remove/Configure data source for network monitoring metric
	Mon_pub	Service & Network Monitoring (acting as provider)	Publish computing infrastructure monitoring metrics Publish network monitoring metrics

7. Design of VITAL-5G Testbeds and Trial Facilities

The VITAL-5G trial facilities are the Antwerp port, Galati port and Athens Diakinisis logistics hub will host the use cases that were designed within the project for implementing the VITAL-5G T&L technologies. These facilities will be supported by the pre-existing European 5G testbeds in Antwerp, Bucharest and Athens respectively. The 5G testbeds include the 5G network components that will be used in the 5G end-to-end infrastructure, as well as the end devices and the software and hardware that will support the development of the VITAL-5G NetApps.

This section focuses on the description of the VITAL-5G testbed and trial facilities design, where the general architecture of the facilities is analyzed, as well as the technology to be used. The VITAL-5G generalized architecture is discussed, where the 5G testbed and overall trial facility design is presented. In addition, information is provided on the interfaces and services offered, while the different levels of design (network, edge, management and orchestration) are described, as well as the facilities monitoring mechanism. Finally, the equipment that will be used to execute the use cases is presented, describing the advantages offered by its use.

7.1 A Generalized Model for VITAL-5G Facilities

This section presents how the vertical user (within the VITAL-5G or third party) may access the VITAL-5G trial facility through a dedicated portal via a dashboard or a programmatic API. The portal acts as an abstraction and aggregation layer across different domains of a 5G facility from Radio Access Network (RAN) to edge and core using orchestration services. It will interface with MANO and 5G RAN control systems where network slice creation, resource instantiation and data collection actions will be executed.

All the parties would benefit from improved quality of services provided by 5G NetApps running on top of an open, flexible and virtualized platform that allows onboarding, testing and validation of vertical specific and agnostic NetApps. Features like Network slice-as-a-service, edge computing, service orchestration, multi-tenancy are all necessary for providing superior resources availability and quality.

An online repository will manage onboarding procedures for NetApps, and the catalogue service will implement a programmable APIs to on-board, query, retrieve and update VNF packages, network slice and network service descriptors/service blueprints and a role-based access control to regulate access and actions permitted on NetApp packages.

All the testbeds and trial facilities will be validated through use cases and NetApps that require distributed sensor data collection, aggregation and post-processing for performing real-time control operations. Some of the most important KPIs of all the testbeds, described in D1.1 [1], would be service creation time, latency, reliability and sustained bit rate, as required by use cases specificity.

The high-level design of the Vital-5G facility as depicted in Figure 32 and defined by the proposed model will permit to the NetApp use cases and other 3rdparty experimenters to access the Vital-5G platform and 5G network components to run their specific application. The proper definition of the testbeds access, onboarding workflows and NetApps validation will be further detailed in D3.1.

Figure 32: Generalized Model for VITAL-5G Facilities

7.2 Services and interfaces offered by VITAL-5G Facilities

The VITAL-5G project creates a unique opportunity for SMEs to validate their T&L related solutions and services by accessing 5G testbeds (MNOs facilities) and T&L facilities through an open service validation platform, showcasing the added-value of 5G connectivity for the European T&L sector. All three VITAL-5G testbeds shall provide the NetApp developers and third party experimenters with the necessary testing and validation tools, as well as offering them a trusted and secure service execution environment.

The VITAL-5G system and facilities should provide 5G enhancements in terms of capabilities to onboard NetApps and deploy the services, LCM, visualize the data, as each facility provides a set of common functionalities toward the platform, implemented as Facilities Interfaces to the Platform for a set of mandatory functionalities:

- Orchestration
- Monitoring
- Slice Management and inventory
- Catalogues

As described in Section 6.3, the VITAL-5G Platform is performing in relation with the facilities and the NetApps services several 5G procedures and actions, summarized as:

- Instantiate and manage the vertical services

- Centralized monitoring platform, data visualization and service KPIs
- Service experiments execution
- 5G sites slice management and inventories

In order to fulfill this, starting from VITAL-5G Platform Software Architecture, several key services have been identified to be available at the Facility to VITAL-5G Platform, through RESTfull based interfaces, between the VITAL-5G Platform and VITAL-5G Testbeds designed as:

- **A-Interface:** the interface providing the facilities basic slice management information, acting like GET function to retrieve the 5G slicing characteristics of the facilities
 - In this context, the slicing is supposed to be manually configured (based on SST)
- **B-Interface:** the interface collecting the local facilities network and service KPIs, monitoring the facilities related parameters, by reusing the 5G-EVE already existing Kafka Broker
 - each VITAL-5G facility is presenting own monitoring tool and PUSH the data to the Centralized monitoring Platform
 - the interface exposes the network and the service data from 5G network elements as RAN, 5GC, Transport, Virtualized Infrastructure for service load (network resources, slice)
- **C-Interface:** the interface providing the NetApps experiment LCM, the NetApps Runtime configuration at facility level, facility orchestrator (OSM) related
- **D-Interface:** the interface providing NetApps and service orchestration, NFVO for services LCM(OSM)

The Platform to the Facilities interfaces are transported through the secured VPNs to the testbeds, further details and implementation activities related to the VITAL-5G Interfaces will be provided within WP3 deliverables. The above interfaces, along with the common blocks and those that may be differentiated between the testbeds through different technology and implementation are illustrated in Figure 33 below.

Figure 33: Vital-5G Architecture – functional blocks and interfaces

It is considered that each VITAL-5G facility has its own technology implementation (RAN, Core, Virtualization, Security) in terms of 5G infrastructure and network implementation, monitoring tools and related service KPIs.

The NFVO function is provided through OSM on each testbed, linked to the virtualized infrastructure for NetApps service deployment and to the VITAL-5G Platform through NBIs for NetApps configuration and NetApps service configuration. The C-Interface and D-Interface support the NetApps LCM and onboarding process, interfaces linked to the targeted facilities through the Restfull APIs.

RESTful standardizes protocols specification for D-Interface is the Os-Ma-nfvo OSM IFA013 SOL005 for CNF/VNF NFVO and for C-Interface is the Ve-Vnfm-em IFA008 SOL002 for NS LCM, for the two main functions: (1) On-board NSD and VNF Package and (2) VNF LCM. The 5G Services and interfaces offered by VITAL-5G Facilities ensures the proper Platform Integration for the required NetApps services onboarding and NetApps LCM, slice inventories, as highlighted in Figure 34.

Figure 34: Vital-5G Testbed services

7.3 VITAL-5G Testbeds Architecture

This section focuses on the description of the facilities that are used in VITAL-5G Use Cases. VITAL-5G architecture is separated in several infrastructure components. More specifically, in order to implement the facilities infrastructure, the design of the 5G network infrastructure as well as the cloud and edge infrastructure that will be implemented are required. Additionally, a management and orchestration and a testbed monitoring mechanism will be used to provide the necessary control of the facilities. Finally, end devices, sensors and IoT equipment will be used as part of the end-to-end facility architecture.

7.3.1 5G Network Infrastructure

The 5G Network Infrastructure is providing the technology capabilities in order to offer to the 5G Vertical’s users the required communication services with the support of the E2E network slicing, Network Function Virtualization, Management and Orchestration, Service Operation and Life Cycle Management, as depicted in Figure 35 [32].

Figure 35: 5G-PPPP Overall Architecture

The 5G Network Infrastructure (Figure 36) is composed by the main Resource Layer level and Network Layer level, each of these levels being composed in addition by the specific physical or virtual network elements and the logic network function for the targeted E2E service creation and services operation. The resource level is described by the 5G Radio access (gNBs), broadband transport network (IP/WDM network infrastructure), Cloud and Edge Cloud Computing infrastructure and the 5G Telco Cloud Network, including the tools for functions virtualization. The 5G network level is composed by the 5G Core functions (e.g. AMF, UPFs, SMF) that are running on top of the physical infrastructure (servers, cloud), utilizing the pool of resources from the Resource Functional level (VMs, CNFs, RAM, CPU, Network), presented as an abstract layer for the 5G Core network functions.

In VITAL-5G, the proposed Infrastructure, depicted in Figure 36, is indented to support E2E NetApps services operations, LCM and service RUN time configuration, with support of the 5G network architecture implementation:

- Management and orchestration, NetApps orchestration
- ETSI MANO system, Programable networks, SDN/NVFs, Automation
- Transport network orchestration
- 5G SA RAN Rel.16
- 5G Core, Service Based Architecture Rel 16
- E2E RAN and Core Slicing support, MEC extension for NetApps
- 5G Infrastructure monitoring, analytics functions
- Restfull APIs exposure and network interfaces exposure
- 5G Virtualized Infrastructure (Openstack/K8s)
- 5G security architecture
- In the VITAL-5G project, the key component from the architectural perspective is the 5G Core network, described as the 5G System. The 5G system is mainly based on a virtualized network, 5G Service Based Architecture, the modularized services, flexible and adaptable, on-demand networks, fast deployment cycles, dynamic services launch in the network and the Virtualization capabilities, introducing the slicing concepts with the ability of adapting to the services as network slices for each type of usage, with support of Network Function, based on Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (NSSI). The Service based architecture in 5G Rel 16 is illustrated in Figure 37.

Figure 36: VITAL-5G 5G Network Infrastructure

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Figure 37: Service based architecture in 5G Rel 16 [44]

Detailed descriptions of the VITAL-5G infrastructure and 5G Facilities will be provided in the next deliverables and activities, mainly in WP3 5G Testbed and Infrastructure Upgrades & Integration, deliverable D3.1 [33].

7.3.2 Cloud and Edge Infrastructure

Along with the 5G core network and edge network elements, each VITAL-5G testbed shall be equipped with the necessary infrastructure to support cloud and edge deployments along with the testbed-oriented components (Orchestrator, Monitoring, 5G Slice management, inventory, and Catalogue). While each testbed may deploy internally different 5G infrastructures, SDN technologies and monitoring platforms, they should expose a unified set of basic functionalities towards the VITAL-5G platform.

Cloud and edge workloads include the VITAL-5G NetApps which will be deployed and executed as virtual functions running in virtual computing resources. These computing resources are provided and managed by Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) such as OpenStack for VM-based virtual functions (VNFs) or Kubernetes for container-based virtual functions (CNFs). For container-based virtual functions there are two options in general:

- The first option for service providers with existing NFVI platforms is to add a container as a service (CaaS) platform on top of an existing VIM such as OpenStack.
- The second deployment option is to deploy CNFs over a bare metal infrastructure which may enable more efficient use of hardware and a simpler architecture.

The first option, as depicted in Figure, is an attractive option for those with stable working platforms and it allows multi-vendor VNF and CNF with full MANO and security and therefore it is the suggested testbed VIM architecture.

Figure 38: CNF and VNF on top of existing VIM

VIMs are also used for the organization of networks subnets and ports as well as the management of NFVI hardware resources (compute, storage, and networking).

Regarding hardware each testbed may choose to adopt different architectures. Hardware resources include racks, PDUs, as well as switches supporting the division of host (infrastructure) and guest (VNF) traffic into separate physical or virtual networks. The computing resources for a VIM-orchestrated computing cluster may include servers with multi-core CPUs, tens to hundreds of gigabytes of RAM, and HDDs in a reliable and performant RAID configuration. File and object storage may either be provided by a separate distributed cluster or using a Hyper Converged Infrastructure (HCI) with storage co-existing with compute nodes. Common hardware features include support for CPU Pinning, NUMA topology and SR-IOV.

Edge deployments may also be required to push the data collected from field through a service profile of an ultra-reliable service (URLLC) or greater data bandwidth (eMBB). Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine to Machine (M2M) services are typical examples of applications that can particularly benefit from running specific software components in the proximity of the network edge. Each edge site should support the steering of specific traffic flows towards the virtual applications running locally in the edge site, with the rest of the traffic proceeding towards the core. The computing resources placed at the edge of the network may also run network functions and local applications from the operator itself. An example architecture is depicted in Figure 39.

The edge sites are typically equipped with a limited amount of computing and storage resources but should be managed in a similar manner as the core infrastructure and expose a common interface to the NetApps and T&L service developers who should be able to choose the edge site for the deployment of NetApp components such as sensor aggregators and message brokers.

Figure 39: Example of distributed architecture with VNFs and CNFs running on both the core and the edge

7.3.3 Management and Orchestration

The VITAL-5G NetApps are deployed and executed as virtual functions (VMs or containers) running in virtual computing resources available in the VITAL-5G testbeds. Following the Network Function Virtualization approach, the NetApps and their associated services are managed through an NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) platform deployed in each testbed. This NFV MANO platform follows the high-level architecture defined in ETSI NFV (see Figure 40) and operates over an NFV infrastructure that integrates the computing nodes (see Section 7.3.3) where the NetApps are dynamically instantiated and orchestrated.

The MANO component in charge of orchestration is the NFV Orchestrator (NFVO), which provides the following functionalities:

- Onboarding of VNF packages and Network Service Descriptors, which in VITAL-5G corresponds to the virtual components of NetApps and Vertical Services, as discussed in the previous sections.
- Management of the lifecycle of NFV network services, including their instantiation, scaling, monitoring, self-healing and termination. Implicitly, through the network service lifecycle management, the NFVO coordinates also the lifecycle of the NetApps that compose the service.
- Configuration of the NetApps, through the Virtual Network Function Manager (VNFM).

The service lifecycle management coordinated by the NFVO is driven by the specification defined in the VNFDs and NSDs which are onboarded and stored in the NFVO catalogue. For example, during the service instantiation process, the NFVO creates and interconnects the VNFs on the basis of the virtual links and Virtual Deployment Units declared on the descriptors. The NFVO has also the capability to perform fault management, performance monitoring and performance-driven actions, e.g., triggering recovery procedures in case of failure of a VNF, scaling out in case more resources are needed, etc. The NFVO can interact with different Virtual Infrastructure

Managers (VIMs), which are in charge of managing the infrastructure resources. Examples of VIMs are OpenStack or Kubernetes and, in general, they can handle VM-based or container-based virtual functions. The VIMs are also used to configure the interconnectivity of services and NetApps, within the NFVI network and towards external networks. This is particularly relevant in VITAL-5G, since it allows the interconnection to the 5G infrastructure (at the data network level) of the various testbeds.

In general, the NFVO can interact with other external modules. For example, the configuration of the VNFs composing a network service is handled through the VNF Manager. Depending on the particular implementation, the VNFM can be embedded in the NFVO or external and it can adopt different techniques to configure the VNFs, e.g., via juju charms¹⁰ or REST API. Moreover, the NFVO can interact with external monitoring platforms for gathering and collection of performance metrics, e.g., related to resource usage at the VIM or VNF indicators. The data gathered can be used to trigger alarms or automate lifecycle management tasks related to scaling or recovery actions.

Figure 40: ETSI NFV Architecture (source etsi.org)

VITAL-5G testbeds adopt OpenSource MANO¹¹ (OSM) as reference NFVO for the instantiation of NetApps and Vertical Services. OSM implements VNFD and NSD data models and a REST-based interface compliant with the ETSI SOL specifications for the NFVO NBI, i.e., the os-ma reference point depicted in Figure 40. This interface is exposed from the VITAL-5G testbeds to the VITAL-5G platform, to enable the onboarding of NSD and VNF packages, as well as the request of lifecycle management actions on NFV network services and related NetApps. Moreover, OSM provides mechanisms to dynamically configure the VNFs. This feature is used by the VITAL-5G platform to re-configure or launch scripts on the NetApps as part of the test automation procedures.

¹⁰ <https://jaas.ai/>

¹¹ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

7.3.4 Monitoring

The monitoring component is a key service on both sides, test bed and VITAL-5G platform, enabling NetApps developers, test bed owners and third party experimenters to test their NetApps and services, diagnose a potential problem that may occur during the experiments or access information collected from previous tested services.

The monitoring data includes both network and service KPIs. The VITAL-5G test beds shall measure, collect and publish the 5G RAN, 5GCN and Transport KPIs and those related to virtual computing infrastructure, associated to the resources allocated and consumed for the NetApps/services deployment. Additionally, the service-level KPIs shall also be exposed to the VITAL-5G platform after NetApps/services being deployed on the VITAL-5G testbed (the NetApps must have service monitoring capabilities).

As mentioned in Section 7.2, the interface between the facility and VITAL-5G platform will reuse the 5G-EVE already existing Kafka Broker and through this interface each test bed shall present its own monitoring tool and shall push the data, in a unified format, to the VITAL-5G Centralized Monitoring Platform, thus enabling collection, storage, retrieval and visualization of both network and service KPIs.

Figure 41: Data monitoring solution High level architecture in Romanian facility

Belgian (Antwerp) testbed

The Antwerp testbed is capable of providing monitoring RAN, core and network E2E KPIs. The current monitoring tools available is based on 5G NSA while 5G SA tools are currently under design phase. The complete tool set includes network KPI and parameters directly from network management then translated into 5G VITAL KPIs, probing system implement on testbed, and third party tool for field test & drive tests.

- Network KPI monitoring: by monitoring O&M system of RAN, transport and core, following KPIs can be monitored.
 - User downlink/uplink data rate: including data rate per user, per application layer, per cell or per GNB.

- User downlink/uplink throughput: the amount of downlink data between two selected end-points of selected time window, per user or per cell.
 - Packet delivery ratio or package loss: ratio of package delivery or loss on RAN over a selected time window.
 - User plane latency: the time required to successfully deliver an application package over RAN in downlink/uplink directions.
 - Air interface setup success rate: NR or ENDC setup successful rate.
 - Resource allocation efficiency: efficiency of NR resource allocation such as PDSCH RB symbol utilization, PDSCH slot utilization, PUSCH RB symbol utilization and NR Scheduling efficiency
 - Network load: network load on RAN.
 - Handover success rate: ratio of successful handover event when UE moving across NR cells.
 - Network density: number of devices connected within a certain area, NB or cell.
- End to End monitoring from application backend or third party probing
 - Guaranteed data rate: the network guaranteed data rate over a network slice while application is functioning
 - Peak data rate: the network achieved max data rate over a network slice while application is functioning
 - E2E Latency: the time required for a data packet to go from application source to application destination.
 - Guaranteed latency: the guaranteed network latency over a network slice
 - Jitter: the variation in E2E latency.
 - Service interruption: the interruption on application layer due to network exceptions.
 - Reliability: the amount of application layer message successfully delivered over a selected time window.
 - Network coverage: the geographic area within which the Mobile Network Operator voice/data services can be accessed and used by the subscriber
 - Mobility: the availability of service over a certain UE mobility speed.
 - Mobility at speed: the max allowed speed at a required availability

Greek (Athens) testbed

Even though the 5G-SA testbed to be used in the Athens trial facility, will not include a default monitoring mechanism, several external monitoring tools (probes and a management server) are planned to be installed in order to provide KPI measurements. The monitoring tools could allow the accurate measurement of both the network parameters monitoring and the time relevant parameters (such as packet loss or latency). More specifically, these tools will provide values about:

- Throughput
- End-to-end latency
- RAN latency
- Packet Loss
- Data Rates
- Availability
- Jitter

The tools will be installed in several spots within the network, such as in the RAN and in the packet core, as it is presented in Figure 42.

Figure 42: GR testbed network topology with measuring tools included

Romanian (Galati) testbed

The Romanian 5G testbed is composed by several 5G architectural components, as 5G RAN and 5G Core (NSA and SA), broadband transport network and virtualized infrastructure based on a cluster of servers providing VNFs or CNFs, Openstack or Docker based, orchestrated by OSM/K8s. The level of the testbed monitoring capabilities is referring to the possibility to monitor and expose data from each relevant network element, that will be further exposed to the VITAL-5G platform. These capabilities are:

- RAN: per IMSI/linked to the slice: call success rate; drop call rate; data traffic volumes; average DL/user
- Transport: per slice: interfaces network load; packet loss; QoS; failures in the network; inventory database
- Core (5G SA Core):
 - General per system:
 - Status; Alarms;
 - Number of slices/average active users per slice
 - Active PDU sessions
 - Active QoS Flow; Data Networks
 - KPIs: PDU Sessions Success
 - PDU Session Failures
 - QoS Flow Success; QoS Flow Failures
 - Initiated PDU sessions
 - System Load
 - Per Slice:
 - Active Subscribers/Slice
 - Load
 - UDM subscribers
 - PDUs
 - QoS Flow
- IaaS/CaaS virtualized infrastructure:
 - NetApps: per VM/CN in the VITAL-5G tenant, per compute/server within the SFC: load; CPU; RAM; VM state
 - 5G Core Virtualized environment: per system load

Data Acquisition Layer is provided by Orange tools (Prometheus, StableNet) that are aggregated by Orange within a Data Processing environment and pushed to the VITAL-5G Platform.

7.4 Support of VITAL-5G Use Cases

Each VITAL-5G trial facility will use (and make available) a different set of devices/equipment in the field to be used during testing and experimentation. These devices could include IP cameras, environmental/fixed (IoT) sensors (e.g., infra-red, temperature, etc.), vessel/robot on-board sensors, end-devices (e.g., laptops, smartphones) and more. These devices can significantly differ among the different testbeds, as they are meant to support the execution of disjoint experiments in different T&L environments. Each of these devices will be able to be interfaced via (at least) one of the VITAL-5G NetApps on the portal, and to establish data exchange with it to be used during experimentation

An inventory of available devices will be exposed from each trial facility (through the VITAL-5G portal) along with their respective access level. Access to each of these devices will be strictly regulated via the portal's RBAC system and based on the user's/experimenter's profile and its associated access level/rights. As the use of some of these devices can be strictly regulated due to security/safety concerns (e.g., control of a vessel), access to some of the devices will be restricted to a limited number of authorized personnel from within the consortium. Each of the available devices will be linked to a certain platform user profile, which will indicate which users will have access rights to that specific device. This information will be displayed in the devices inventory of the portal, to facilitate the selection of appropriate devices for experimentation by internal and external consortium experimenters. The detailed list of available devices per VITAL-5G experimentation facility is provided in Section 7.4.

A description about the equipment that will be used in Use Cases is also provided in D1.1 [1].

7.4.1 Availability of Trial Facility Assets

Use Case 1 (Antwerp)

The purpose of 5G network in of Use case 1 is to provide connectivity towards the vessel and sensors either in vessel or along the waterway. Thus, 5G devices installed must support network frequency and network slice from the 5G network, while also support the maritime environment and provide addition connectivity to application devices. Typical application devices are cameras and monitoring sensors. Different application devices can be to one 5G UE or each application device use a dedicated 5G UE, depending on the best available physical installation approach on board, given the limited space/flexibility for cabling.

The 5G UE ideally support maximum IP68 level of protection, functions at a maximum 95% of humidity and -20 to 60 degrees of temperature. In addition, LAN and WAN ports are needed to extend the connectivity over cable and integrate with existing hardware. If needed in extreme scenario, multiple 5G UE with different configuration can be connected to a traffic aggregator for testing purpose. Regarding network slices, if one 5G UE (hardware or software version) does not fulfil the requirement of all network slices simultaneously, 5G device can be separated according to service type. For example, there could be one use case device installed on vessels to gather all traffic from camera, sensors and control units. Inside this use case device there will be three 5G UEs to support three or more network. The device solution is evolving quickly at the moment and will be further changed and refined during field trails

Use Case 2 (Galati)

The objective of Use Case 2 is focused on the implementation of a data-enabled assisted navigation application using IoT sensing system and video cameras installed in Galati port and on ships and barges (cargos). It will be achieved by a real-time connectivity of the radio and video navigation equipment respectively of the sensors that monitor the operating parameters of the ship with the dispatcher office, the safety and decision navigation

departments. All sensors and cameras will enable the interoperable wireless protocols over a private 5G network and will permit the extension of Internet connectivity of the sensing system. Several sensors, described in detail in D1.1 [1], such as GPS, humidity, smoke, engine power sensors located in the machine room, will be installed on the ship and barges and will provide relevant information such as velocity, heading, water and wind speed, etc. to the ship local monitoring equipment, allowing the captain and crew to take proper decisions and supporting on-board diagnosis. The crew will also have access to live video streaming from the surroundings through high definition video cameras in order to achieve high-resolution video streams, high connectivity and low latency that is uniquely offered by 5G. In addition, the dispatcher office or port safety/navigation offices which are farther away from the ship can benefit from receiving the data across the 5G link. The hardware components that will be used on the ship are described in detail in D1.1 [1].

The Galati port 5G testbed will be based on existing Orange 5G facility built with components from ICT-17's 5G-EVE project; it will be upgraded with additional 3GPP Rel.16 features and extended to provide coverage at the Galati port. A dedicated 5G site already deployed in Galati port for the two network slices, eMBB and URLLC for the NetApps data services and will be further integrated with 5G SA in Q1 2022.

Orange Romania facility will evolve during the life cycle of the project to a 5G infrastructure end state, able to address all NetApps project needs. The 5G E2E communication services are provisioned, and proper resources are configured through the 5G RAN and Core based on the predefined services catalogues. A set of 5G devices, UEs, CPEs and industrial CPEs to support Galati port use cases, for both NSA and SA 5G technologies are deployed benefiting by 5G Rel. 15/16 for URLLC/eMBB services with 5G RAN support: Samsung S21, Huawei CPE PRO2, Industrial 5G CP Sierra.

The evolution of Romanian facility deployment will consist of:

1. Deployment of 5G private standalone 3GPP Release 16 network (5G PMR SA) in H1 2022 in Galati running on dedicated virtualized infrastructure that will be integrated with the NetApps Cloud infrastructure in Bucharest. The 5G PMR will provide 5G SA connectivity, service network slice implementation for the eMBB/URLLC use case's communication needs.
2. 5G SA RAN and Core, Option 2, 3GPP Release 16 facility deployment planned to be finalized in H2 2022, based mainly on a virtualized network.

Use Case 3 (Athens)

The main target of Use Case 3 is to provide solutions that would optimise the processes within a warehouse. For that purpose, a 5G-connected Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV) will be used, which will be able to move on specific coordinates given by the employees or create its route automated based on the task assigned, transporting and lifting pallets and improving picking process.

Several extra equipment will be also used in the warehouse site, such as cameras, for monitoring the warehouse area, localization devices, for real time detection of the AGV's position and IoT sensors, for environmental measurements within warehouse, such as temperature and humidity. Additional equipment will be also available to be used by AGV, such as Lidar, cameras, sensors and barcode scanner, to let AGV monitor the area and the objects and offer security by calculate the distance between AGV and obstacles or human.

8. VITAL-5G Platform Components

The VITAL-5G Platform will consist of a Service Portal for NetApps lifecycle management and an Open Online Repository. The synergistic actions of these two components will allow VITAL-5G's vertical stakeholders, i.e., either members of the consortium or external users (e.g., third party NetApps developers), to design, on-board, instantiate, monitor/manage and benchmark their T&L NetApps.

8.1 VITAL-5G Portal

The VITAL-5G Portal will be the frontend to aggregate the individual components as described in the following subsections.

8.1.1 Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager

The Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager is the component that manages the lifecycle of Vertical Services composed of NetApps in the VITAL-5G platform. This component is triggered by the user through the VITAL-5G Platform Web GUI, to request the instantiation of a vertical service providing a set of service-level requirements declared in a Vertical Service Descriptor. When the vertical service is up and running, the user can request the execution of an experiment associated to it, which is then managed through the Service Testing & Experiment Manager component.

The Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager implements the logic for the selection, allocation and configuration of the resources required to build the service, acting as main coordinator for the service instantiation procedure described in the workflow in Section 6.3.4.2. In particular, it interacts with the other VITAL-5G platform components and with the NFVO at the target testbed, as follows:

- Retrieves the VSB and related NetApp blueprint from the related catalogues and translates the service requirements into the set of NFV network services, NetApps and 5G network slices required to build the service.
- Interacts with the Multi-Site Inventory to retrieve characteristics and capabilities of the target testbed and the endpoints to interact with its NFVO.
- Interacts with the Multi-Site 5G Network Slice Inventory to select, create or configure the required network slices in the target testbed, depending on its capabilities. For example, it may configure a pre-defined network slice to associate the User Equipment declared in the request. In case of testbeds supporting dynamic slice management, it triggers the creation of new dedicated network slices compliant with the service profiles defined in the NetApp blueprints.
- Interacts with the NFVO to request the instantiation of the NFV network service, its interconnection to the 5G network and the configuration of its NetApps. It monitors the status of the network service to verify its correct deployment and gathers all the details required to access the NetApps (e.g., the IP addresses which have been assigned dynamically at the VIM level).
- Interacts with the Service & Network Monitoring component to activate and configure the collection of the network and application KPIs declared in the NetApp blueprints.
- If needed, it interacts with the NetApp License Storage and Manager component to validate the licenses and verify the feasibility of the requested actions.

The Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager stores and manages the various service instances during their entire duration, handling the requests related to their scaling or re-configuration and keeping the synchronization with testbed NFVO. Moreover, it exposes APIs to retrieve the status and the details of the running services and their internal NetApps. This API can be invoked by the user (directly or via GUI) or other VITAL-5G platform components, e.g., the Service Testing & Experiment Manager, to receive updated information about service instances.

8.1.2 Service Testing and Experiment Manager

The Service Testing and Experiment Manager is a stand-alone software that provides support to the VITAL-5G platform for the creation and execution of the experiments. It is activated by the experimenter, by requesting an experiment execution once the related vertical service has been successfully instantiated by the Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager, as described in Section 8.1.1.

Figure 43: Service Testing and Experiment Manager stages

The service testing and experiment manager, as depicted in Figure 43, consists in four different stages, where each of them has a well-defined scope.

The first stage is the configuration of the experiment, which consists of configuring several elements, as follows:

- Configuration of the NetApps composing the service on the basis of the experiment configuration data provided by the vertical user;
- Configuration of the monitoring agents to allow the identification of the given experiment execution during the collection of the target KPIs;
- Configuration of other VITAL-5G platform components (e.g., Result Analytics and AI-based Diagnostic) to trigger the processing of the metrics, KPIs and data produced during the execution of the experiment.

The second stage involves the actual execution of the experiment. During this phase, the relevant metrics and KPIs will be generated from the service or the infrastructure (as defined in the NetApp blueprint) and collected by the components in charge of processing them on the basis of the indications provided in the experiment blueprint. As option, during this stage some testing scripts can be executed on the various NetApps to automate the execution of several testing steps. Alternatively, the experimenter will have secure access to the NetApp virtual machines to give manual commands.

The experiment execution can be terminated on-demand or on a timing basis, indicating the duration of the experiment. Once it is completed, the third stage of validation takes place. The Service Testing and Experiment Manager notifies the Result Analytics component to proceed with the validation of the KPIs, based on the metrics collected during the experiment execution. After the validation, the Service Testing and Experiment Manager collects and stores the experiment results and start the termination of the whole experiment, cleaning the previous configurations where needed. After the experiment termination, the vertical service will be ready for a new experiment execution.

8.1.3 Intent-based Interface for Experiment Requests

The portal and the API will expose an intent-based interface that will allow for the abstraction of the service description for the Vertical Service and autonomously transform service intents into 5G/NFV service descriptions and lifecycle management actions.

The start definition of an intent-based interface is given in [34], where it is stated that such an interface is used to express “what” its users “want to achieve”, instead of “how” to achieve it. The purpose is to improve the management of the network and to reduce the operational costs. This approach represents a novelty in the VITAL-5G project and it is a research problem in its infancy.

In the VITAL-5G portal the intent-based interface for Experiment Requests will try to convert the user generated intent (natural language) into a concrete executable network function [35]. Its purpose is to facilitate customer interaction in private networks. An intent message should be generated through this interface and if the internal command is part of the templates of functionalities that the system knows to implement, then it is implemented.

The intent-based interface has the purpose to enable “declarative intent expressions” to build “service-oriented intents with different targets” [34]. This type of interface should be used by actors that are not network experts. The main feature on which this type of interface is based on the requests for different service demands named *intents*. The challenge in the implementation of such an interface is the implementation of the linkage between the “high-level targets in terms of business objectives” and the “lower-level management policies and operations” [34]. The purpose of an intent-based interface is to develop a more rapid network management, service deployment and without human intervention. Thus, though an intent a user can express some outcomes that he requests to the system.

The novelty of the VITAL-5G project is the fact that it builds a network for transport and logistics that is based on 5G experimentation facilities. The intent-based interface should be able to respond at transport and logistic related business objectives to low level networking operations that are unknown to the business users. In [34] the intent-based interfaces are classified in two main categories: client-facing service-layer implementations and operator-facing resource-layer ones. The intent-based solutions translate high level requests of the users of the VITAL-5G platform into low level networking commands.

Next, we propose an architecture for the intent-based interface for experiment requests. This is shown in Figure 44

Figure 44: An architecture for the VITAL-5G intent-based interface for T&L experiment requests

The proposed architecture has three different layers:

1. The Business operations layer. This layer has the purpose of collecting intent-based operations from the business users and sending them to the intent-based analysis layer.
2. The intent-based analysis layer is the most important functional part of the architecture. It contains 4 components:
 - a. The AI-based inference engine that takes the intent-based user requests and based on the intent-based user requirements database and the 5G operations database transforms the requests in commands and sends them to the agents that send the commands to the 5G network.
 - b. The intent-based user requests database contains the possible user requests that need to be compared to the business user requests from the business operations layer by the AI-based inference engine
 - c. The 5G network operations database component is used to transform the intent-based user requests in 5G network command by analyzing the operations available in this database by the AI-based inference engine

- d. The agents represent functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform that send commands to the 5G network. The commands come from the AI-based inference engine.
- 3. The 5G layer represents the actual 5G network that can receive commands based on the intent-based interface. The results of the execution of the commands will be useful for improving the AI-based inference engine.

The intent-based application will abstract experiment specification through intent-based mechanisms. For example, a use-case implemented in the VITAL-5G as an intent-based NetApp creation is the tracking of the 5G service in a smart transport scenario. We can extend the use case about the intelligent railway for smart mobility use case from the 5G EVE project to implement the use case specific for the VITAL 5G project. An example of the envisioned intent-based functionalities based on the implementation of the 5G EVE project can be seen in Figure 45, while the resulting 5G EVE blueprint is presented in Figure 46.

Tracking Service Guided Selection

Select the attributes you want your Blueprint to have

Select the country you want to run the experiment:	Select the date you want the experiment to be executed:
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Italy	Day: <input type="text" value="1"/> Month: <input type="text" value="1"/> Year: <input type="text" value="2019"/>
Select the country you want to run the experiment from:	Select the time you want the experiment to be executed:
<input checked="" type="radio"/> France <input type="radio"/> Greece <input type="radio"/> Italy <input type="radio"/> Spain	Hour: <input type="text" value="0"/> Minutes: <input type="text" value="0"/>
Number of Devices (smartphones):	
<input type="text" value="1"/>	
Make sure to that the devices include the following sensors	

Figure 45: An intent based blueprint for the 5G EVE platform

The 5G EVE intent based platform will be modified to implement experiment requests about several use cases related to the T&L domain. For example, the VITAL 5G implementation will be able to deal with tracking T&L 5G environments. The VITAL-5G intent-based environment will deal with service sizing and scaling based on the service description. The 5G EVE implementation will be enhanced with functionalities for implementing specific 5G network topologies and configurations capable of delivering the desired performance.

The VITAL-5G intent based functionalities are used to implement various parameters associated with the 5G network. For example, video streaming and data coming from different sensors (GPS, humidity, smoke, velocity, etc.) are transmitted to the navigation centre using wireless protocols over a private 5G network and permit the extension of the Internet connectivity of the sensing system to be used by specific applications, e.g., assisted navigation for avoiding collisions, diagnosis, etc.

Tracking Service Blueprint Created

If the Blueprint satisfies your needs please press confirm, otherwise press the edit button to modify the blueprint

Blueprint Information	
Name	<i>5G EVE tracking service</i>
Description	<i>Integration of 5G data and mobility data from different transport operators</i>
Version	<i>1.0</i>
Identity	<i>BP Identity</i>
Sector	<i>Smart Transport</i>
Launched from	<i>France</i>
Executed to	<i>Italy</i>
Date of Execution (dd/mm/yyyy)	<i>3/5/2022</i>

Figure 46: The results of the 5G EVE tracking service

8.1.4 Network KPIs Collection and Service Monitoring

This is an important component of the VITAL-5G Portal Backend and refers to a centralized monitoring platform that allows for the collection of data referring to:

- Varying T&L type of facilities, i.e., sea or river ports and warehouses, and NetApp components;
- Different 5G infrastructures and therefore different network/virtual computing KPIs to be monitored;
- Specific T&L devices, depending on the facility in question.

It further interacts with the Service Testing and Experiment Manager as the latter triggers the monitoring of the related KPIs during the experiment execution over a running vertical service.

The KPI collection is done through the southbound interfaces with the monitoring components in the various testbeds for the acquisition of data. The envisaged approaches for accessing this information are two:

1. HTTP REST services, where an HTTP REST API is utilized to directly query the data source in question;
2. Message bus services, where the data source exposes and provides a message bus itself for the data to be fetched. Related technologies that are widely used in the industry and will be supported are Apache Kafka [36] and RabbitMQ [37].

Furthermore, this component, depending on the given parameters and monitoring mechanisms' capabilities, may be able to acquire information at (a) different rates and (b) through different mechanisms, i.e.:

1. A periodical acquisition of data through a polling process;
2. The acquisition of streaming data based on the pub-sub (Publish-Subscribe) paradigm, i.e. receiving messages in a continuous manner by a publisher based on the given topics requested by the subscriber;

3. An asynchronous request-response approach for acquiring data once-off.

The data collection interaction can be initiated by the monitoring component itself (active) or by the various testbeds (passive approach), e.g., as the publishers of network/ virtual computing and service KPIs.

In addition to the above, the component also refers to a persistence entity where both network KPI and service monitoring information is ingested, stored and then retrieved for fusion of data and post-processing. The different functionalities support the manipulation of both structured and unstructured data given the diversity of the T&L devices. These functionalities are described in Table 15.

Table 15: Persistence and message queue functionalities

Functionality Description	Type
Persist multi-dimensional datasets of numerical and categorical features	Data Persistence
Persist unstructured or semi-structured data	Data Persistence
Query for multi-dimensional datasets of numerical and categorical features	Data Retrieval
Query for unstructured or semi-structured data	Data Retrieval
Transformation of an unstructured object into a multidimensional structured dataset	Data Transformation
Transformation of multidimensional tabular-based datasets into semi-structured or unstructured form	Data Transformation
Translation of a dataset/ object to a specific format (dataset/ object respectively)	Data Transformation
Create topic	Message bus-related
Destroy topic	Message bus-related
Consume message queue for real-time data acquisition	Message bus-related
Produce message queue for exposing to internal components	Message bus-related
Produce message queue for exposing to third parties/ verticals	Message bus-related
Conversion of message queues into entries to existing schemas	Interoperability
Conversion of mini-batch data to message queue events	Interoperability

The aforementioned functionalities require a big-data lake, a distributed file system, which will allow for storage of structured and unstructured data with high-throughput read/ write operations and for other query engines and SQL interfaces to perform SQL-like operations. In this context, the selected de-facto industry standards are the Apache HDFS [39] storage layer coupled with Apache Hive [40], an SQL tabular data storage layer, and Trino [41], an open source distributed query engine.

Lastly, data can be visualized through the VITAL-5G dashboard (see Section 8.1.5) or, through the programmable interfaces offered, they can expose to third parties (subject to access control mechanisms) other platform components, namely Result Analytics, AI-based Diagnostics, AI-based Placement, and LCM Management.

8.1.5 KPIs Analytics and Automated Service Performance Diagnostic

The VITAL-5G dashboard will also offer tools for KPI monitoring and analysis, taken from 5G EVE and integrated in order to adapt to the VITAL-5G operation context. The Service Portal will interface with the underlying local MANO and NG-RAN control systems available at the trial facilities, through the Service & Network Monitoring component (see Section 8.1.5), where the primitive actions of network slice creation, resource instantiation and data collection for monitoring will be executed as a result of the lifecycle management in the Service Portal.

In this respect, the VITAL-5G Portal serves as an abstraction and aggregation layer across different domains of a 5G facility (5G RAN, edge/core based on NFV MANO).

More specifically, the dashboard metrics/KPIs refer to:

- The monitoring data collected through the Service & Network Monitoring component in order to compute/ perform analytics on the experiment results; and,
- The monitoring data and the experiment results which through AI-based techniques allow for the extraction of advanced experiment diagnostics.

Thus, the dashboard itself presents metrics as well as aggregation of metrics and KPIs, utilizing fusion schemes performed through complex data pipeline processes and Artificial Intelligence (AI)/ Machine Learning (ML) models, for the appropriate visualization and graphical representation of the metrics/ data and diagnostics.

Overall the selected technologies should support the following:

- Building from simple to highly complex processes for the creation of data pipelines, invoking computing tasks that read/ write large amounts of data;
- Deployment and production-readiness of AI/ML-models, model repository functionality and storage of model performance metrics, such as accuracy, recall and others, to maintain model performance.

The aforementioned will be supported through Apache Airflow [42] for the creation of the data pipeline processes, and ML-Flow [43] for the deployment and production-readiness of ML models. The Machine Learning and /or Deep learning framework will be chosen based on the best AI/ML approaches that will be decided through the R&D work.

8.1.6 AI/ML techniques in support of lifecycle management and diagnostics

The decision on placement of VNFs/VxFs related to the NetApps and re-optimization of the instantiated services will be assisted by Artificial Intelligence (AI) & Machine Learning (ML) algorithms that will allow for the mix of real-time monitoring data on resources, services and models to plan appropriate optimizations.

This will be done through the AI-based Placement & LCM Logic component. More specifically, this component is optionally invoked by the Vertical Service LCM responsible for the instantiation, management and termination of vertical services, NFV-NSs and network slices.

In order to achieve this (as in the case of KPI analytics and service-related analytics described in the previous section), the following apply:

- Monitoring data on resources and services will be employed, fused and further analyzed through simple and/or complex data pipelines;
- Advanced AI/ ML techniques will provide the appropriate diagnostics that will support the optimal placement of NetApp components or the automation of the execution of service scaling actions; and
- Deployment and production-readiness of AI/ML-models will be essential.

The monitoring data will be acquired through the Service & Network Monitoring component (see Section 8.1.4) and Apache Airflow [42] will allow for the data pipeline processes. With respect to AI/ML-assisted diagnostics MLflow [43] will be utilized along with an optimization framework, namely Optuna [38]. The latter is framework agnostic, i.e., it may be used with any ML/AI framework and allows for automated search for optimal hyperparameters with state-of-the-art algorithms.

8.2 VITAL-5G Open Online Repository

The VITAL-5G Open Online Repository is one of the core components of the VITAL-5G Platform, providing the catalogue of the NetApps developed in the context of the project and giving the opportunity to third party experimenters and developers to download and select them for the experimentation, as well as to onboard their own NetApps to build new vertical services and validate them using the VITAL-5G experimentation functions. The Open Online Repository is composed of three different catalogues, i.e., the NetApps Catalogue (described in Section 8.2.1), the Vertical Services Catalogue and the Experiments Catalogue (both described in Section 8.2.2), offering features for querying and onboard NetApp packages, Vertical Service Blueprints and Descriptors, as well as Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors, together with their associated VNF packages and NFV Network Service Descriptors. NetApp packages, blueprints and descriptors can be declared as public, so that they become available for all the users of VITAL-5G, including third parties, and they can be re-used freely to create new services and experiments. Others can be declared as restricted, limiting their visibility and access to a set of user groups or just to their owner. Following this approach, the NetApp, Service or Experiment owner can freely decide the level of openness that he/she wants to grant to his/her own software and artifacts, in compliance with different business strategies. The three catalogues are complemented with two additional components for (i) the management of software licenses associated to proprietary NetApps (Section 8.2.3) and (ii) the preliminary validation of NetApp packages in terms of format and compliance with the capabilities of the VITAL-5G testbed and trial site where the NetApp is supposed to run (Section 8.3.4).

8.2.1 NetApps Catalogue

The NetApps Catalogue offers the centralized access point to browse the NetApps available in the VITAL-5G Platform and to onboard new NetApps developed from partners of the VITAL-5G consortium or third-party software developers.

The NetApp Catalogue stores the NetApp packages (see Section 5.2) and maintains the synchronization with the NFVO catalogues of the VITAL-5G testbeds to keep the map with the VNF packages corresponding to the NetApps. At its NBI, the NetApp Catalogue offers mechanisms to onboard new NetApps, query the existing ones specifying filtering criteria (e.g., per vendor, per site, per category, etc.), download a NetApp package or retrieve its NetApp blueprint, as well as remove and update NetApps. The NetApp Catalogue NBI is based on programmable and open REST APIs, to enable a simple integration with external third-party software. Moreover, on top of the REST API, the VITAL-5G Platform web GUI offers a graphical interface to simplify the manual interaction with the catalogue. The web GUI allows users to browse the list of available NetApps, to set the appropriate filters, to provide a graphical visualization of the NetApps, with their atomic components, their internal interconnectivity as well as their external connections, including the one towards the 5G network with the related requirements and slice profiles. Moreover, the GUI can integrate tools and wizards to facilitate the creation of the NetApp Package, guiding the user in the steps to add all the required elements and fill the various fields of the NetApp blueprint.

Internally, the NetApp catalogue interacts with the Access Control (Section 8.3.1) component to authenticate and authorize the requests according to the user profile and group. Each NetApp declares an access level,

encoded in its blueprint, which specifies the level of visibility permitted to different users. In particular, the access level of a NetApp can be:

- Private: the NetApp is visible and can be downloaded and instantiated only by the user that has created and onboarded it;
- Restricted: the NetApp is visible and can be downloaded and instantiated only by the users participating in the use case(s) the NetApp is associated to;
- Public: the NetApp is visible and available for everyone, including third-party experimenters. If public, a NetApp can be used to build any kind of vertical service, without restrictions on the use cases the service is associated to.

The workflow to onboard a new NetApp is described in detail in Section 6.3.4.1. The schemas of the NetApp blueprint can be downloaded through the web GUI to facilitate the offline definition of new NetApps. Moreover, the interaction with the NetApp Validator (Section 8.2.4) allows verification of the correct format of NetApp package and NetApp blueprint at the onboarding time and its compatibility with the features, capabilities, and devices available in the target testbed. If requested, the NetApp Validator can also trigger a default testing deployment of the NetApp in the virtual computing environment, to verify its correct instantiation.

Internally, the NetApp Catalogue is structured in two components: a file repository for storing the NetApp packages and an SQL database for storing high-level information about NetApp packages, as well as the details of the NetApp blueprints. During the NetApp package onboarding, the package file is unzipped and the NetApp blueprint file is parsed, validated and stored in the SQL database. This approach allows its information to be indexed in a more efficient manner, simplifying the querying of particular NetApp blueprint elements and the verification of their relationships. In case of proprietary software licenses, the generic template of the license information is stored in the file repository. Then, it will be up to the NetApp developer (acting as software vendor) to onboard on the License Manager (see Section 8.2.3) the licenses issued for the various users of the NetApp.

8.2.2 Vertical Services and Experiments Catalogue

The Vertical Service Catalogue stores Vertical Service Blueprints (VSB) and Vertical Service Descriptors (VSD), which have been introduced in Section 5.3, and manages the synchronization with the NFVO catalogues of the VITAL-5G testbed where the corresponding NFV Network Service Descriptors (NSD) are stored. As for NetApps, VSBs and VSDs can be declared as public, restricted or private, limiting accordingly the access rights for the various users. In particular, during the onboard procedure, the catalogue logic verifies the consistency of the access rights declared for the vertical service with the ones declared for the NetApps composing it. For example, a vertical service declared as public can only include public NetApps. Similarly, a vertical service restricted for a given use case can only include NetApps which are declared as public or as restricted for the same use case, etc. User authentication and authorization are performed interacting with the Access Control component (Section 8.3.1), as for all the other VITAL-5G Platform procedures.

The onboarding procedure of a VSB takes as input the VSB itself, the associated NSD and, as option, custom translation rules to drive the mapping between a VSD built on the given VSB and the characteristics of the corresponding NFV network service, based on the given NSD (see Section 5.3 for further details). In practical terms, a translation rule specifies the map between acceptable value ranges for the VSB service parameters (to be defined by the user in the VSD as part of the service customization) and the corresponding NSD's deployment flavour and instantiation level to be used to instantiate the service. However, the declaration of translation rules is not mandatory; if absent, the default deployment flavour and instantiation level will be used during the deployment of the service. This approach allows support of different levels of users' expertise and expectation, with developers and service providers interested in evaluating the performance of their NetApps and Services for variable flavours (e.g., varying the number of NetApp instances, or the size and virtual resources assigned to their VMs) and other simply focusing on the validation of a single and static deployment.

The onboarding of a VSB can involve the onboarding of a new NSD or simply refer to an NSD already available in the NFVO catalogue of the target VITAL-5G testbed. In this sense, the Vertical Service Catalogue acts as a mediator for the interaction between the user and the NFVO catalogue on the VITAL-5G site. In fact, the VITAL-5G user can browse and query the NSDs stored on the various testbeds interacting directly with the single access point offered by the Vertical Service Catalogue. Moreover, during the VSB onboarding procedure, the Vertical Service Catalogue will coordinate the onboarding of the new NSD or verify the presence of the referred one on the target NFVO, as shown in Figure 47.

The interaction with the target NFVO is fully wrapped and, where needed, the NSDs are translated to/from the ETSI SOL 006 [30] format adopted as unified data model in VITAL-5G. This format is also adopted in OSM, the NFVO currently planned for all the three VITAL-5G testbeds. However, the adoption of different NFVOs is not prevented and it would be supported through a dedicated SBI plugin to implement the required translation and adaptation (see Section 6.3.6 for the plugin-based design of the unified VITAL-5G Platform SBI).

The Experiment Catalogue stores Experiment Blueprints (ExpB) and Experiment Descriptors (ExpD) and follows the same access rules of the other catalogues, classifying the items in public, restricted and private. ExpBs and ExpDs are maintained locally at the Experiment Catalogue (i.e., without further onboarding towards the testbeds) and they are queried by the Service Testing and Experiment Manager to retrieve the information required to create and launch the experiment instances.

Figure 47: VSB onboarding

8.2.3 E-License Manager

The VITAL-5G Platform aims to provide e-licensing mechanisms in order to support proprietary NetApps that require the validation of their software license when they are deployed in a virtual computing infrastructure of

a VITAL-5G testbed, during their instantiation and orchestration procedures. This functionality is suitable for all the scenarios where a NetApp developer desires to grant in a limited way the right to use a proprietary NetApp to other stakeholders, especially third-party experimenters, which may want to profit from already available NetApps.

For this reason, the Open Online Repository includes an E-license Manager with a catalogue of different types of e-licensing models which can be associated to the NetApps. The NetApp developers will be able to specify their e-licenses, based on these generic models, as part of the NetApp package which is onboarded in the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository. An e-license can be associated to a NetApp as a whole or, in case of NetApps with multiple atomic components, to one or more components.

The VITAL-5G Platform addresses the management of e-licenses associated to the lifecycle of the NetApps (e.g., related to the number of NetApp instances deployed in the environment for a given user, to the duration of this deployment, etc.), considering the internal applications running in the NetApps components as transparent. Other types of licenses associated to the application software itself and managed as part of the software execution are typically handled with proprietary mechanisms by the software provider and they are out of the scope of the VITAL-5G Platform.

The VITAL-5G e-license manager supports three types of license models, roughly inspired by the VNF licensing models defined in ETSI. In particular, the following models are identified:

- Flat: A license is bought at a fixed price and it gives perpetual right to use the software.
- Subscription: A license gives right to use the software for a given certain period of time.
- Usage-based: A license grants perpetual use of the software given a certain metric (also called pay-as-you-go license). While in ETSI this model is mostly related to software-oriented metrics (e.g., number of users), in VITAL-5G the focus is on metrics associated to the deployment of the NetApps, i.e., the number of concurrent instances or the dimension of the virtual resources allocated to run the NetApp.

The management of the licenses imposes a number of challenges for the orchestration and lifecycle management of the related NetApps. In fact, depending on the particular license model, the lifecycle actions must be regulated on the basis of the permissions granted by the license owned by the user. This license is identified by an E-License Key, owned by the user requesting the vertical service, which is provided as part of the service instantiation request and used by the Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager to validate the various steps of the service lifecycle interacting with the E-license Manager. In particular, depending on the license type, the following checks are performed:

- Flat model: The Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager verifies the validity of the key at the beginning of the service instantiation procedure. If valid, all the service lifecycle actions are considered permitted.
- Subscription: The Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager verifies the validity of the key at the beginning of the service instantiation procedure and retrieves the maximum duration permitted for the given service, starting a timer. At the expiration of the timeout, if the service is still up and running, it is automatically terminated.
- Usage-based: The Vertical Service Lifecycle Manager verifies the validity of the key at the beginning of the service instantiation procedure and retrieves the metric to be evaluated to determine the feasibility of the service. In this case, the validation of the license depends on concurrent instances already running for the same user and it must be evaluated again before performing any upscaling action on the service.

8.2.4 NetApps Validator

The NetApps Validator is a stand-alone component of the VITAL-5G platform with the purpose of validating the NetApps from both syntax and deployment perspectives.

The NetApps Validator offers a REST API interface that can be invoked by the VITAL-5G Platform Web GUI to perform a live validation of the format of blueprints and descriptors that the users will try to onboard for their NetApps and services. The validation of these components will be performed based on the data model schema of the related component. Only in the case of valid data being provided, the VITAL-5G web GUI will allow the user to proceed further in the onboarding procedure. In case of failure, an error message will notify the user, and the procedure will be stopped. The vertical users will have the opportunity to validate their blueprints and descriptors not only during the onboarding phase, but in any moment, performing the validation of their models in a dedicated page of the GUI.

The NetApps Validator is also able to provide to the users with the latest version of the data model schemas, facilitating the creation of blueprints and descriptors. Based on these schemas, the user can generate with third party tools a basic blueprint or descriptor to be used as baseline for further customizations. The NetApps Validator offers also the possibility to generate basic VNFDs and NSDs, starting from a given NetApp or Vertical Service blueprint, respectively.

From the deployment perspective, the NetApps Validator will perform a testing service instantiation during the NetApp onboarding, if required, upon trigger from the NetApp catalogue. The instantiation of the NetApp will be performed in a testing environment with the objective of verifying the NetApp creation in the declared testbed. This will allow the VITAL-5G platform to verify if the required descriptors and images are correctly in place in the local orchestrator and in the local VIM.

8.3 VITAL-5G Platform Internal Tools

As previously mentioned, most of the VITAL-5G portal components will be based on assets from 5G EVE, that will be customized to VITAL-5G's needs [3]. The following subsections will describe their relevance and use within the project.

8.3.1 Access Control

One of the integral assets to securing the platform is the Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), which will enable the authentication and authorization of all requested actions received from the backend. Management of user roles will be through Identity and Access Management (IAM) service that will enable creating, merging, reading, updating and deleting users and their corresponding authentication tokens. This token-based authentication process will be valid for a certain period of time in order to create a secured environment where the users will be able to fetch specific resources and NetApps from the portal backend either as a single user or a group of users. The RBAC will also allow creating and closing user sessions and refreshing access tokens. This access control functionality will be made available to the backend components (e.g. e-LCM, NetApps Validator) via a REST API.

Figure 48: Example of the token-based affiliation process [3]

Furthermore, RBAC will create an affiliation process, in which different roles will be assigned to the different types of users and groups. The affiliation process is shown in Figure 48, whereby registering the different backend components (e.g., e-LCM, NetApps Validator) directly at the IAM we can create a trusted service environment. Each service will be able to validate user requests and retrieve information about the owner of the token, which can be a single user or a group. Also, the trusted components can create their own roles at different levels: (i) site-specific level and (ii) client level. The former refers to a specific “realm” of the Vital-5G portal, where all the related services (e.g., e-LCM, NetApps Validator, etc) will be placed at the same realm. As for the latter case, by client level we mean that the roles available in a certain directory will be dedicated to a single client, and all the services of the VITAL-5G portal will be clients of Keycloak¹² in order to be able to set their own set of roles.

8.3.2 Load balancing and API proxy

The load balancing function distributes loads of incoming user requests by routing to the closest backend from the user on case-by-case basis. This function not only ensures smooth management of requests vs responses but also a consistent user experience with the platform. Different load balancing strategies will be employed by the VITAL-5G portal like the least connections load balancing, which assigns each new request to the server with the fewest outstanding (queued) requests. Additionally, an API proxy will be used as a simple lightweight API Gateway to add security and additional monitoring capabilities.

¹² <https://www.keycloak.org/>

8.3.3 Common Logging

This component will collect all the data produced by the various users on the platform and normalize their format homogeneously. This data collected will include user (role) types, activity on platform: services, NetApps, and experiments created and/or instantiated, in addition to relevant experimentation results and KPIs. This log data will be stored on the Elasticsearch (ES) database, which is part of the Elastic-Logstash-Kibana (ELK¹³) stack that is integrated into the platform for the monitoring of the experiments and analysis of their performance. The Kibana component of the stack will be responsible for the monitoring and visualization of the data, through default but customizable widgets that produce live charts, graphs, and data tables, among others.

8.3.4 Name Resolution Service

The Vital-5G portal will use a Name Resolution Service (NRS) to convert names of resources into IP addresses and vice versa in order to interconnect all the users with the available resources. The most common method is called Domain Name System (DNS) name resolution that provides a way to look up name mappings over a network.

8.3.5 VITAL-5G Testbeds Inventory

VITAL-5G use cases will be hosted in three different sites: Port of Antwerp, Galati Port on Danube River, Athens logistics hub. In each site, a 5G SA Rel.16 testbed will be integrated. The testbeds consist of both hardware and software elements and an inventory of these elements is necessary as the initial part of the testbed integration strategy.

The main architecture layers of the testbeds are the RAN, the packet core, the edge, the transport network and the OSM. Each layer includes both hardware and software elements (e.g., hardware elements are the NR and the packet core, while software elements are the VNFs that will be created). In Table 16 a list of the key hardware and software components of the testbed(s) is provided.

Table 16: VITAL-5G testbeds inventory

Architecture layer	Hardware	Software
RAN	NR (antenna, BBU, RU)	RAN VNFs
		3GPP Rel. 16
edge	MEC	Edge VNFs
transport	POTP	VLANs
5GC	5G SA packet core (UPF, NSSF, AUSF, NRF,UDM, SMF, UDR)	Core VNFs
		3GPP Rel. 16
Management and Orchestration	OSM	Monitoring, NFV MANO, Slice manager, Controller

¹³ <https://www.elastic.co/>

8.4 VITAL-5G Web-based Graphical User Interface

For building the Vital-5G Portal Web GUI we will utilize resources available from the 5G-EVE project. Figure 49 shows the home page of the portal with 4 distinct buttons. The Design Experiment button (green colour) will offer the needed functionalities to the experiment developer to design blueprints and generate the corresponding NSDs, including the thereafter blueprint and NSD descriptors validation. More specifically, the web GUI will offer the following functionalities to the Vital-5G experimenters:

- Vertical Service Blueprints,
- Execution Context Blueprints,
- Testcase Blueprints,
- Experiments Blueprints,
- Virtual Network Functions,
- Network Services,
- Support Tools.

Additionally, through the Request Experiments button (yellow button) the users will be able to request an experiment that will support the creation of various descriptors: i.e., Vertical Service, Context, Test-Case and Experiment Descriptors. The third button of the home page is called “Manage Experiments” (red button) that will display the status of the requested experimented (e.g., “SCHEDULED”, “ACCEPTED” or “READY”). Furthermore, as the experiment is running the user will be able to view monitoring metrics and KPIs that were set in the Design Experiment stage.

The fourth button is called “Manage Site” (blue colour). Through this button the UC manager will be able to inform the user for the availability of the required experiment resources are available in order the user to deploy and execute the requested experiment.

Figure 49: The home page of the Vital-5G portal web GUI [3]

9. Conclusions

The system specifications and architecture presented in this report provides a detailed view of the conceptual and technical vision of the future VITAL-5G Open Platform and Repository. It consolidates the work done during this first year of the project and by taking into account the use case requirements (Business, Application and Network) stated in D1.1 to identify the platform requirements, lays the foundations for its development.

The proposed service-oriented architecture, taking advantage of previous 5G PPP projects, will be used to release a flexible platform adapted to serve the specific needs of the Transport & Logistics (T&L) sector. Description of the NetApps, Experimentation Services and the involvement of third parties will support the validation of T&L Vertical solutions and applications in real-life conditions along the 3 Use cases selected. In addition, general architecture of the facilities is analyzed providing information on the interfaces and services offered, as well as the facilities monitoring mechanism.

Finally, the proposed architectural design includes the description of the Open Online Repository, core components of the VITAL-5G Platform, providing the list of the NetApps, Vertical Services and Experiments catalogue developed in the context of the project giving the opportunity to third party experimenters and developers to download and test them using the VITAL-5G experimentation functions.

The results of the description of the VITAL-5G Platform will be used in WP2 and WP3 to develop the VITAL-5G Platform components, testbeds and the end-to-end VITAL-5G system integration.

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Annex I: Standards and conventions

The VITAL 5G open service validation platform requires a strong emphasis on standards enforcement to enable secure, reliable, interoperable solutions in order to achieve reliable exchange of information and effective processing of data to validate services execution under realistic conditions. This annex provides the general guidelines that will be followed to implement the vision of the open platform and information architecture.

Exchange Formats

As a general rule, the preferred format for data exchange and representation in the VITAL 5G platform will be *REST APIs based on HTTP* for structured data.

Encodings

The encoding for all textual data in the platform is JSON or YAML. All documents, subsystems and tools will be configured to accept and emit JSON or YAML and ensure correct handling of the diverse content

Compression

For systems in the platform that use it, the compression standard will *be .tar.gz files*, which is widely supported, is cross-platform and offers reasonable performance and compression ratio.

Namespaces

For formats that allow/require namespaces, the canonical namespace root for document data is <https://www.vital5g.eu/>. Definitions of entities and their members should be nested under the canonical root.